

An evaluation of innovative marketing strategies employed to recruit Colombian students into the UK higher education sector. A proposal for developing guidelines to select marketing strategies to increase recruitment and retention

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on Colombia, where students are committed and have a desire to gain deep knowledge that they can transfer and apply in practice thereby contributing to the economic development of Colombia. Unfortunately, over the past few years the number of international students has been decreasing in the UK, for this reason Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are creating new strategies in order to reach the international market again.

The purpose of this research is to examine how marketing strategies in Higher Education Institutions engage Colombian students, evaluate processes and customers' cultural needs, and determine whether those strategies need to be reviewed and what new innovative ideas can be implemented in order to re-establish the market in the UK. Institutions at the forefront of educational development display innovation in marketing with an effective use of social media, and a well-designed, user-friendly website containing relevant information, with the option to chat one-to-one with a sales representative and apply online.

The research collects primary, qualitative data using semi-structured interviews with Colombian students who have studied in the UK alongside with agents working for universities involved in the recruitment of Colombian students. This data provides insight into the marketing strategies applied by HEIs, solidifying its reputation as one of the key countries when it comes to investment in education.

The results of this research analyse the phenomenon experienced by the students and the existing approaches used by HEIs. The findings show that students tend to compare the educational system in both countries and have high expectations due to the reputation of the British Educational system. These expectations are taken into account from the beginning of the process until the students complete their studies in the UK. Agencies are interested in feedback from students because students' life experiences provide valuable information to agencies, hence increasing their knowledge base.

The recommendations propose alternative strategies that UK institutions may adopt in order to retain Colombian students as an emerging market offering them high-quality of education to be at the forefront of the market demand in order to increase the international student market in the UK.

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DECLARATION

The research presented in this thesis was carried out by the undersigned, Luz Stella Leguizamon. No part of this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for any other degree or qualification at this or any other institution. This work is the result of my own investigation, and all sources used are properly cited.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CEFR	Common European Framework of Reference for Languages
HE	Higher Education
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
HEPI	Higher Education Policy Institute
HTS	Highly Trusted Sponsor
EF	English First
EPI	English Proficiency Index
ICEF	International Consultants for Education and Fairs
ICETEX	ICETEX in Spanish. Colombian Institute of Education Loans and Technical Studies Abroad
IELTS	International English language Testing System
ONS	Office for National Statistics
UK	United Kingdom
UKBA	United Kingdom Border Agency
UKTI	United Kingdom Trade Investment
UKVI	United Kingdom Visas and Immigration

CHAPTER 1

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Rationale for the proposed research

This research is focused on an evaluation of innovative marketing strategies that are employed to recruit Colombian students into the UK HE sector. A proposal for developing guidelines in order to select marketing strategies to increase recruitment and retention.

It focuses on the quality of education and international educational development based on economic, sociocultural dimensions of Colombia and the UK. It has been classified into three main categories: Colombian students, higher educational institutions in the UK and the government in order to retain international students.

This classification highlights the areas that the research is focused on. The aim is to propose strategies for review and implementation that would, in the end, improve international students' level of satisfaction and provide them with a better experience during their studies in the UK.

This thesis contributes to knowledge by analysing the educational sector as it relates to Colombian students, decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006), processes and socio-economic status regarding the marketing theories and practices (Gronroos, 1990; Cubillo et al., 2006; Raimo et al., 2014). The analysis is based on the performance of HEIs in the UK, quality of education and the policies that operate in the country. The marketing practices are described in terms of customer retention (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Clarke and Shyavitz, 1992; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016) placed on marketing mix (Gummesson, 1994; Gronroos, 1994; Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Ivy, 2008; Tuten and Solomon, 2015), marketing orientation (Narver and Slater, 1990; Conway and York, 1991; Molinari, 2000), brand value, customer service and, digital marketing strategies (Beech, 2015).

These practices seek to retain new students and improve their performance, increasing Colombian student mobility in education.

1.2. Background of the study

1.2.1. Colombian educational market

Brazil and Colombia share the compelling need to improve lifestyle through studying abroad, although there are many countries in South America, each of which has its customs and culture. Brazil, the largest economy in South America, has more international education facilities than the other South American countries. The modest economic growth in countries like Mexico, Colombia and Brazil has caused a significant affluent of students from middle-income families to study overseas (Trines, 2017). The demand for English language skills in Latin American countries has increased in the global labour market.

Another significant aspect of Colombia is the fact that it is emerging from its internal conflict with a peace agreement between Colombian government (Ballentine and Nitzschke, 2006), Juan Manuel Santos's Nobel peace prize (The Norwegian Committee, 2016) and leftist FARC, guerrilla group that has caused serious disruption in Colombia for more than 53 years. This agreement gives hope, especially to marginalised communities, with the opportunity to have access to education and to avoid the risk of returning to conflict again (Trines, 2017).

As a result of this achievement, the UK's Minister of State, Johnson MP and Colombia's Ambassador Nestor Osorio signed a Mutual Recognition of Degrees Agreement on behalf of both governments in order to boost mobility, enhance academic and research collaboration between HE institutions and support the creation of new partnerships. Colombia is the third country to sign this agreement after Chile and Mexico. According to the British Council (2016), this agreement validates and recognises Bachelor's, Master's and Doctoral degrees in both countries.

“The mutual recognition of degrees is expected to strengthen existing links between the two countries enabling greater academic exchange and benefiting thousands of students from Colombia and the UK” said Tom Miscioscia, Director British Council Colombia. British Council (2016: p.1).

Colombian Students and parents find it time-consuming going through different university programmes, requirements, adapting to a different currency between countries, expenses, and accommodation in the UK due to a considerable risk of investment. Although most people find the UK expensive, especially London, it is still one of the most selected countries to study due to potential job opportunities in Colombia with a degree awarded from a UK university that potentially improves their career prospects (Moncada, 2007; Usma, 2009; ICEF Monitor, 2015).

Depending on the program, students must be aware of the different approaches to learning offered by teaching universities or research universities. In teaching universities, most of the time is spent in seminars and lectures; therefore, less time in independent study, meanwhile research universities rely more on self-discipline and motivation by the student, who must work independently and attend fewer hours in class. The decision is based on the interest and self-discipline of the student (Chapman, 2005; Lauder, 2017).

Another important fact relates to the services advertised by the university and what they provide when the students arrive on campus. Although a good ranking, the university’s name and high performance are relevant, the most significant factor for the university should be that students enjoy learning, progressing and living while they are in the host country because that feedback represents a great prestige and valuable opportunity for future students (Peters, 1992; Mercer, 2015).

UK universities require that applicants have completed the International English Language Testing System (IELTS), which demonstrates the applicants’ English level, as a prerequisite to obtaining a place (Yen and Kuzma, 2009). This exam tests the level of English in four basic skills, reading, writing, listening and speaking, providing a score in each skill and a general score for all the skills

combined. Most universities require a general score between 6 and 6.5, which is equivalent to a B2 level. The student must obtain a minimum of 6 in each of the individual components. In other cases, some highly trusted sponsor universities are autonomous and can provide their own internal English test.

Bragg et al. (2013) support the hypothesis that people with English skills are more innovative and better communicators, helping the economy and exports of companies. In some countries, people that speak different languages use English to do business, because it is a widely used language around the world, for this reason, Colombian people look for opportunities to study English particularly overseas (Usma, 2009; ICEF Monitor, 2015).

Figure 1.1. Motivations for studying English in Colombia (British council, 2015, p.34)

The Figure 1.1. explains a survey released by the British Council (2015) to a thousand Colombian people between 19 to 35 years old. It showed that in Colombia, most people are encouraged to learn English because of the skills needed at university (48%), and employment prospects (47%) or because it is required in secondary school (38%). This measure applied by the education system highlights the necessity of studying a foreign language. The percentages decreased significantly for the other reasons, i.e. to perform better at work, design

a network (8%), communicate in English when travelling overseas (8%), friends and family support (7%) because people find it difficult to speak English with relatives or friends, non-reported reasons (7%), for social status (4%).

The study shows a concern from the British Council with this “National Bilingual Program 2004 – 2019” target. The Colombian people's difficulty would be a bilingual culture in 2019. People need more motivation that comes more from work, political and economic insights rather than family members, friends, or business culture (Moncada, 2007). For this reason, the government has invested £500 million in order to improve the education system (ICEF, 2015).

“Due to recent economic opening up of the country in response to globalization tendencies, career advancement is dependent to a large degree on English language proficiency and bilingual education is seen as the key to foreign language development. Thus, prestigious or ‘elite’ bilingualism has a very high profile among the Colombian middle and upper classes and there is an increasing demand for bilingual programmes” Usma (2009: p.130).

For instance, during the last years, the Colombian Government and the Colombian Ministry of National Education have been developing diverse projects intending to improve the quality of education through “Education Revolution” (Moncada, 2007). They have raised public awareness of the need to study English and launched a plan, “National Bilingual Program 2004 - 2019”. According to (CEFR) The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages, it targets levels of English proficiency to make Colombia bilingual; furthermore, the Government has taken the initiative of employing foreign English-speaking teachers to support and improve the English skills of students in public schools.

Most researches in the field believe that English language is essential to obtain a better job position and allows possibilities to communicate when people travel, internationally (Usma, 2009; Fandino et al., 2017), but unfortunately it is seen as a privilege only available to a certain group of people with financial means (Trines, 2017). Although this study concentrates on tertiary education, it is relevant to

mention the base level of English in Colombia in order to identify the possible weaknesses, specially in those students with limited incomes and resources. Colombians are exposed to English through the internet and social media, which encourages them to learn the language. Also, it brings long-term benefits and better opportunities for vocational, personal, and social development throughout their lives. The typical obstacles that these students face are the large class sizes, lack of access to schools due to the isolated geographical locations in Colombia, limited training and lack of adequate resources (British Council, 2015).

During recent years, UK institutions have expressed interest in contacting agents from Colombia because of the influence in the student decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006), local knowledge about the culture, needs and expectations of the student (Raimo et al., 2014). A study by the British Council (Willets, 2013) disclosed that 40% of international students in the UK have used the services of agents because parents feel more confident and safer for their children. These agencies are typically small companies that have the experience of connecting universities with potential clients in exchange for a commission.

On the other hand, students rely more on agencies that operate in their home country or even find it more beneficial if they have a branch in the UK as well. The role of the agent (Willets, 2013) is pivotal for students who receive advice and support in the same language, also parents feel more comfortable and confident because they receive personal information about courses and country features. Agencies support students and encourage them to be committed to achieving their goals and to add value to their professional life and country by going on the journey of studying overseas.

Additionally, agencies offer packages of programmes with a wide portfolio of institutions, universities and scholarships. Students are supported in the process of visa applications and interviews (Willets, 2013). Yet another service is accommodation and airport pickup. Beech (2015) clearly demonstrates that an important aspect is the availability of communicating through social networks, websites, in order to support students and help them to adapt easily in the UK

because they are able to keep in touch with friends and family members at home sharing positive and negative experiences, feelings and photos frequently. This behaviour creates an impact on the decision-making process of new potential students.

The embassy of each country offers guidance during the early days of the student's stay. They give advice relating to transport, the main places to find help in difficulties or issues if their passport is lost. The institutions or universities are aware that this support exists but unfortunately students rarely take advantage of it, preferring instead to ask friends or classmates.

Colombian Students invest in their studies in order to receive value for money, facilities, support and high standards of academic education. The academic term and length are important. Mainly, students look for improving their English skills through immersion in an English-speaking country and culture, as well as the ability to develop their professional career internationally with the knowledge of a new university program (Eder et al., 2010)

(AUCC) Universities Canada describe: *"Internationalization as a multitude of activities aimed at providing an educational practice within an environment that integrates a global perspective"* Tayeb et al., (2016: p.2).

This explains the socio-cultural context as a relation between cultural integration, broader cultures from other countries and learning languages as a process, thus Colombian people find traveling to the UK as a broad challenge, leaving behind their own culture, weather, traditions, food, professional jobs and most importantly, family and friends. The students must fit into a new culture with different traditions, some people find it as a way of escaping, looking for knowledge, boundless opportunities for growing personally, surviving and solving everyday issues by themselves, knowing that their life would not be the same after having arrived at the UK.

1.2.2. United Kingdom a host country

Recent studies from Hajela and Sumption (2016), indicate that the UK higher education sector (HE) has been characterized mostly by competitiveness in the global market by recruiting international students, not only fulfilling the need for generating income but also being notable for the professional benefits that students receive from HE institutions (Eder et al., 2010). These practices are becoming strategically crucial for institutions in order to sustain growth. Therefore, the UK has been actively recruiting overseas students from South America, specifically Colombia, a country that has proved to be committed and genuine. This engagement of students helps to develop the reputation and ranking of institutions that make a considerable effort to help the students to adapt easily during their stay, offering material resources such as books, internet access, high-quality research and teaching.

Brennan (2013) affirms that UK Trade Investment (UKTI) and British Council have reached markets in the USA, Mexico, Brazil, India, Turkey, South Korea, Indonesia and Russia, but mainly students from China. The UK is actively recruiting highly qualified overseas students, and this is the reason that representatives in the UK and Colombia encourage potential students to apply for a Chevening Scholarship. This programme is available to international students giving them the opportunity to study a post-graduate degree or develop their skills as a researcher in the UK. Committed HEIs are prepared to be at the forefront, offering protection and support to students during their stay in the UK

Statistics gathered over the last years confirm that the Higher Education sector is a global leader after the USA and is vastly attractive for the UK. Willetts (2013), Universities UK (2014) and Universities UK (2017) highlight the economic impact of international students in the UK, with more than 50% revenue increase for the educational economy. In 2012/2013, non-EU students represented 13% and in 2014/2015 represented 14% of the total population of HE students in the UK.

1.3. Problem Statement

Chapleo (2004) argues that students face factors that affect the recruitment process related to changes in visa regulations from the UKBA, this situation has decreased the number of international students' enrolment especially in English courses.

Figure 1.2. Applicants for Tier4 visa to study in an English language school using sponsor acceptances. (Adapted from the Home Office, 2017)

Figure 1.2. confirms a sharp decrease of more than 40% in English course enrolment amongst international non-European students in the UK from 2010 to 2011. This fell further by more than 80% between 6 years from 2010 to 2016, which indicates that policies introduced by the government greatly affected this recruitment (Home Office, 2017). The application of the rules closed an important number of institutions and colleges. Though those institutions had the opportunity to obtain the licence once again if they fulfilled the conditions required to offer a high standard of education, or obtain a new licence to enrol international students. According to a study in 2011 by the Home Affairs Committee, (2011) international students interested in English courses contributed approximately £1.5 billion to the UK economy and increased tourism, thereby creating 30,000 national jobs.

Figure 1.3. Applicants for visas to study using sponsor acceptances. Tertiary, Further education or other colleges. (Adapted from the Home Office, 2017)

Figure 1.3. According to information taken by the Home Office (2017), it clearly shows that other groups of schools and colleges in tertiary education were affected by the new regulations, with a decline of more than 80% between 2011 and 2016. The Minister of State for Immigration, James Brokenshire, in his written Statement said:

“The Government is reforming the student visa system to reduce net immigration and tackle abuse. These changes will help achieve this, whilst ensuring the UK maintains a highly competitive offer and continues to attract the brightest and best international students” (Brokenshire, 2015: p.1).

According to the statement in July 2015, the British government eliminated the opportunity for non-European Tier 4 students to work while students are enrolled in Colleges or request a work visa from the UK. The students must leave the country as soon as their studies conclude and apply from their country of origin. This measure impedes the student progression from college to university and severely risks international student recruitment due to the expense of having to

return to Colombia before coming back to the UK to start over, finding accommodation and settling down.

The work experience for non-EU students is based on their own skills, but Hajela and Sumption (2016) confirmed that not all non-EU students are able to easily find a skilled job in their chosen profession. Due to the type of visa these students are excluded from government benefits, and in addition, some students have dependents, so their children generate an extra cost of schooling. Therefore, only British universities listed on the official UKVI Sponsor obtain authorisation to offer 20 20-hour work permits a week and full-time on holidays to Tier 4 students.

Most students feel the pressure after finishing their studies to find some work experience. Employers avoid students that need a part time working permit due to the rules and licenses they need apart from the uncertain student situation in the UK. Employers must be well informed about the requirements and visas in order to avoid several penalties or expensive fines.

As a result, this situation explains the difficulty in the decision making considering that living in the UK is expensive and most Colombian students would need to improve their English skills before attending university and pursuing a professional programme in order to perform better and complete their studies successfully.

However, students feel more confident when the institution has a highly trusted sponsor provided by the United Kingdom Visas and Immigration (UKVI) that allows institutions to recruit students into academic programs. In order to meet the standards required to support full-time international students, these HEIs, as sponsors, are assessed on a point-based system and pass by scoring at least 70 points out of 100 (Baskerville, 2013). This measure avoids potential abuse of the system by institutions that are not committed to offering exacting standards of education to international students.

1.4. Purpose of the study

Student retention has been a significant issue in HEIs in the UK, this concern increased between 2012 and 2013 when student recruitment decreased for first time in 29 years (Marsh, 2015), and yet the latest data from the Migration Observatory at the University of Oxford (Blinder, 2017) and Home Office (2015) indicate that the mobility of non-European international students has actually been decreasing since 2010. In 2010, the UK government created policies to control the students' status and which prevents migrants from coming to work instead of studying. Between 2010 and 2014, approximately 800 institutions lost their licenses to sponsor international students because of the introduction of new polices. UKBA invited those institutions to apply to become a High Trusted Sponsor (HTS) in order to demonstrate they had met the standards and obtain the licence to recruit international students again.

Consequently, HE institutions decided to modify the marketplace strategies, focusing on marketing orientation and retention in order to improve their recruitment performance due as seven out of ten non-European international students came to the UK in 2016. In recent years, although the mobility of non-European international students improved, there is still a lot concern.

The Prime Minister, Teresa May, has insisted on classifying international non-European students in the statistics of immigration, which is counterproductive for Britain's world-class universities (Crofts, 2017). Despite the HEIs attempts to exclude students from being part of the UK's migration issue, the government maintained that students are temporary migrants due to their visa situation. This action was taken because it was believed that some students remained in the country once the course had finished and so should be included in the measure in order to keep migration under control.

A report from the Office for Statistics Regulation (2017) contained data showing the quality of international students and their decision to leave the country once their studies finish. There was a concern related to immigration and emigration data in 2013, with a lack of information about student emigration or overstaying

after their studies concluded. A student is classified as a migrant when they obtain a visa to study for twelve months or more. As a result of this extensive data, the Home Office created an 'Exit Check Data' programme to obtain better control of immigrants and statistics about their departure according to the expiring date, country and type of visa (Home Office, 2018). The Office for National Statistics (ONS) conducted a survey to understand the international non-European students' intentions after ending the course, trips out of the UK to visit family or destinations. However, the government need to reinforce the growth and quality of education for genuine international students and recognise their favourable impact on the economy and Britain's reputation.

Figure 1.4. Sponsor visa applications by sector (Adapted from the Home Office, 2017)

Figure 1.4. shows the visa applications from non-EEA students from 2010 to the end of 2016 (Home Office, 2017). The student visa application increased by 1% in 2016. Even with the increase, the overall numbers in 2016 still fell short in comparison to 2011 and 2013, which saw the highest enrolment during the 6 years. The Russell group represents an elite group of twenty-four out of a hundred and thirty universities that operate in the UK. This group recruited 5% more international students around the world in 2016 in comparison to 2015, proving that demand for the very best UK universities is still on the rise.

Figure 1.5. Central American and South American applicants for visa Tier 4 to study at Higher Education Institution using sponsor acceptances (Adapted from the Home Office, 2017).

Observing the statistics of Central and South American countries in Figure 1.5. (Home Office, 2017), the students that applied for a Visa Tier4 decreased by a notable 30% between 2014 and 2015. The volumes further reduce by 16% between 2015 and 2016. This suggests that students opting to study in other countries or remain in their own.

It is important to point out the mutual recognition of Degree Agreements signed between the UK's Minister of State for Universities and the Colombian ex-president Juan Manuel Santos, and based on:

“Recognition of quality assurance systems for higher education in each country. We hope to boost mobility between the two countries an increase academic and research cooperation between institutions, facilitating and encouraging the creation of academic partnerships” said Francisco Cardona, Colombian's Minister of national Education British Council (2016).

On the other hand, there is an extensive market demand in Colombia and other South American countries, where students are aware of the pivotal need of learning English and pursuing a higher level of education, gaining intangible skills such as self-confidence, social skills, understanding others, time management, personal savings and organization, thus, becoming more marketable from the professional perspective. (Brennan et al., 2013). Although there are many benefits of studying abroad, South American students feel concerned, scared and anxious about a new culture, rules, weather, fashion, religions, languages from other countries, customs and experiences. Due to these reasons, Colombian students rely more on the experiences and recommendations of the people around them as a recommendation to travel abroad, this behaviour is part of the culture.

One of the main problems in Colombia is the lack of resources and qualifications in English language learning. There is a lack of skills, motivation and incentives to develop a structured pedagogy for teaching English. Unfortunately, very few teachers reveal an interest in learning English and usually learn it through self-financed study (Granados, 2013)

Researchers from the British Council (2015) confirmed that English is the second most spoken language in the world, with 4.1% of the total world population. In Colombia, there is a high proportion of people without basic job competences, such as English skills, specialised profile, analytical skills, commercial and project management skills. The Colombian Ministry of National Education (MEN) values English teachers and can offer them a wide range of employment and self-employment opportunities. MEN (OECD, 2016) is developing strategies to encourage students to finish school with the necessary skills to undertake a professional degree, supporting and preparing them to perform successfully in the labour market. The measure requires a long-term strategy in the public and private sector in Colombia. The aim is that professionals have access to support and guidance sectors during their professional career and working life, allowing them to fully develop their potential skills (Eder et al., 2010).

Whilst publications aimed at students planning to study abroad do exist there is a lack of specialist information related to aiding decision making of those Colombian students that have a desire to study abroad and specifically into the UK. Also, there is limited research about the experience of these students in the UK in particular.

This study attempts to identify the strategic management context in HEIs; thus, universities spend time on planning in order to promote the mission, reach the vision and objectives of the organisation. Therefore, it is vital to explore the opportunities of linking the theoretical framework of strategy and its use in HEIs. This analysis contributes to a better operational execution in terms of competitiveness and quality. HE institutions as a business need a strategic plan based on a long-term plan that outlines the path for the future of the institution and needs to be reviewed every year according to the performance and feedback (Peters, 1992).

In terms of corporate-level strategy, there exist older universities that remain stable due to their capabilities and strong skills in staying competitive in the educational market. On the other hand, other organisations use a growth strategy of creating new alliances or partnerships with other institutions that share reciprocal interests. This strategy develops a competitive, dominating position in the market because this alliance shares the same cooperative portfolio.

1.5. Research Method

The best approach for this qualitative research is phenomenological because it captures the participants' experiences and analyses them (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015). The method of reasoning is inductive, non-probability, which observes and predicts the behaviour of the participants. The sample selection is purposive (Ritchie et al., 2014) using interviews with semi-structured questions (Cohen et al., 2003; Gray, 2014). This data is collected from two groups: 18 Colombian people who studied in the UK and 4 agents who have extensive knowledge and experience with universities in the UK and the Colombian educational market. After the data collected is organised using N-

VIVO software, (Joffe, 2012; Bazeley and Jackson, 2013) as a tool to examine the information and provide meaning to the process of social construction, the researcher clusters sources based on the data collected and creates nodes as a framework. These nodes are clustered in themes based on the research questions. This coding practice is fundamental in qualitative research in order to start the process of analysis.

1.6. Research Aim

There exists a high level of interest in international migration and broadly opportunities to recruit students, for this reason policy makers in central government are debating several factors to control the student migration without affecting educational institutions and the economy of the country or preventing the student recruitment phenomenon; which is propagated by students who have studied abroad and encourage others to take the same path.

The rules issued by central and local government benefit the student intending on travelling with professional purposes where the UK institution meets the legal requirements, licences and obligations of improving the customer service and market orientation.

This research aims to critically review the innovative marketing strategies that are employed to recruit Colombian students into the UK HE sector and recommend guidelines that can be developed from a university perspective in order to enhance the growth of recruitment.

1.7. Objectives

According to the research aim, four objectives are proposed and take the qualitative approach chosen in this study.

- 1. To identify the usual marketing strategies that are employed to drive Colombian students in higher education to the UK.**

2. **To analyse how effective these marketing strategies are for recruitment from a Colombian student's perspective.**
3. **To describe the operational framework for university student recruitment.**
4. **To recommend innovative marketing strategies to the universities in order to enhance recruitment and improve student retention in the UK.**

1.8. Main question

What are the innovative marketing strategies that are employed to recruit Colombian students into the UK higher education sector, and what guidelines can be developed from a university perspective to enhance the growth of such recruitment?

1.9. Research questions

The main question concerns the students' experiences and agents in order to propose solutions that generate new strategies in the field of HEIs in the UK.

1. The first objective addresses the research question:
What are the usual marketing strategies employed while recruiting Colombian students to the UK in the higher education sector?
2. The second objective addresses the research question:
How effective are these strategies in recruitment from a Colombian student's perspective?
3. The third objective addresses the research question:
What are the operational guidelines for university student recruitment?
4. The fourth objective addresses the research question:

What recommendations can be made to universities in selecting the best marketing strategies to enhance recruitment and improve student retention in the UK?

1.10. Research structure

In order to give a clear understanding of this study, the investigation comprises chapters that expand upon the main themes previously described. The first chapter describes the purpose and gives a general introduction to Colombian culture, economic development, the importance of English language skills and tertiary education, decision making focused on UK educational status and competitiveness in the educational market and application processes to the UK.

In addition to this, the chapter details HE institutions' main concerns and offers to students, prerequisites to the application process, the role of agencies as it relates to a bilingual procedure and difficulties experienced by students during this process and the issues they face once in the UK. The UK as host country is also discussed in this chapter. It looks at the performance of the country, the execution of UKBA regulations that seek to benefit the country and support international students. Finally, the aim, objectives and research questions of this study are explained.

Chapter two is concerned with literature review, where secondary data is consolidated and analysed in depth. The background of Colombian culture, current knowledge about pedagogical issues in education, English language impact, policy, environment and student choice concerns. The advantages and disadvantages to international students of UKBA laws are discussed.

There is an extensive study in the UK competitiveness in education and recruitment processes from the universities point of view and international students around the world. However, there is a lack of studies related to Colombian educational market into the UK, creating a competitive disadvantage for the UK when English speaking countries worldwide offer the same kind of English courses and professional programmes.

Chapter three expands upon the research methodology, describing the different methods and techniques necessary to approach the investigation. Furthermore, it describes and discusses the research approach for this specific project, which is based on qualitative data collection with semi-structured interviews with Colombian people who have studied in the UK and agents that work with universities that enrol Colombian students (Dey, 1993; Willets, 2013). In the qualitative method, the identification of the phenomena (Husserl, 1999) follows a well-supported study of the theory in marketing. The secondary data has been collected for analytic purposes from other people who have researched related topics in order to conduct this study. Primary data is collected after studying the secondary data research through interviews that can be adjusted during the participation of agents and Colombian professionals who have studied in the UK tertiary education, when talking about their experiences and points of view.

Chapter four analyses the data collected in nodes to answer the four research questions according to students' and agents' points of view, also explores and confirms the acknowledgement of the concept and theories mentioned and applied in the study. The interviews are translated from Spanish into English and coded into meaningful groups. Once the themes are coded in each transcript, the subsequent analysis will reveal the common aspects and differences of the participants' experiences. The themes coded generate provisional nodes in order to assign them to more categories. (Miles et al., 1994; Smith et al., 1999). This analysis aims to develop an understanding of the experiences of the students and agents by the theme of study.

Chapter five presents the conclusions and recommendations that summarise the findings of the primary and secondary data gathered. It contributes to the knowledge of the topic with new alternatives that add value to the research through the analysis of the data, and proposes new possible topics to investigate and enhance the study. This chapter answers the main research question and offers guidelines that can be developed from the UK Government and UK HE sectors as strategies to enhance the growth of Colombian students' recruitment.

1.11. Definition of Terms

In marketing and education, there are several definitions of the terms that give a clearer interpretation of the concept. Definitions of concepts as they relate to this study are below:

Academic capitalism: this term considers Colombian students a consumer who chooses freely the institution or university that is most suitable to their needs. Thus, institutions and universities commercialise education as a service and a new lifestyle for the consumer's end (Slaughter and Rhoades, 2004).

Globalisation: in HE in the 21st century challenges the economic, social and political demands of the nations. Although the concept of globalisation has many definitions, it is clear that it interconnects educational institutions, enhancing their attractiveness and facilitating the inflow of students. From a marketing point of view, it increases the strategies and competitiveness not only between universities but also within countries. Most HEIs that desire to be in the market competing for status and ranking must implement a marketing plan that modifies the governance, academic work and policies made (Vaira, 2004; Marginson and Wende, 2006).

Internationalisation in HE is a strategy in educational policy that seeks to improve the quality of the education system in order to meet the needs of the university sectors and globalization demand among nations (Gazel-Avila, 2005).

Customer loyalty is a term linked to customer satisfaction (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Joseph et al., 2005; Ndubisi, 2007). However, a satisfactory service given by universities does not necessary result a loyal student / customer, but it is the main way to influence loyalty through the enrolment of the student to the institution (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Wong and Sohal, 2003).

Customer satisfaction (Joseph et al., 2005) is a process that is measured from the first contact with the student and throughout the service given while the institution sponsors the consumer. Feedback and recommendations are used to evaluate this service.

Quality of education is related to the best standard of competitive distinction between the purpose of the service and the customer satisfaction (Joseph et al., 2005) given. This term involves efficiency using the resources and effectiveness reaching the goals of the institution (Johnston and Clark, 2008). In other terms more used in business is value for money (Jain and Singh, 2002) through efficiency and effectiveness.

1.12. Summary

This thesis contributes to the existing knowledge in the field of higher education of Colombians who study abroad and the trend in the increased number of students who desire to develop themselves professionally and personally in the UK.

Firstly, this research provides information related to the process, difficulties and performance of Colombians from the moment that they decide to apply for a place at the university or college in the United Kingdom until they successfully complete their studies. Secondly, these results debate the advantages of studying in the UK, the and the existing university weaknesses.

Thirdly, this work's findings are supported by concrete and substantial indicators that Colombian students are a potential market to explore. It would improve the quality of life in Colombia and the economy, and the educational status of the United Kingdom.

The next chapter presents a review of literature, it studies how the trend towards a global higher education growth generates prestige, better university rankings, societal and economically valuable benefits to the UK. The number of students who are ready to study overseas is increasing; the Colombian market, especially, needs to be considered in terms of international non-European students' policies. Colombian people recognise the importance of learning a second language and the opportunity to speak it fluently, but the opportunities in the country are limited.

Thanks to globalisation, more students seek to reach the minimum standards to improve these skills, mostly travelling overseas to a country with the best offer.

Universities and institutions in the UK can improve their market share looking at the weaknesses and strengths of Colombia educational market in order to target the customer's needs.

This study explores the most common practices used by institutions that recruit and retain customers through the use of student interviews in an attempt to verify whether those practices are adequate to fulfil their expectations. Also, it identifies the weaknesses and strengths of the programs to improve them with a strategic plan. This research could be extended to reach more Latin American markets where students have a similar culture and traditions, but with the same strong motivation and desire to study abroad.

CHAPTER 2

2. A REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1. Introduction

The literature review analyses and synthesises information found to support the research related to HE organisations in the UK. It seeks to satisfy the needs of Colombian customers in accordance with their culture and expectations. Colombian people prefer to specialise abroad and obtain work experience in order to become a competitive candidate for Colombian' organizations that seek to improve the economy of the country.

Figure 2.1. Literature Review Structure

Figure 2.1. explains the structure of the chapter concerning Colombian students' recruitment, international marketing strategies in HEIs in the UK and addresses models and theories. The chapter critically reviews the literature, observing that

there is insufficient marketing knowledge in HEIs. It discusses how the application of theories applied to the phenomenological research method can approach different markets according to the culture. Additionally, this chapter identifies new opportunities for further research. Finally, the conceptual framework at the end of the chapter analyses the Colombian students' input in the UK, learning processes and students' output. It reveals how the methodology in chapter three would be developed and analysed in chapter four in order to propose new marketing strategies and guidelines in chapter five.

Colombia's efforts in improving the educational system to create more opportunities for children, especially in high school, require time and awareness concerning the importance of learning a language and following tertiary education. However, due to the economic situation in Colombia, some professionals feel discouraged because their high skills are inadequately remunerated (Termes et al., 2015). Therefore, Colombia has a familiar culture where most of the families support the students and usually are responsible for university fees and basic expenses.

There have been many studies concerning international student recruitment, however, since the focus of this research is specifically on Colombian students and their culture, this information is not discussed in detail, but it is referred to as appropriate.

2.2. United Kingdom worldwide student destination

"I have always said that embracing globalisation as one of the great challenges of the 21st century will benefit the UK massively, and education is absolutely fundamental to that. Encouraging more talented students from overseas to come here will make the UK a stronger, brighter and better place to learn, for all our students" (Blair, 2006, p.2).

Certainly, Higher education has been transformed in this 21st century by the impact of globalization, therefore universities are more competitive enterprises that seek to obtain the best ranking and status in the market in order to respond

to the mass demand of student mobility using new communication, technology, integrated world economy and engaging new institutional partnerships as strategy in other countries where English is not a first language (Altbach et al., 2009).

According to Willets (2013) and Raimo, Humfrey and Yuelu-Huang (2014), the education sector system in the UK is globally the second largest sector after the healthcare sector. The effectiveness of international education recruitment increased the economy with a growth of £17.5 billion in 2011, which also represents 75% of the educational export revenue that comes from foreign students in the UK. Also, 511.000 international students are expected to be attracted to higher education institutes by 2020, showing an annual increase of 4.7% (Smith, 2015; Conlon, 2011).

Figure 2.2. The UK Second Best Destination for International Students(Universities UK, 2014, p.27)

The United Kingdom is the second-best destination for students worldwide after the USA for students interested in opportunities to study non-degree courses (English courses or diplomas), undergraduate and post-graduate programmes (Marginson and Wende 2006; Budd, 2016). However, Figure 2.2. (Universities UK, 2014, p.27), shows that this UK destination has dropped 1% in comparison

to Canada since 2013. According to HEPI (Higher Education Policy Institute) director Nick Hillman (ICEF Monitor 2018), asserts that the Ministry of the Interior is ignoring the benefits that international students bring to the United Kingdom. Recent information indicates that, during the period of 2015 and 2016, the economic benefits of hosting international students were approximately 15 times higher than internal costs.

It means that the cost of hosting a non-European student is £ 7,000 and European £ 19,000; the difference is due to the lower fees paid by European students (teaching, public services for the student and dependents, support service), Hillman (ICEF Monitor 2018). Other benefits come from tuition fee income, accommodation, rent, council tax, bills, personal items, food, travel costs, entertainment, university programme items like books, computer equipment and expenses from family members and friends. There are other expenses, such as visa cost, national insurance, which benefits the country before students arrive in the UK. (Conlon, 2018; ICEF Monitor, 2018). The information mentioned above represents a benefit of £102,000 from a non-European student and £ 68,000 for a European student, respectively. It means a net value of £ 1 million contributed to the country's economy during the short-term study time of 15 European students and 11 non-European students (Conlon, 2018).

Grove (2016) points out that there is a lack of clarity on the ramifications of the Brexit vote, concerns the status of non-EU and administrative staff of the universities who would not be eligible to work with a Visa Tier 2 because they earn less than £30,000 a year. It means that UK colleges and universities (Mazzarol, 1998) could face difficulties recruiting talented teachers from outside European countries. Those teachers need to obtain a job offer from universities or colleges. It takes time to adjust requirements and train new teachers to provide high-quality education, it also has consequences in terms of productivity, economy and growth of the country. However, there is an inconsistency with this argument because the UK guarantees highly skilled teachers in colleges and universities, and thus, teachers would receive a fair offer with adequate salary and benefits, supervised closely by the UKBA.

Higher Education and Research Bill (2017) added “*Communicate to the world, which is particularly important at a time when we are leaving the EU, that our higher education system is open for expansion and innovation, but that the university title in England is not given easily*” (p.1).

Brexit has vigorously challenged British citizens; the UK needs more people with higher education and skills that offer good service to students. These teachers need to be keen on maintaining the high international status of the country. A more comprehensive analysis would include the investment in human capital, offering a position to highly skilled international students. Although this option for the international student could be difficult, due to the decision they have to make between opportunities in their home country and being close to family and friends versus the opportunity to have work experience in the UK with a competitive salary. New generations are keener on travelling, making a positive impact on their lives and home country, saving money, looking for options to achieve a professional degree and master’s degree (Eder et al., 2010).

Social media sites (Paliszkievicz and Koohang, 2016) like LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, Pinterest are key in this path, providing vast information regarding facilities, accommodation, living expenses, support from universities, institution fees, better job opportunities according the program selected, experiences from other people around the world. Adding the support from the home country with loans, scholarships, and university agreements with universities around the world, currently, there are around 15 universities and colleges that offer this opportunity to students in Colombia. Students also count on the support and advice of agencies, and most importantly, the emotional and economic support from family.

Colombian students can find it an unsettling experience to come to the UK when there is insufficient information about the culture, and they can find that their expectations differ from the reality of coming here to study. Most students meet classmates from the same country or other countries, but have difficulty integrating with English speakers in their classes, especially at the more expensive universities.

Statistics from the British Council (2016) show that non-EU students can choose to study at 160 colleges and universities in the UK that are recognised by the UK as well as the Scottish Parliament and Welsh and Northern Ireland Assemblies as Tier 4 licensed sponsors. These HE institutions are making significant efforts to promote new opportunities, encourage professional progress, strengthen best practice and supply superior quality education through the awareness of the benefits and values that international education can offer. The largest number of students prefer to study business courses as most of the universities offer those programmes, while technology and engineering are the second most popular programmes chosen by students.

However, there is a key problem with the education sector policy and government, and the members of national parliament whose still need to reduce further the barriers and obstacles related to immigration rules, to attract more students by creating policies that increase the international flow (Solimano, 2009).

Universities UK (2014) argues that new controls made for Tier 4 student visas resulted in increased fees in comparison to international competitors, there is some evidence that factors like visa regime and Home Office Government immigration policy, services, the cost of applying from the home country each time that the student starts a new programme, the double surcharge to NHS services (Department of health and Social Care, 2018), and no working hours for students who are enrolled in an English course while study in UK. Those policies encourage people to choose HE institutions in countries like the USA, Australia, Canada or New Zealand.

It is reported in the Higher Education and Research Bill (2017) that there is concern about the quality of education and international student recruitment, especially for master's degrees. It goes on to recommend that universities should be concerned about the students' future related to successful jobs after leaving the institution. This is a measure that would improve the quality and reputation of UK education.

There is some evidence that most institutions seek to attract more overseas students and are investing in teaching, career support, technology, innovation and structure in order to meet global competition, serving the national needs and promoting international people interest. They are also constantly looking for new strategies based on their own issues like economic pressures and diverse student bases to be applied in order to find new markets.

The UK, with its position among the best 100 higher educational institutions and even the top 10 ranking around the world, is highly determined to keep this position as a global HE provider. Therefore, the UK aims to attract the best students with a high level of academic standards from around the world, some universities also emphasize their recruitment practices at masters and PhD's offering scholarships in order to strengthen the country's economy while other universities try to recruit as many students as possible (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Mercer, 2015). Universities are vital for a strong economic growth and labour market that has a demand for workers with high competencies, where knowledge is pivotal. Therefore, the challenge is offering high-quality education where teaching and research engage students to develop fundamental abilities in problem solving and entrepreneurship training and stimulating startups.

Tayeb et al., (2016) point out that a definition of high quality in HE institutions goes beyond the variety of courses, programmes or degrees on offer, that in fact involves a process of observing, maintaining and improving through constant assessment.

Padilla and Peixoto (2007) argue that HEIs are more than providers of education or a highly-ranked course; they have the responsibility of educating people, improving lives, developing countries and increasing the economy. For this reason, universities are looking for new strategies to reduce costs and stay competitive in the market. Pereda et al., (2007) challenge some of Padilla and Peixoto's argument, concluding that HEIs are constantly redesigning the curriculum to prepare students for employment needs in any country where they are planning to work; some students find work experience in the UK relevant when they choose a programme.

2.3. Colombia Background

Colombia is a country with 32 departments with its own governor elected for 4 years, it is bordered by Panama, Peru, Ecuador, Brazil and Venezuela; also, the Caribbean and Pacific coastlines. It is the fifth biggest country in Latin America, with an area of 1,42 million Km², and an estimated current population of 47.220.856. The capital city, Bogota, is in the centre of the country in the northern Andes mountains. The warm tropical climate in Colombia is determined by altitude due to its geographical location near the Equator, the seasons vary depending on the 5 natural regions with an average temperature, rainfalls, winds, and humidity throughout the year (Parsons and Kline, 2017).

Figure 2.3. Colombian Population by targeting age 2017 to 2021 (Adapted from PopulationPyramide.net, 2017)

Figure 2.3 presents the target Colombian population per year and age (PopulationPyramide.net 2017). The group of people studied are between 20 to 34 years old. The main population to be targeted is between 25 to 29 years old,

with a bachelor's degree with a desire to study a master's degree or doctoral degree, usually, this group of people are working already, and learning is part of their societal and personal progress. This is followed by those in the 20 to 24-year-old category who are looking to start a professional degree. This population has an interest in travelling to improve their professional status (Eder et al., 2010). This graph gives an approximate number of the population that could be recruited per year.

2.4. Colombia current situation

Colombia's democratic republic has the advantage of being an important coal exporter in the world, ranking the fourth position, and with the same position is the largest oil producer in Latin America. The country depends on mining and energy exports. Other products exported by Colombia are: emeralds, coffee, nickel, cut flowers, petroleum and apparel.

The list of products imported includes chemicals, paper products, industrial and transportation equipment, fuel and electricity. Unfortunately, poverty, narcotics trafficking, inadequate infrastructure, inequality and insecurity are obstructing economic development. The ex-president Juan Manuel Santos obtained the Nobel Peace Prize 2016 with the accord that ended the armed conflict that has been affecting the population considerably for 60 years, reintegrating former fighters and fostering reconciliation.

2.5. Education System in Colombia

Education for development, proposed by the Colombian Ministry of National Education, promotes a sustainable future that ensures the training of the students of tomorrow. In the first place, the national education ministry is generating reforms to improve the quality of education, understood as:

"The educational policy of the Government of prosperity, is based on the conviction that a quality education is one that forms better human being, citizens with ethical values, respectful of the public, who exercise human rights, fulfill their duties and live together in peace " (Ministerio de Educación Nacional, 2010: p.5)

According to the ex-president Juan manual Santos says that Colombia aims is to become "*The most educated country in Latin America by 2025, allocating more money to education than to the military*" Wyss (2014: p.1).

Table 2.1. Structure of Colombian's Education System (Adapted from OECD, 2016, p.27)

Table 2.1. explains the education system in Colombia from the OECD (2016, p.27). This system has improved over the last decade, as a consequence of prosperity in the economic and social sectors of the country. The system is divided into eleven years, five years of free elementary or primary education, four years of free and compulsory lower secondary education, and two years of noncompulsory upper secondary or vocational education. The vocational education aims to prepare students with technical skills within two years to enable them to compete in the employment market and improve their lifestyle. Children study for a full day of seven hours according to the General Law of Education 1994, and the system starts from an early age.

Despite the socio-economic situation specially in regional places, Colombia has high expectations investing in qualified professionals that teach in government schools, improving the curriculum framework inculcating values, increasing knowledge and skills according to every student's need (OECD, 2016; Termes et al., 2015).

In addition, access to the quality of education proposed by the National Education System (Ministerio de Educación Nacional, 2010) seeks to bring the country closer to a better international standard that achieves equal opportunities for all Colombians. The ICETEX implements an educational credit strategy to help the most vulnerable students access higher education by covering a hundred per cent of the enrollment with flexible payment. In the same way, Colombia created a master scholarship plan for teachers. This educational strategy seeks teacher training and improvement of skills and knowledge. In this aspect, two situations converge for the favoured teachers, one is to fulfil the teaching responsibility, and the other is the fulfilment of the master's degree studies without neglecting either of the two aspects. Unfortunately, not all the teachers are willing to accept the challenge.

However, there are still important issues where children with economic disadvantages do not start their studies on time or never attend classes, also the precarious quality of education due to the number of students in a classroom, where a teacher difficulty can help each student towards obtain high standards,

in comparison to the wealthiest families who can afford primary and secondary education in bilingual private schools. Colombia needs to use the advantage of having the best-established information system in Latin America (Usma, 2009) wisely.

Related to tertiary education, in order to obtain admission to universities, students require a state exam, ICFES (Colombian Institute for the Evaluation of Education) (Nuffic, 2015). Colombia counts with approximately 288 institutions through 4 types of academic and vocational programmes such as universities offering from undergraduate degrees to sub doctoral degree programmes, universities that offer all academic programmes and doctorates, Professional technical institutions that offer post-secondary training in different vocational areas in short term and Technological institutions that focus in high level training guided to higher level of tertiary education (ICEFMonitor, 2014).

Figure 2.4. Applicants for visas to study at Higher Education Institutions using sponsor acceptances, in Central and South America (Adapted from the Home Office, 2017)

Figure 2.4. indicates that most students prefer to start their studies in the third quarter of the year (July, August and September). This means that at the

beginning of the year, students are looking for options and getting the documents ready for the visa application.

Although Colombia is looking at the future in education, the Academic Ranking of World universities (2016) related to Latin-America discloses poor performance, Brazil and Argentina are still far in the top 101-150 with just one university each one, while United States and United Kingdom are in the first positions, for this reason more of Colombian students apply for the opportunity to study in the UK.

Figure 2.5. English skills in South American countries (ICEF monitor 2015)

According to Bragg et al., (2013) and EF EPI annual report in the ICEF monitor (2015), shown in Figure 2.5. Argentina is the country with the best English skills in South America, most other countries still show low proficiency skills. Unfortunately, in those countries, English is still taught as a separate subject, while most private schools are bilingual but expensive. Due to this statistic,

Colombia reveals low English skills and the necessity of focusing on studying English, which is the first strategy that universities must consider in order to attract more students (Marginson and Wende, 2006). Similarly, within the innovation and relevance, some strategies and actions proposed by the Ministry of National Education are:

"Expand the teacher training plan in English" and "Promote the internationalisation of education at all levels, mobility of students and teachers, curricula, recognition of degrees and accreditation" (Ministerio de Educación Nacional, 2010: p.10).

The UK and Colombian education systems are very similar, divided into primary, secondary education, further education and higher education. Usually, Colombian students travel to study master's degrees and PhD programmes rather than an undergraduate degree.

The difference in this educational system related to an undergraduate programme is the length of one or two years less in the UK compared to Colombia, which usually takes 5 or more years to obtain a bachelor's degree, and for this reason, it can be economically more attractive for students. Another advantage is the trimester and quarter universities system in the UK, where students can start their new programmes at different times of the year in January, May, June, September or October, according to the school (Clausen, 2016). Colombian Government became more aware of the importance for social, economic and cultural national development and is creating opportunities that encourage people to study overseas (Mazzarol, 1998).

The Colombian ex-president Juan Manuel Santos aims *"Colombia as the most educated country in Latin America by 2025 spending more money in education than to the military. It would happen through the increase of hours to public schools and improvement the wages and training to teachers"* says Wyss (2014). Nowadays, students feel the pressure from family and society to get an international diploma if they want to succeed professionally.

The objective of achieving a more educated Colombia requires a productive, educational and research development of the country. On the other hand, this ambitious proposal requires necessary resources that are not yet available. All proposals must be far from political interests, focused on an equitable education that privileges the development of Colombians. (Ministerio de Educación Nacional, 2010)

Smith and Taylor (2004) describe 'push and pull' strategies as pivotal tool to the student's final decision. The push strategy makes students more aware and encourages them to develop themselves as professionals, to find better job opportunities with an international diploma; to open up to new horizons, new cultures and start up new international businesses.

The pull strategy, expressed by Sitkin and Bowen (2013), pulls the student into the institution, motivating them to accept the service. Universities and agencies are aware of customer needs and desires (Mazzarol and Soutar, 2002). This is shown through adequate advertising, scholarships, assistance and quality programmes, providing cultural advantages of studying with people from other countries and working hours suiting the programme (Maringe and Carter, 2007). One of the most important evaluations of university performance comes from students' feedback related to experiences, classes, services, and support (Mercer, 2015).

Critically, the push and pull factors in this research are influenced by the age, nationality, social and economic status of the students, and resources from institutions that are interested in the selection of these students (Mazzarol and Soutar, 2002). The pull factors imply that the UK government and higher education institutions recruit Colombian students through attractive programmes while the student stays in the host country. Also, at this stage, the efforts of the United Kingdom are focused on making the country competitive and more attractive than others. The push factors are based on the economic and social situation in Colombia (Mazzarol and Soutar, 2002). This results in Colombians seeking new professional opportunities that are scarcely available in their home country in terms of educational programmes and intercultural experiences. These

factors push the students to make a significant and expensive decision to travel overseas. The selection finally depends on the pull of different destinations and more attractive offers by the country and institutions (Mazzarol and Soutar, 2002).

2.6. Colombia operating as a culture

Institutions put customers at the centre of the organisation (Kotler and Murphy, 1981), offering the best service and identifying beforehand the primary target audience as students or stakeholders who pursue improvement of their English language in order to start a professional programme and display another consumer behaviour. The Colombian students' goal is to have an overseas work experience that allows them to improve their performance when they return to the country, but it is well known that English is a barrier that needs to be overcome. The opportunities of having the same professional status from Colombia in the UK are few; for this reason, Colombian students find it more profitable obtain an overseas degree and experience and return to Colombia with the opportunity of obtaining a better salary and status (McIlwaine et al., 2008; Eder et al., 2010). Thereby, the institution helps achieve its organisational goals (Johnston and Clark, 2008) in a market effectively segmented in geographical factors of Colombia as a relevant variable (Kotler et al., 2009).

The consumer behaviour of the target audience refers to the benefits and motivations affecting processes involved in choosing the institution, including residential cultural and social integration, welfare needs, education progress in English language teaching or research direction (Kinnell, 1989). However, satisfaction through expectations and experiences with the service can vary from the branding and marketing position of the institution or universities (Nicolescu, 2009).

2.7. Marketing Philosophy

The theory of Academic capitalism (Slaughter and Rhoades, 2004) would define universities as a source of knowledge as a raw material that is converted into a product or service profitable for the new economy. This theory uses networks that

communicate between the private and public sectors in the new economy. Understanding that academic capitalism in the education sector is based on the behaviour of people who are part of this community and faculty, such as staff, administrators, teachers, and students.

The global HE sector is growing rapidly, and it has become increasingly important to ascertain the optimal method of recruitment in relation to international students (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015). Colombian customers take time to evaluate alternative options whilst investing in career development in the UK. To understand the purchase behaviour and decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006; Maringe and Carter, 2007), students follow a process in order to make the most adequate decision.

First, students plan their future, identifying the opportunities to achieve their goals, as a problem that needs to be solved, they research deeply in order to find the latest information, universities, scholarships, prices, location and services. Students evaluate these alternatives based on their liabilities. Sometimes clients feel more confident obtaining extra help that encourages them to decide to purchase, and finally, evaluate the decision based on the services taken (Tax et al., 1998).

Students tend to make the decision to study abroad after having researched passively. They base it on the subject they are interested in, employment rates after their graduation, and their potential earning power. University ranking has an important impact on alumni reputation as does academic quality, qualified English professors and, tools necessary to undertake the programme for their future progression. A tool that has become increasingly important recently is LinkedIn. Students can view the ranking of universities and get a feel for connections, support, employability post-graduation opportunities, internships and opportunities to grow professional networks on offer during their learning (Karzunina et al., 2015).

After students have chosen the program, they list the options that have and submit the applications to different schools or universities and wait for

acceptance. Universities make the choice decision, and students decline the offers. It discloses the customer behaviour of the students, whether it is a right or wrong decision. Educational institutions require much effort to make students accept the offer because they offer intangible services associated with benefits.

Pull factors for students are the preferences of Colombian companies for students who have studied and worked in the United Kingdom (Mazzarol and Soutar, 2002). This opportunity offers a recognised standard of excellence in research to organisations in Colombia. Undoubtedly, investing in education in the United Kingdom provides opportunities for both personal and professional growth, although there are countries such as New Zealand, Australia and the United States where Colombian students find investing their time and money an attractive proposition (Quacquarelli, 2016).

First, they become interested in the possibilities offered and research the options to choose the best programme that offers them more profit, through the marketing strategies used by institutions (Damodaran, 2008). Conway and York (1991) argue that recruitment practices are becoming more competitive and challenge HE Institutions to create more innovative strategies.

Narver and Slater (1990) and Molinari (2000) in their study of market orientation, highlight the market based on current and future customers' needs and expectations, where processes are important to improve the market performance in order to generate business profitability. The competitive international market has gone through difficulties since 80s as reported by Kinnell (1989), when the government rules and policies charged full fees to overseas students and leaving the HEIs experiencing financial constraints, cut revenue, and difficulties of falling student rolls. Despite this financial constraint, universities have had the advantage of adding value when promoting the UK as the best quality of education, academic teaching and support, free of corruption, because a degree cannot be bought.

However, in the marketing aspect, education is more than merely selling a course, using traditional media and social media as a systematic way to enrol

students. The market segment expects more according to the culture, background, and country where they belong. Welfare support for individuals, accommodation facilities, needs of the market are pivotal at the moment to offer a course. For universities is well known that overseas students support the political and cultural boundaries, improve the quality of education, and increase competitiveness more than a financial resource.

2.8. Increasing international student mobility

Gronroos (1990) argues that customer retention is the main purpose in higher educational institutions, and it varies between institutions depending on the marketing plan due to students are regular customers who would enrol one or probably twice at the same institution. Whilst it generates valuable economic benefits, it is linked to customer loyalty (Oliver, 1999; Ndubisi, 2007) that encourages students' progress and to continue their studies in the same institution. The advantage is that it would increase customer referrals.

Retaining existing customers can be an issue because current students expect special prices if they decide to continue studying other course, while new customers can be attracted with an introduction price, however cutting prices is a risk as marketing strategy disclosing lack of confidence in the service provided instead of focusing more in value.

According to Tayeb et al., (2016) financial resources are key in order to invest in reaching academically talented students, a dynamic leadership team, policies designed to support an academic excellence, appropriate technological infrastructure with computer laboratories, facilities for active learning plus conventional lecture rooms, creating a comfortable academic and educational environment. It is important to create strategies that enhance scientific research, creativity and innovation based on sustaining superior teaching and learning. These ideas are implemented when institution approaches the practices and requirements of international authorities that protect the education sector.

Although there is an insufficiency research in customer retention planning in HE, this study aims to measure and compare the customer retention (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Clarke and Shyavitz , 1992; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016) processes in HEIs, their marketing positioning and adding value that make the organisations different and competitive. This is the biggest challenge for HE institutions, because the services in question are similar. However, it is not an impossible path to create a distinctive position in the market, when the country counts with high reputation in education (Danjuma, 2016).

According to this study, the market Signalling theory (McCollough and Gremler, 1999; Meyer et al., 2013) studies the information obtained by institutions and students regarding the quality of service. HEIs in the UK have the competitive advantage of being among the first top-ranked countries with the best quality of education and guarantee it to students whose expectations are higher and demanding. For instance, the quality of education as a service can be verified after consumption. Marketing services, especially, have an advantage in selling tangible products that the customer can appreciate and pre-purchase. instead, in business education, Hart (1988) points out that services can be delivered only by teachers and educational institutions, who are not as predictable as machines.

However, services can be guaranteed whether the strategy is designed carefully and implemented appropriately, being easy to understand and communicate, followed by a meaningful experience according to customers' needs and unconditional service that guarantees the control of the institution with the necessary tools to improve the performance. A service guarantee is a powerful tool that builds customer loyalty (Oliver,1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Ndubisi, 2007) and market share due to the institution focuses on high standards that disclose reliable data on the performance and last examination of the service offered.

Customer value and customer satisfaction (Joseph et al., 2005) are key in recruitment practices development, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2016) a service must be concentrated in benefits and experiences as a result of a service

which acts as a tool that solve the consumer problem, turning into a brand experience for customers. In this market, the universities are unlikely would have the same customer more than twice, but can benefit from feedback about good customer experiences (Sweeney, et al., 1992; Mercer, 2015). The level of expectations projected by universities to target the right group of students, creating a successful relationship, cannot be lower than expected if the goal is attracting more clients and cannot be too high because the customer gets disappointed (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006). The marketing activities by HE institutions must consist of a thorough investigation of Colombian culture based on a targeted group of students, service development according to their needs, one-to-one communication, distribution, and pricing.

The Colombian educational system in some cities is affected by economic, political, social, technological, demographic, and natural factors. Nevertheless, digital technologies like smartphones, online sites, apps, and facilities offered by social media make institutions more competitive and accessible to students. Digital media is a powerful tool that increases the target audience through awareness and informs the students about the programmes offered and their facilities (Beech, 2015). This tool encourages the student to ask for more information and make the decision to apply for the course.

Universities target students under their brand's value proposition and Shared value. It means that identify and distinguish the institution in the marketplace, and in addition persuade the customer to purchase by delivering value in order to benefit the student and society in the UK and Colombia. In modern marketing the society is driven by technology, building a continuing and stronger customer relationship where the customer is satisfied and engaged receiving high customer value (Gronroos, 1994; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

The theory of marketing (Morgan and Hunt, 1994) through the years has had a great relevance in the academic framework in relation to the provision of services, creating a base of loyalty (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Wong and Sohal, 2003), trust and commitment to the client and for long lasting relationships. (Gwinner et al., 1998; Garbarino and Johnson, 1999; Ndubisi, 2007). In this way,

it is necessary to analyse and know the student to link him to the institution as a promoter and salesperson based on his experience and identification with the institution.

Figure 2.6. Quality Students Relationship (Source: own Figure)

Figure 2.6. explains the relationship with the consumer (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006) when the organisation knows its strengths and weaknesses and works hard to achieve its objectives (Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Johnston and Clark, 2008). The competitiveness between national institutions and at a global level is increasingly demanding with new political frameworks, financial limitations and difficulties with the financing system. Therefore, the institutions seek to establish new marketing strategies in order to guarantee the survival of the institution that creates the relationships between the institution and the students (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006), mainly the graduates who are more motivated to promote values and create commitments of belonging.

There is a growing concern about the educational focus of institutions that still insist on training students to achieve a degree instead of preparing them to obtain

a job. This indicates that there are very few studies conducted concerning marketing research in educational services (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Helgesen and Nettet, 2007).

Studies conducted have shown a correlation between the student and the institution within the context of marketing that is based on two important theories. On the one hand, the theory of social identity (Stets and Burke, 2000) and on the other hand, the organizational identification (Ashforth and Mael, 1989).

The identification of consumer-company or organisational identification is focused on the proximity of the consumer to the organisation (Ashforth and Mael, 1989). These authors argue that this identification refers to the sense of belonging to the organization, on the other hand Dutton et al., (1994) define it as the self-concept that the person identifies in himself and also in the organization, achieving a mutual cognitive connection as a concrete type of social identification within the organization. These theories point to an empirical knowledge according to the companies, but they have still been limited to studies carried out regarding universities and students. Bhattacharya and Sen (2003) and Scott and Lane (2000) offer a convincing argument showing that students in their search to satisfy their needs voluntarily create a selective and participatory relationship with the university.

“The more prestigious consumers perceive a company’s identity to be, the more attractive that identity is to them. In other words, the relationship between consumers’ perceptions of a company identify and their evaluation of its attractiveness is mediated by the identity’s perceived prestige” (Bhattacharya and Sen 2003: p. 80).

It can be inferred that a growing interest is currently developing in the context of services (Crosby et al., 1990), especially when it is personalised and requires a series of transactions to reach the proposed objective, as happens between the teacher and the student. Although the available evidence regarding the relationship of educational services is not conclusive because the relationship must go beyond teaching curricular content (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006).

The theory of social identification determines that the institutional values are shared when the student finds them similar to their own values. It is evident that this positively influences the organisational identity, creating a quality relationship with the student. It is based on trust, satisfaction and commitment (Kashyap and Sivadas, 2012). The concept of commitment welcomes a long-term relationship based on the trust, effectiveness, efficiency and productivity of the institutional results generated (Moorman et al., 1992; Swatz and Iacobucci, 2000) The benefits of this approach justify the institutional interest to increase student commitment with long-term relationships (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006) that makes the student feel committed to the objectives of the institution, motivating him to actively collaborate and interact with the members of the institution. Similarly, loyalty (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Ndubisi 2007) can be described as the emotional or psychological link between the consumer and the service or organisation that commits them to choose the same service or product offered (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Marzo et al., 2005; Soderlund, 2005; Helgesen and Nettet, 2007).

There seems to be a correlation between the concept of reputation and loyalty (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Wong and Sohal, 2003). This means that the reputation of a company is reflected in the product or service that has been built through past actions. From the institutional point of view, the students perceive favourably the study program or the university's service. Researchers such as Wong and Sohal (2003) and Standifird (2005) relate the concept of reputation as strategic management to attract and retain students. Johnson et al., (2001) define reputation as a direct experience with the object, and it is satisfactory according to the results obtained, which can be positive or negative.

According to the theories mentioned above, customer loyalty (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Wong and Sohal, 2003) is associated with a positive attitude in relation to a brand where the customer purchases regularly. This purchasing customer behaviour brings a satisfactory service that creates new business referrals through word of mouth and customer publicity through feedback. These types of customers are likely not going to the competitors and

probably will return to investing more than the less loyal customers (Bowen and Chen, 2001). It can be concluded that the loyalty of the graduated students attracts more students through the diffusion of their experience (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Wong and Sohal, 2003). This strategy creates not only a better image and reputation of the university but also attracts new entities to invest or finance research projects.

2.9. Current Strategic Marketing Plan in Institutions

According to the classical approach in marketing management and service, the student-customer is the consumer with specific needs in terms of education in a competitive market with several options. Tertiary institutions as business organisations are aware of those needs, and strategically create the appropriate service and advertise it to customers via resources such as social media, marketing campaigns and virtual campus tours. Some universities use a range of communication support (Schuller and Rasticova, 2011) as a strategy, such as rewarding prizes, educational fairs, events, open days and conferences. Other types of advertising commonly used to target students are fliers, billboards, radio and television commercials, advertising in the press and posters in public transport.

In order to succeed, the strategic plan must be created through the guidance of 7Ps marketing mix (Ivy, 2008): people, product, process factors, physical evidence, place factor, promotion, price factor. As a result of technology and social media, an additional “P” in marketing mix can be added for “Participation” or one to one conversation through marketing communication (Tuten and Solomon, 2015).

The adoption of education marketing as an evolutionary model is characterised by high technology, innovation, positioning, analysis, planning and control. The satisfaction is linked to performance (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). The set of all these activities aims to identify what is best for the students and the institution, where students are motivated to conclude their studies in an environment that supplies and facilitates their learning in a friendly and participative atmosphere.

There seems to be a correlation between expectations related to physical facilities that the institution offers to attract the students and, teaching and learning experience in a proper environment during the year that the student would be in the institution (Clewes, 2003)

Many studies (Douglas et al., 2006; Douglas et al., 2008; Grow, 2009) have shown that a facility's institutions influence the expectations of the students' decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006; Maringe and Carter, 2007), and once the students are enrolled, the challenge for the university is retaining the customers. They need to ensure that they are satisfied with a high level of teaching from a competent staff (Mazzarol, 1998; Grow, 2009; Zeithaml et al., 2010) who are able to understand students concerns, feelings and opinions. Institutions also need to evaluate the student perceptions (Babin and Griffin, 1998; Peters, 1992) through feedback related to the performance during the journey and at the end of studies, to a high level of expertise.

It is emphasised that student-customers have been empowered by social media marketing such as Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn, as a result of constant interaction with brands (Paliszkievicz and Koohang, 2016). Years before television and radio programmes were interrupted by advertising, now, while people are reading through their phones, tablets or laptops, different kinds of adverts pop up, taking some seconds of attention from the customer. Kotler et al., (2009) stress the importance of creating a strategic marketing plan in order to build a competitive position in the market. It must be embraced by the whole organisation, creating innovative ideas, having good communication skills, and following the vision and mission of the company. Customers have control of creating new clients, collaborating, and sharing content with institutions or friends.

4Ps McCarthy 1960	5Ps Judd 1987	6Ps Kotler 1984	7Ps Booms and Bitner 1982	15Ps Baumgartner 1991
Product Price Promotion place	Product Price Promotion Place People	Product Price Promotion Place Political power Public opinion formation	Product Price Promotion place participants physical evidence process	Product/ service Price Promotion Place People Politics Public relations Probe Partition Prioritize Position Profit Plan Performance Positive implementations

Table 2.2. Marketing mix extensions (source own Table)

Table 2.2. indicates that a considerable amount of literature has been published on marketing mix (Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Ivy, 2008; Tuten and Solomon, 2015). These studies are supported by different authors that have raised their own definition of marketing mix from their field of research. In general, it can be interpreted as a set of manipulability tools available to the organisation to influence the response of the consumer and contribute to the creation and development of the brand. The theory of marketing mix was described in 1960 by McCarthy with the 4Ps: price, product, place and promotion (Gummesson, 1994; Gronroos, 1994).

In 1995, Jobber supported the view, *“The important issue is not to neglect them, whether the 4-Ps approach or some other method is used to conceptualize the decision – making areas of marketing... the strength of the 4 – Ps approach is that it represents a memorable and practical framework for marketing decision – making and has proved useful for case study analysis in business schools for many years.”* (Zineldin and Philipson, 2007: p. 232).

However, the McCarthy research was challenged by Judd (1987) who proposed the 5P for People, believing that McCarthy's approach lacked validity because it did not consider the customer's needs. Later, Bitner in 1982 proposes the 7Ps adding 3P's: Participants, Physical evidence, and Processes. Four years later Kotler added 2Ps for Political power and Public opinion (Gummesson, 1994).

Finally, in 1991, researcher Baumgartner proposed the 15Ps, focusing on the client and their needs. Although these concepts of 4Ps to 15Ps are created for the benefit of the client, this marketing mix theory is criticised as manipulative, to keep the customer under the power of the company, avoiding their desertion. This is acceptable in the short term in companies that do not ultimately seek only an economic return, and not long-term mutual welfare.

In contrast, Palmer (2004) emphasised that marketing mix must be seen as a conceptual framework rather than a theory, which aims to identify the responsible elements in the decision-making process to satisfy the customer. These elements are used for the effective development of long-term strategies and short-term tactics in the organisation (Gummesson, 1994).

The marketing concept is a powerful tool that facilitates the commercialisation of company activities in order to delegate tasks in each area. This tool supports the design of marketing strategies controlled by the different variables of the marketing mix that fit in each organisation. At the same time, it analyses the strengths or weaknesses of each variable to allocate available resources. Starting from this point, the institutions carry out the analysis, planning, application and constant control of this marketing process (Rafiq and Ahmed, 1995; Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003).

In this sense, it is deduced that the students are the motor of the institution towards which the concentration must be directed, in an effort to prevent their decision making go with the competitors (Cubillo et al., 2006) Once the student is interested in the educational programme, the institution develops their strategies to retain the student and gives him a higher value than the one he is looking for (Mazzarol, 1998; Zeithaml et al., 2010). For this reason, the

commercialisation plan of the institutions includes an exhaustive study of the customer, their needs and the added value.

The marketing theories in the area of financial services highlight the importance of student participation in productivity and educational quality that meets their educational needs (Bitner et al., 1997). Experts argue that student socialisation can help the recruitment of new students in the context of what is expected of them, the acquisition of knowledge, skills and the appreciation of organisational values (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015). In education, the students co-create the service/product because it requires active participation. When the service does not fulfil the expectations, it notably affects the service outcome, affecting the productivity, quality and customer satisfaction (Zeithaml et al., 2010).

DELIVERING VALUE PROPOSITION	
Marketing Mix in HE Institutions in the UK	
(Ivy, 2008; Tuten and Solomon, 2015)	
People factor	Staff who work at the university in the UK, face to face tuition. Academically successful students, genuine students. Society
Product / Service Establish a need-satisfying market	Offer the best experience through a variety of programs, curriculum excellence in research, high quality teaching to the students.
Process factors	Regarding admissions, procedures and all the queries from the customers.
Physical evidence	Facilities for the students when they are in the institution, or online services Qualified faculty, infrastructure, well-equipped facilities, computers, and accommodation or residential requirements.
Place factor Make the offer available to the students	Accessible location and transportation facilities for students.
Promotion Engaging, communicating and persuading the target students	The profitable use of social media, recruitment practices, advertising using traditional and digital marketing, easy access and navigation on the website, and general publicity.
Price factor. How much would it charge for the service offered	The competitive tuition fees offered to students, scholarships, payment advice, payment arrangements, and program duration.
Participation (Tuten and Solomon, 2015) One-to-one communication	Maintaining an effective customer relationship, apprising customers about special offers, services or benefits.

Table 2.3. Marketing Mix in HE Institutions in the UK (Source: own Table)

Table 2.3. points out that there are no similar models related to the participation of students in the provision of services that have been proven in the field of higher education (Maxwell, 2015). Therefore, it can be concluded that this marketing theory is a recently created phenomenon in education (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014).

The classic marketing mix (Ekwulugo, 2003; Ivy, 2008; Binsardi Tuten and Solomon, 2015) plan supplies customers' needs and creates loyalty (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001) through a product policy. In this regard, institutions accomplish their goals through this tool due to customers would be satisfied with the service in accordance with their expectations. The universities based on academic preeminence need high levels of academic, educational excellence and achievement. Tuten and Solomon (2015) pointed out the importance of social media techniques adding the fifth P for Participation to the basic 4P's of marketing mix tool (Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Ivy, 2008) which improves the relationship with customers (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006), informing the customer about offers, benefits or new service. P for Participation in marketing discloses the necessity of the customers to communicate one-to-one with the institution to feel confident that the institution is the best decision made, thus their expectations are met, being unique and important as a student who needs support.

Student recruitment is important from the point of view of the economy and status of the institution, but going further, HEIs find it more challenging recruiting qualified human resources, great skills, good qualifications, scientists, and technology experts. These kinds of students are attracted by universities that offer them the possibility of increasing their knowledge using the necessary equipment and a job with a high salary in exchange for sharing students' knowledge and capabilities, pursuing a successful career (Solimano, 2008).

2.10. Customer Retention Theory

The customer retention theory (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos 1990; Clarke and Shyavitz , 1992; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016) is strongly linked with customer satisfaction (Joseph et al., 2005), customer loyalty (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001) and marketing mix. (Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Ivy, 2008; Tuten and Solomon, 2015) This theory helps to predict the student-customers' needs, potential new clients, retention and the delivery a better service. For some decades (Dennis,1998), universities have faced the task of creating an effective enrolment and retention policy for qualified students. These universities offer a quality service until the moment the student receives the university degree (Sultan and Wong, 2012). The culmination of the programmes by students ensures the success of the educational business.

Dennis (1998) affirms that an adequate enrolment plan takes three years to be implemented and even then, it needs to be continually reviewed and modified by the campus administrators and university staff who are responsible for the success or failure of the programme (Zeithaml et al., 2010). Technology has brought alternative options for the development of innovative marketing strategies to facilitate the recruitment of international students (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015). These have helped to achieve the mission and objectives of the institution (Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Johnston and Clark, 2008).

Competent and responsive enrolment in HEIs improves marketing retention because more students would choose the UK as a country to satisfy their educational and professional career objectives (Dennis,1998). Nevertheless, enrolment and retention management are an institutional community matter to support the student choice (Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

An adequate customer quality service in institutions is the key in the competitive educational market globally (Joseph et al., 2005, Sultan and Wong, 2012),

although the meaning of quality can vary from institution to institution according to the expectations of the student-customer and resources of the organisation.

Theoretical marketing models such as: customer retention theory (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Clarke and Shyavitz, 1992; Danjuma, 2016), customer satisfaction (Joseph et al., 2005) and marketing mix (Ivy, 2008; Nicolescu, 2009; Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Tuten and Solomon, 2015) have an impact in the decision making of Colombian students (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006; Maringe and Carter, 2007). Although there exists a significant amount of research related to recruitment practices of international students around the world, there is a lack of studies relating specifically to Colombian students coming to the UK.

When making the decision to invest in studying in the UK the intention of most of Colombian students is to choose the correct English course to obtain the appropriate English skills to advance to a postgraduate, masters or doctorate level in the university (Marginson and Wende, 2006). These students also evaluate the type of university programs offered and the quality of service when requesting information online.

All of the above influences decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006), which may be affected by UKBA visa regulations, student socio-economic status, educational level, English language level and the time taken to achieve the appropriate language level to obtain a position in the university. This course could take between 6 months and years, generating higher expenses; these factors affect the recruitment process (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Bryman, 2016).

The traditional approach that universities use to recruit students is via advertising campaigns to make students aware of the brand, sales and processes (Ozturgut, 2013; Beech, 2015; Mercer, 2015). The approach used to recruit students is largely the same among universities. Their main objective is moving people from stage to stage in order to make sales, the internet is an important tool in this process (Beech, 2015).

First of all, universities spend time and money on advertising visits, producing promotional literature, and open days where students can visit and take campus tours. Universities could take a more proactive approach with a combination of different strategies: email campaigns, one-to-one conversations with faculty members who are willing to talk with students, telephone or Skype calls, text messaging, and webinars. This would serve to nurture people through the various stages from the initial student inquiry to arriving on campus.

2.11. Universities recruitment practices

The most effective practices used by universities are employing a marketing assessor who has a wide range of expertise in the culture and the advantage of the language. Although a profitable strategy is travelling abroad to access customers directly in the Colombian market, universities are required to consider financial expenses and time. Another tactic is contacting agencies in foreign countries and the UK who have experience with students, visa applications and the admission process; this measure increases the number of students enrolled in HE institutions and, in return, the agents obtain a commission from the university (Willets, 2013). The disadvantage is that agencies work with multiple universities worldwide (Ozturgut, 2013), therefore, HE institutions must develop strategies that ensure agents recommend them as a first option over other institutions.

Most universities need to review the practices that they are using in recruiting students such as: accommodation cost, English language support for students, plan extracurricular activities and encourage students to participate actively in them, inform students about trends and alternatives to enjoy safely during their stay in the country.

Retention of international students (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos 1990; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016) brings some issues that challenge the institutions (Rajapaksa and Dundes, 2002). There exist cases that students experience a culture shock, find it difficult to integrate into the social life in the new country, feel homesick, experience social isolation,

frustration in coping with the new style of life, get depressed, fear, and be overwhelmed in their personal life. Also, in class could feel the competitiveness and the need to fit into the British multicultural people (Sandhu and Asrabadi, 1994). The student's adaptation to the new country requires support in developing their skills, communicating effectively and confidently (Gao, 2015). Students tend to adapt better to university life, forming friendships from the same country or abroad through the familiarity of social media.

Figure 2.7. Conceptual framework

2.12. Conceptual framework

Figure 2.7. analyses the Colombian students' input in the UK, influences to make a decision, the process of recruitment, learning process and motivations to study abroad in order to improve their career opportunities (ICEF Monitor, 2019). This enhances the HEIs' performance, research profile and capability, which in turn promotes brand awareness and new strategy development to increase the percentage of Colombian students. The analysis is based on Colombian students' experience in the UK (Dey, 1993; Maxwell, 2015), and representatives in the UK who work with universities that train them to offer their programs, scholarships, and different benefits to students.

Colombia is a developing country with a complex education system concerning English language standards and economic resources. The recruiting student process (Ozturgut, 2013) requires a knowledge of the culture, which means that the decision of studying overseas does not depend on the student; families must be consulted to obtain the approval for the enrollment, this is because usually students receive financial support from family members. Theoretical marketing models provide new knowledge in the field of study, as well as identifying new variables, issues and key concepts related to the phenomenon (Dennis, 1998; Cohen et al., 2017).

Higher Education and Research act 2017 (Legislation gov. UK, 2017) make changes about the way that Higher education is regulated in England, their operating framework is concerned about the students' interests are protected responsibly, it gives a better understanding about the fees payed are invested wisely and well.

Developing a competitive marketing strategy for international recruitment is a complex issue for institutions since education is a service rather than a tangible product, and the characteristics of the international market are demanding (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015).

Through the use of a qualitative research approach this work provides an expansion of knowledge in the area of UK education sector performance and the interests of Colombian students in being part of the UK education services, the quality of education related to the expectations of Colombians in the professional field when they make the decision to study in the United Kingdom.

The marketing theories applied to the phenomenological research method (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015) seek to get a description of the real world by interpreting and explaining the phenomena experienced by Colombian students through their constant exposure to the sociocultural environment, their individual feelings and perception of reality. It means that the analysis of primary and secondary data would propose guidelines that can be developed by the UK government and UK HEIs to make this experience more meaningful for future students.

It can be inferred that there is much to be done in terms of recruitment practices by agencies and important points that should be taken into account by educational institutions to achieve a better performance that satisfies even more the students' needs in the United Kingdom (Ozturgut, 2013). Through the pull strategy (Mazzarol and Soutar, 2002; Sitkin and Bowen, 2013) and marketing mix (Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Ivy, 2008; Nicolescu, 2009; Tuten and Solomon, 2015), agencies (Willets, 2013, Raimo et al., 2014, Beech, 2015) agreed that HEIs use the right strategies to recruit students, with the advantage of being located in a prestigious country, specially London that is known as the business city where students develop their professional skills in a globally market and intercultural country that contribute a lot to them.

“The most successful improvement strategies may be those that concentrate on one specific dimension of service quality, with the retail firm seeking clear leadership on that dimension rather than trying to improve marginally in several areas at once” (Wong and Sohal, 2003: p.513).

It would mean that the strategies employed by HEIs while recruiting Colombian students met the basic customers' needs and desires through marketing orientation (Narver and Slater, 1990; Conway and York, 1991; Molinari, 2000; Ozturgut, 2013). It was seen through the successful student enrolment made (Dennis,1998).

Universities must evaluate their strengths and weaknesses periodically and propose strategies to enhance the reputation and positioning of the institution (Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). This is achieved by issuing the correct message to the students to recruit talented and loyal students to the institution through their selection system (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001). HEIs that aspire to improve their position in international research rankings would need to understand the particular metrics and performance levels in them and what differentiates them from HEIs that currently perform better.

2.13. Theoretical framework

The Table 2.4. represents the theoretical framework, which is based on the most significant research done by researchers interested in education, marketing and methodology.

The findings in each of those topics investigated guarantee the extension of knowledge, the academic position and guide the study to the achievement of the proposed objectives. These findings are consistent with the application of theories and models in marketing. The correct application of the theories strengthens the purpose of the study and allows a greater understanding for the readers.

COUNTRY	LEADER	YEAR	POSITION	KNOWLEDGE FIELD
MARKETING AND EDUCATION				
Minnesota USA	McCarthy Jerome	1964	Professor, author, consultant	4Ps marketing mix, managerial approach.
Arizona	Rhoades Gary	2005	Professor and Director, University of Arizona	Academic capitalism and the new economy.
East Carolina USA	Tuten Tracy	2015	Professor of marketing at East Carolina university	Advertising, social media and digital marketing.
Texas, USA	Hunt Shelby	1994	PhD Professor, author, consultant, and organisational theorist	Competition theory, resources, productivity, economic growth, and marketing.
North Carolina	Armstrong Gary	2016	Distinguished professor of undergraduate education. PhD in Marketing	Consultant researcher, sales management, and marketing strategy.
Philadelphia	Solomon Michael	2015	Professor of marketing at Saint Joseph's University	Consumer behaviour and lifestyle issues, branding strategy, marketing applications. Advertising and retailing, Marketing mix
Stockholm	Soderlund Magnus	2005	Professor, department of marketing strategy	Consumer behaviour, consumers' reactions to marketing stimuli, and marketing communication.
Germany	Hennig- Thurau Thorsten	2001	Professor university of Muenster	Consumer behaviour, social media digitalisation, and entertainment industries.

Australia	Wong Amy	2003	Associate professor, department of management, Monash university	Customer loyalty, service quality.
Finland	Gronroos Christian	1990	Professor of service and relationship marketing	Customer retention, marketing mix.
United States	Grow Gerald	2009	Professor emeritus of magazine journalism at Florida A&M University	Decision-making situational leadership. Self-directed learning model.
Madrid	Cubillo Jose Maria	2006	Associated professor	Decision making, Customer retention, International Marketing.
Massachusetts	Solimano Andres	2008	Doctor in Economics	Growth, development and international migration.
Norway	Nesset Erik	2007	Professor in economics	Industrial economics, market analysis.
United Kingdom	Bowen Nick	2013	Principal lecturer in international business at the European Business School	International Business and Economics.
Australia	Mazzarol Tim	1998	Winthrop Professor	International education marketing and management, Innovation, entrepreneurship, international marketing of services, marketing and strategy.
United Kingdom	Dennis Marguerite	1998	Vice-President for development and enrolment at Suffolk University, Member Board of Trustees	International strategic planning, Strategic enrolment retention.

United Kingdom	Raimo Vincenzo	2014	Pro-Vice-Chancellor, Global Higher Education specialist, Commentator and consultant	International student recruitment agents, a higher education network.
Indianapolis	Standifird Stephen	2005	Dean Butler Lacy School of Business	Leadership, finances, and marketing.
United States	Clarke Roberta	1992	Associate professor emeritus, marketing	Management research and strategies.
Colorado, USA	Borden Neil	1964	Professor of Harvard Business Review	Marketing advertising.
Alabama, USA	Murphy Patrick	1981	Professor of marketing, university of Notre Dame	Marketing ethics, micromarketing.
Zaragoza	Marzo Navarro Mercedes	2005	Professor and researcher	Marketing management and market research.
Chicago	Kotler Philip	1981	Distinguished professor of international marketing	Marketing management, principles of marketing, Market your way to grow winning global markets.
Pennsylvania	Ivy Jonathan	2008	Doctor in behaviour analysis and special education. Assistant professor of psychology	Marketing mix, behaviour analysis, behavioural economics
United Kingdom	Binsardi Ben	2003	Senior lecturer, Departmental research Co-Ordinator, Wrexham Glyndwr university	marketing mix, research methodology, digital marketing research and financial accounting.

Argentina	Padilla Beatriz	2007	Associate Professor at the University of Illinois, Senior Research	Migrations, public policies, social movements, gender, race, ethnicity.
United Kingdom	Douglas Jacqueline	2006	Senior Lecturer, Liverpool Business School	Student satisfaction/dissatisfaction with HE quality.
Saudi Arabia	Tayeb Osama	2016	Professor and president of King Abdulaziz University. International Advisory Board	Teaching and learning, HE administration, and professional development. Culture, politics and education
Alabama, USA	Morgan Robert	1994	PhD Phifer Fellow and Professor of Marketing and Director of the STEM path to the MBA	Thrust theory of relationship, theory of competition.
United Kingdom	Sitkin Alan	2013	Senior lecturer and pathway leader for the MA in international business	Politics and finance. Economic and commercial research. Language and sustainability.
METHODOLOGY				
Germany	Husserl Edmund	1999	Professor of Philosophy	Methodology, Phenomenology philosophy.
United States	Maxwell Joseph	2015	Professor Emeritus in the College of Education and Human Development	Author of Qualitative research. Qualitative analysis, Mixed methods, Research design.
Stockholm	Gummesso n Evert	1994	Professor Emeritus of Service marketing and management at Stockholm business school	Qualitative methods, services marketing, research methodologies, and relationship marketing.
Australia	Silverman David	2013	Visiting professor University of Technology in Sydney	research in qualitative social research, ethnomethodology.

Nigeria	Danjuma Ibrahim	2016	Head of Department and Dean, Modibbo Adama University of Technology	Research methodology, thematic analysis, qualitative enquiry, strategic marketing approaches, customer service and students' enrolment.
United Kingdom	Cohen Louis	2017	Emeritus professor of education at Loughborough University	Research methods in education, strategies for data collection, data analysis, and planning educational research.
United Kingdom	Saunders Mar NK	2007	professor of business research methods, Birmingham Business school	Research methods for business students, business and management, qualitative research, reliability data, and the research onion.
Norway	Helgesen Oyvind	2007	Professor in marketing and management accounting	Service and relationship management, customer profitability accounting, international business strategy, and marketing.
United States	Mack Natasha	2005	researcher in Social and Behavioural	Social and Behavioural research, Qualitative research methods.
United Kingdom	Bryman Alan	2016	Professor of Organizational and social research	Social research methods, Recruitment process.
United Kingdom	Joffe Helene	1999	Professor of Psychology	Thematic analysis, a Qualitative research method.

Table 2.4. Theoretical Framework.

2.14. Summary

The literature review has been important in this study because it takes into consideration the various facets that describe the process of international student recruitment such as Colombian background and culture, role of agents in the recruitment process, HEIs performance, current strategies, use of marketing theories that help to enhance the student's needs, retention and the recruitment of potential clients with a higher standard of customer service.

Educational organisations in the UK are aware of the effects of globalisation and how English-speaking countries are highly competitive. For this reason, countries globally are using technology as an emerging trend, developing new projects in marketing, branding, recruitment and enrolment to attract students around the world.

HEIs in the UK regularly review the standards and regulations governing the institutions across the country, requirements and support for non-European international students (Marginson and Wende, 2006).

There exists a lack of consistency between universities and colleges that enrol students without a proper understanding of culture, purpose and general preparation needed for them to fit into the institution and ultimately obtain mutual benefits. Thus, studies related to best practices and methods to recruit and retain international students are necessary to examine what can be done to improve the situation. Recently, universities have found it more effective financially and culturally to employ agencies with extensive expertise to recruit students instead of sending an agent from the university to a prospective country to meet new students (Willems, 2013).

Also, there are no similar models related to the participation of students in the provision of services that have been proven in the field of higher education

(Maxwell, 2015). Therefore, it can be concluded that marketing theory is a recently created phenomenon in education (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014).

Recruitment strategies must focus not merely in teaching standards, but also recruit well trained researchers that teach skills (Kolster, 2012; Becker and Ozturgut, 2013; Martin et al., 2013; Mercer, 2015), in order to improve customer satisfaction (Zeithaml et al., 2010; Joseph et al., 2005; Tuten and Solomon, 2015), cultural enjoyment and gain work experience.

This chapter provides an overall framework concerning what is known about the main research question from the past and accomplishes four objectives. An analysis has been performed of the different aspects researched in the literature, which are crucial in shaping this study of the recruitment of Colombian students as a new market, their motivations and goals, the role of representatives, HEIs internal capabilities, resources and marketing practices. The literature found that researchers have conducted similar analyses on different populations, indicating a lack of research on this type of target population, as Colombian students belong to.

The information gathered is based on objectives to clearly understand the operational guidelines used in HEIs and their effectiveness. It is based on agents and the experiences of Colombian students in the UK, to reach this market more effectively according to culture and customer needs (Saunders et al., 2007)

To strengthen the literature review, the next chapter of methodology explains the reason why the researcher believes that phenomenology (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015) is the most suitable methodological approach in this qualitative assumption paradigm. The inductive approach is based on verbal data collected through semi-structured interviews with the support of N-VIVO software (Joffe, 2012; Bazeley and Jackson, 2013). This non-probability sampling is chosen because of a requirement for a specific type of person in order to answer the research questions of this thesis.

CHAPTER 3

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This chapter is concerned with the methodology of the study that answer the research questions and explains how the approach was decided. It provides a justification for the use of qualitative method approach and explanation of the process on the research design and sampling used to reach the objectives (Stake, 1995).

This proposal examines the various research instruments that are employed in the context of design methodology, population, sampling, highlighting the data collection methods in the adopted qualitative research as well as the analysis and interpretation of the research problem (Dey, 1993; Stake, 1995; Cohen et al., 2003; Mack et al., 2005; Moffatt, 2015).

For this reason, it considers behaviours, attitudes and values from Colombian people in a specific environment and companies that work with HEIs. Institutions attempt to be competitive in a global market but need to be aware of cultural response planning in order to satisfy the Colombian customers (Jogulu and Bansiri, 2011). The paradigm used in this research is explained in detail in the next Figure.

Figure 3.1. Qualitative Research Paradigm

Figure 3.1. explains the qualitative research paradigm used in this study. Qualitative research (Mack et al., 2005; Yilmaz, 2013; Creswell and Poth, 2017) based on constructivist epistemology is more suitable in this study because the information collected is individual and the questions more specific in order to obtain more detailed involvement at a personal level and gain perceptions, thoughts and information from experienced participants.

Consequently, the knowledge is psychologically and socially constructed through interaction with the participant. Constructivists or interpretivists (Poland, 1995; Myers, 1997; Cohen et al., 2017) enhance the level of awareness about the way that the world is constructed socially through human experiences, and the researcher interprets their experiences through the participants' eyes. The chapter comes to an end by analysing the ethical implications and the process that was undertaken in this study.

3.2. Research Philosophy

The assumptions of philosophical research contribute to the direction of the research and the specific paradigm. Saunders et al., (2007) raise two main philosophies: positivism and interpretivism paradigms. The epistemological position defines interpretivism as a philosophy that allows one to observe the social world and describe how people interpret information and express themselves based on their experiences in order to reach conclusions based on what happens in reality (Atkinson et al., 2001)

The interpretive/ constructivist paradigm (Poland, 1995; Myers, 1997) in this study describes people actions in a specific time in their life, their interests and beliefs related to their own experience in education (Cohen et al., 2007). The interpretative paradigm and the personal history obtained through semi structured interviews, allows the researcher to focus on the research questions and strategy of the study.

3.3. Research Strategy and Objectives

Colombian students are committed leaders and professionals, motivated and enthusiastic with a desire to develop new knowledge, contributing to the economic development of their country. Unfortunately, several situations, such as currency exchange, new regulations adopted by the UKBA due to the problem of immigrants from all over the world to the UK, have led to a decline in the number of Colombian students in the UK. For this reason, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are seeking to increase their revenue by developing new strategies to increase the market once Colombian students have fulfilled the requirements necessary to obtain a place in the educational institution and have secured a visa. Against this backdrop, designing innovative strategies that encourage Colombian students who are seeking opportunities to improve their lifestyle, employment prospects and broaden their knowledge.

This research attempts to examine the main marketing strategies that engage Colombian students in Higher Education Institutions, evaluate processes and customers' needs according to the culture and measure whether those strategies need to be reviewed and what new innovative ideas can be implemented in order to establish the market in the UK.

The four research questions proposed are based on the main question of the research and confirm the qualitative approach selected in this study. They would contribute to the improvement of university performance, student satisfaction and decision-making process.

Research question one **(RQ1): What are the usual marketing strategies employed while recruiting Colombian students to the UK in the higher education sector?**

In order to answer the question, the information provided by the representatives of the agencies is obtained through a small sample that gives more importance to the data quality and analytical skills of the researcher. The representatives needed for this data have a small elite of specialised agencies in the Colombian and British markets. In the same way, the information provided by the students who were recruited by different universities is considered.

Research question two **(RQ2): How effective are these strategies in recruitment from a Colombian student's perspective?**

A reasonable number of students and some representatives were interviewed to collect this data. It would allow the analysis of the needs and the desire of the participants in order to obtain better opportunities for future students. Customer's feedback provides important data to understand what is needed to improve on different issues when this group of people arrives in the UK.

Research question three **(RQ3): What are the operational guidelines for university student recruitment?**

The information collected in the secondary data, Colombian students' experiences and representative agents, give a clear understanding about operational guidelines of higher educational institutions in the UK. Understanding that HEIs seek to increase brand awareness, engage students and provide high quality services.

Research question four **(RQ4): What recommendations can be made to universities in selecting the best marketing strategies to enhance recruitment and improve student retention in the UK?**

An in-depth analysis of the collected data provides new insight into the business phenomena in HEIs in relation to Latin American culture and the necessity of overseas students.

3.4. Justification for the paradigm and methodology

In order to understand the methodology used in this study, it is fundamental to differentiate the meaning of each assumption in qualitative research. It possesses certain characteristics that are defined as a group of philosophical assumptions that determine the next step in this study (Morgan and Smircich, 1980; Hill et al., 2005; Elo and Kyngas, 2007; Yilmaz, 2013).

Ontology is identified as the nature of reality by Antwi and Hamza (2015), Mertens (2010), who recognise multiple realities, which means that individual background and experience influence the participant's point of view. The research question can be, in some cases, ontological and epistemological due to what the participants say.

An axiological assumption called the nature of ethics, Mertens (2010), is based on the improvement of social justice and promotes human rights and respect for norms.

Epistemological assumption is influenced by the knowledge of the participant in the topic, and the connection between the participant and researcher (Hill et al.,

2005). Yet the conclusion drawn from a reflexive examination of the different philosophical assumptions confirms that an epistemological assumption is more suitable for this study due to the danger of the researcher influencing the participant by making enquiries about their own experiences while the participant clarifies the phenomenon.

Some recent qualitative research (Elo and Kyngas, 2007; Creswell and Poth, 2017) agreed that the approaches must adapt to the research according to the individual problem under investigation. For this reason, the analysis of multiple options guides the researcher into a more interesting and engaging process rather than adopting just one approach. Researchers (Sandelowski, 2000; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Creswell, 2014) describe a progression from the paradigm to the empirical world through five approaches: narrative, phenomenology (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015), grounded theory, ethnography and case studies. These approaches differ from each other with individual literature and characteristics to develop the strategy of the qualitative research (Elo and Kyngas, 2007; Mertens, 2010). The most widely used qualitative approaches are: narrative, case studies, grounded theory and phenomenology. Each approach is useful depending on the research purpose, data collection and analysis of the information collected by the researcher.

The narrative inquiry method (Josselson, 1996; McCormack, 2004; Clandinin, 2006; Elliot, 2015) in social research emphasises the cooperation and interaction between one or more participants and the researcher. The inquiry interaction method (Polkinghorne, 1995) uses four basic approaches: biographical study, autobiography, life history and oral history to describe personal aspects and meaningful experiences of a person or people. This narrative is unique to specific spectators due to the sequence of the events from the beginning to the end, bringing a conclusion and engaging those who are interested in the story. The researcher bears the responsibility of presenting the information obtained from the participants (Clandinin, 2006). The challenge for researchers who adopt this narrative approach is the capacity to understand the considerable amount of

information and the identification and analysis of the relevant aspects of peoples' lives. The narrative approach is useful in different disciplines, for example, in marketing, a narrative approach leads to the recounting of the everyday experience of the consumer (Padgett and Allen, 1997). The "narrative" or "stories" provided by the consumers are interpreted in an average account that represents how consumers identify with a brand.

The case study is a methodology in qualitative research that allows the researcher to analyse the phenomenon under study in a real context. (Dey, 1993; Yin, 2012) researchers who have a case with a problem of restricted time or place use the case study design. The case study has the same degree of validity and reliability as the others, but it is very valuable whether it is applied with seriousness and rigour in order to obtain validity and reliability in the results. (Eisenhardt, 1989; Stake, 1995) This method is commonly applied in research strategies in companies and management work, where an increasing number of study observations are required. However, there are many disciplines in case study research which show that it is difficult to find a detailed definition of these practices (Rialp et al., 2005), also it is used in education, medicine, physiology, governmental or law. It takes place in a program or event where the data is collected using interviews, documents, and observations. The issues in design strategy consist of identifying problems. The study undertaken by Stake (1995) argues that a case study explores the complexity of a situation in depth in order to achieve an understanding of how people behave in certain circumstances. All these authors Eisenhardt (1989), Stake (1995), Rialp et al., (2005) underline that both in the design of a case study and in the characteristics of the qualitative method, emphasis should be placed on the analysis and interpretation of the information collected in order to produce a final report.

Grounded theory explains a process of experiences over time in different phases, it primarily uses interviews with individuals to collect the data. The interviews are constructed and shaped during the interaction with each participant and subsequently analysed and compared (Gubrium et al., 2012).

Glaser and Strauss (1999) agree that existing theories cannot solve the type of problems that are expressed in all research studies. It is because a theory is developed from the concerns of people in a specific area, and there are cases when new theories need to be created. Grounded theory discovers emerging patterns from the collected data in order to address the population's interests and needs.

The ethnography method, as its name implies, links the object of study with the culture. Accordingly, Geertz (1973) understands culture as a group of mental processes with communicative significance that can be understood as a result of human behaviour in a specific time and space. This study comprehends human actions that build the world where people live as members of a community (Hammersley and Atkinson 1983). On the other hand, the anthropologist Spradley (2016) argues that ethnography must be understood as a culture where the researcher learns from people instead of a theory. Spradley (2016) states that the study is also based on five basic characteristics, these are: culture, cultural experience, cultural information, meaning and cultural description. According to this researcher, to achieve the information most clearly, the objective must create work tools. The fieldwork is based on the selection and contact of a cultural scene with a group of specific key participants to gather the most relevant cultural data. This information leads to data analysis and description of the culture that can be known as strategic ethnography.

Phenomenology is a popular procedure where the researcher attempts to comprehend people's experiences concerning a phenomenon (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015). It is commonly used in nursing, health science, sociology, and education (Smith et al., 1999).

This phenomenological method is based on two basic facts that describe pre-scientific and scientific aspects. In this philosophical dilemma, Husserl (1999) explained that the human mind or the brain is objective and tangible, therefore, according to Husserl, phenomenology is a science that discovers the basic structures of consciousness. Therefore, this method must avoid presuppositions

and prejudices to get a real description of the world. On the other hand, Heidegger in Martinez (2012) describes phenomenology as a science that interprets and explains the phenomena that are shown by themselves, which means that they are true and scientific. These phenomena are influenced by the socio-cultural environment in which the person is constantly exposed and expressed through the language.

To conclude, the concept of phenomenology can be defined as the analysis of the phenomena experienced by the human being through one's own perception of reality, of individual feelings. (Martínez, 2012). Therefore, this method of qualitative research (Stake, 1995) has a wide range of possibilities that allow the researchers to explore human behaviour, understand their attitudes and social environment.

The phenomenological method has some stages in the qualitative study. The descriptive stage, the structural stage, and the discussion stage. The first descriptive step reflects the reality of the phenomenon that is being studied using different procedures such as narrative, interview, and direct observation. Particularly, this study uses interviews that aim to obtain a deeper understanding of the experiences lived by the participants. It must be borne in mind that there are difficulties when collecting the data because the researcher needs to maintain a rigorous objectivity in order to obtain genuine information.

The structural stage seeks to describe the information obtained, but it must be considered that the human cognitive activity displays rapid changes when speaking and does not follow strict sequences of information related to the lived experience. To achieve an adequate analysis of the phenomena (Husserl, 1999; Heidegger in Martinez, 2012), it is necessary to organise the interview by thematic units that highlight the central subject further in a structural sequence that leads to the correct utilisation of the interviews with the participants.

The discussion stage seeks to relate the information obtained from the participants in the interviews, with the research done in the primary data from

other researchers. This comparison allows conclusions to be obtained that complement the object of study with the use of ideas and sequences that result in scientific rigor (Hycner, 1985).

3.5. Justification of the Research Approach

The emphasis of the exploratory strategy is to provide insights into individual actions that look for quality participants and, through responses, for this reason, it involves a relatively small group of people. This exploratory research engages the participants and provides them the possibility to respond freely in their own words, respecting their individual personalities (Mack et al., 2005).

Figure 3.2. Methodology used in this Study

Figure 3.2. explains in detail the method followed in this qualitative research. Related to the research study, three approaches can be used: deductive,

inductive or even mixed methods (Morgan, 2007; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015), thus this research is based on verbal data face to face and online interviews; the most suitable approach for this research is inductive due to the observation of process of recruitment procedures and behaviours based on insights (Ozturgut, 2013), priorities and experiences that have affected people studying in the UK and agents that are currently working in the UK and Colombia recruiting and interviewing students (Willems, 2013). The interpretation of this data would deliver new strategies that aim to improve the HEIs performance (Anderson, 2009). In the inductive approach, the data determines the structure of the analysis and the development of the codes. The researcher carefully reads the qualitative data in order to organise it into teams or patterns. The codes are developed to represent those teams, this information leads to the confirmation of the theory.

The purpose of this phenomenological study is to develop innovative strategies for the higher education sector in the UK (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015). Different types of interview methods can be used in qualitative research: semi-structured, structured and unstructured interviews (Smith et al., 1999; Cohen et al., 2003; Kothari, 2004; Gray, 2014). In this qualitative study, a non-probability method is used to explore the research topic through interviews discussing strategies that can be used to improve the consistency and accuracy of the data collection.

3.6. Research design strategy

In this study, this strategy is used to explain the marketing theories that are applied to the phenomena in question (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004; Heidegger in Martinez, 2012) in order to use them to increase the international movement. This process leads to more opportunities for Colombian students and improves the competitiveness of the UK in the global educational market (Russell, 2005; Ariani, 2015).

Thomas Kuhn describes a Paradigm as *"A representation of people's value judgments, norms, standards, frames of reference, perspectives, ideologies,*

myths, theories, and approved procedures that govern their thinking and action” (as quoted in Gummesson, 2000, p. 18).

The purpose of qualitative research (Dey, 1993) is to explore new phenomena (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004), examine the way that people perceive and experience a specific topic and make inquiries. It addresses questions like ‘why’ specific behaviour takes place, people’s thoughts, perceptions and interpretations of the process. This is contrasted with quantitative methods, which examine ‘Who’ is involved and ‘What’ is happening in order to test certain interventions. Many researchers use a combination of both methods in their investigations.

In the research approaches, the data is composed of quantitative (Positivistic) or qualitative (phenomenological) paradigm or mixed methods using the approaches in their investigations (Husserl, 1999; Morgan, 2007; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015). Quantitative data is more inflexible but allows comparisons of answers between participants to be done easily (Smith et al., 1999; Elo and Kyngas, 2007). It has different types of questions, analytical objectives that confirm or reject a hypothesis about the phenomena (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004). It uses other kinds of collection instruments such as surveys, closed-ended questionnaires, and structured observations. Numerical values are assigned to participants’ answers to allow analysis and presentation of results.

The qualitative structure design guides the method of this study focusing on the subjectivity of the research, this data includes processes and focuses on behaviours, student’s words by observation, personal experiences, feelings and concepts that are not possible to represent numerically (Stake, 1995).

The five most commonly used techniques in qualitative research have been described in detail above (phenomenology, narrative, case study, ethnography and grounded theory). This research focuses on phenomenological qualitative research method (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004; Mack et al., 2005; Elo and

Kyngas, 2007). Its strength is describing the experiences of people with similar characteristics and specific cultural information of a given research issue.

In qualitative methods, researchers usually select participant observation, focus groups or in-depth interviews. Each method has its characteristics and is designed to gather explicit data (Stake, 1995; Mack et al., 2005). The first interview would be conducted individually with fifteen to twenty Colombian people describing their experiences as tertiary students in the UK. The second interview would be completed individually with seven to ten agents who work with universities in the UK recruiting Colombian people (Raimo et al., 2014), using the strategies given by universities to engage customers.

This qualitative sampling is related to the people selected to participate in the research, (Dey, 1993; Cohen et al., 2003; Mack et al., 2005) it normally relates to non-probability sampling (non-random) and exploratory because the topic is not well known and requires the evaluation of specific people with the knowledge in the topic, i.e. Colombians that have had experience of working and studying in the UK.

3.7. Data Collection Methods

In phenomenological research projects (Dey, 1993; Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015), the most common qualitative data collection method is that of interviewing (Elo and Kyngas, 2007). The recordings and notes that are gathered during the interviews can be extensive and sometimes difficult to categorise and analyse in a way to produce meaningful results (Mack et al., 2005). The recordings and taking notes of conversations in a qualitative research interview can also be time-consuming, particularly if interviews have to be transcribed. Semi-structured interviews give participants the freedom to express themselves freely. This interview should be done in Spanish, transcribed and translated into English. Participants must give consent to the recording of the interview (Dey, 1993; Smith et al., 1999; Cohen et al., 2003).

There are coding methods that are related to epistemological research question that seeks to understand the phenomena (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004). The most usual software used is N-VIVO because it helps to interpret the qualitative data gathered (Bazeley and Jackson, 2013). This data software N-VIVO uses headings to compare and identify relationships in order for the results to be valid, (Lester, 1999; Elo and Kyngas, 2007).

The researcher has chosen N-VIVO software, Thematic analysis, Joffe (2012) as a tool to examine the information and provide meaning to the process of social construction. It means that interviews inform about a topic through explanations, beliefs and attitudes, but on the other hand, they hide emotions and behaviours based on feelings of the participant. The phenomenological findings from the data and the application of the theories must be transparent, discussing how the researcher comes to the interpretations (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004).

In relation to the thematic analysis, there are few guides that show the process used as techniques. Some researchers like Boyatzis (1998); Clarke and Braun (2013) offer useful information to carry out this process, in this way the researcher must design a thematic coding framework with the guidelines that the software offers. This framework contains a group of nodes based on the information obtained that guide the process.

3.8. Qualitative Sampling Method

The approach of non-probability sampling is used in this research to gather qualitative information from students and agents. Given (2008) mentions three types of qualitative methods to collect evidence: purposive sampling, convenience sampling and snowball sampling. This research would use convenience sampling because both students and agents are interested in participating. However, in order to gather sufficient interviews, the researcher would additionally use a purposive sampling, specifically selecting people who fulfil the characteristics required as experience in the market and have relevance to the research questions (Cohen et al., 2003; Mack et al., 2005; Bryman, 2012).

In general, the qualitative data collection takes three forms: focus groups, observation and interviews. This study would use interviews that are more personal, and collect detailed information, insights, opinions and feelings. The interviews are further divided into three main types: semi-structured, informal, and standardized open ended (Bryman, 2012).

The first collection of data is an interview described as two-person communication or verbal interaction with the purpose of gathering relevant information, and focused on the research objectives. The semi-structured interview has been chosen because the questions are listed out and the researcher has the opportunity to change or add information during the conversation, depending on the participant's responses to ensure consistency, appropriate information and make the interview more comfortable for the interviewee. This data is useful because it leads to detailed and meaningful data whilst keeping sensitive information about the participant confidential and private (Smith et al., 1999; Cohen, 2007). This interview is applied to fifteen or twenty Colombian students, conducted via Skype or face-to-face, where the researcher and respondent interact directly. These respondents must have studied or are currently studying in the UK and obtained the type of Tier 4 visa for this purpose. During this exercise, the interviewer would gather basic personal information, respondents' expectations and procedures before travelling, and what the customers' needs are before deciding to study in the UK. This enables them to obtain direct feedback to identify the key issues that need further improvement.

The primary data is collected Face to Face and on Skype interviews with agents that work with different universities in the UK. These people have a special interest in the Colombian market because of previous recruitment experience or a cultural connection with Colombia country (Ozturgut, 2013).

The aim is to collect the information necessary for HEIs to improve the service and student experience. The information provided would be used to create new strategies that engage more students adding value to higher education institutions at the same time as catering for the Colombian culture and needs.

The prerequisites for interviewees' eligibility is that they must be at least eighteen years old, must have already studied English and/or a professional level of education such as undergraduates, postgraduates, master's degrees and/or doctoral program in the UK institutions.

The sample size for qualitative research studies is usually smaller than that used in quantitative research. One of the reasons for this is the time taken to analyse the data that is produced from interviews. Englander (2012) describes that qualitative research focuses on questions like 'How is ...?' while the quantitative approach (Smith et al., 1999; Elo and Kyngas, 2007) is generally posed as 'How many' or 'How much...?'. The questions that the researcher seeks to answer would determine the type of approach that is most suitable for the study. That is, if the answers to the question can be measured, then the study lends itself to quantitative methods; by contrast, more open-ended questions that cannot be answered with a number are better suited to qualitative research, where the collective experience of subjects provides the insight. A study where the questions fall into both categories is best addressed by a combination of the two approaches, this is usually referred to as a 'Mixed Methods' approach (Mack et al., 2005; Morgan, 2007; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015).

In order to conduct qualitative research effectively, researchers should possess the necessary knowledge of the subject under investigation. They must also be aware of the ethical considerations and those relating to data protection that need to be considered. They must also be good interviewers, having the ability to elicit meaningful information from interviewees. A further responsibility of the researcher is to be able to identify the useful pieces of information from the vast amounts of data gathered from interviews and discard those that are redundant (Dey, 1993).

Participant selection plays a vital role in an effective qualitative study, they must have relevant exposure to the topic under investigation (Smith et al., 1999). The quality of the information from participants can vary; some have more knowledge of the topic than others, and some are more willing to take part in the interview

than others. Morse (2000) suggests that twenty or thirty unstructured interviews are appropriate in phenomenological research (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004); however, several interviews are relevant, but it is more important the amount of information obtained from each participant because this information provides a better and prompt analysis.

Quantitative research methodology is the most commonly used method, and it is based on the positivist paradigm. It is inappropriate for this study (Smith et al., 1999; Morgan, 2007; Saunders et al., 2007; Elo and Kyngas, 2007). It needs a large number of participants in order to reveal explanatory universal laws through the measurement and analysis of statistical information or numerical data. The researcher uses a deductive approach with pre-constructed and planned questions and set answers derived from theory. Participants are required to select the most appropriate options of the questions according to their experience, but it does not capture their thoughts, feelings or own point of view (Mack et al., 2005).

Quantitative and qualitative methods are grounded on different philosophical foundations and possess their distinctive characteristics that guide the investigations on separate phenomena (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004; Hill et al., 2005; Saunders et al., 2007; Denzin and Lincoln, 2011; Creswell and Poth, 2017). Nevertheless, qualitative and quantitative methods can be linked under mixed methods research in a single investigation (Mack et al., 2005; Morgan, 2007; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015).

3.9. Access Issues and Ethical Considerations

The involvement and cooperation of students and agents in this research would be vital to reach the objectives of this study (Willets, 2013), the researcher would interact directly with the participant to gather accurate, personal experience information from students in order to improve the customer service in HEIs and agents who have experience with universities with the aim of encouraging new Colombians to study in the UK.

The new EU legal framework for data protection, called the General Data Protection Regulation GDPR, stated on 25th of May 2018 (legislation.gov.uk, 2018), it substitutes the Data Protection Act 1998 (legislation.gov.uk, 2005). This regulation presents a new law protecting the digital age in organisations that work with collecting and using personal data. The students and agents would be aware of the purpose of this research, the advantages, future benefits to UK HE institutions and Colombian students and how their cooperation and use of their personal data could help future Colombian people travel and make the most of their studies in the UK.

Figure 3.3. Ethical Considerations. (Source own Figure)

Figure 3.3. describes how the fundamental principles of respect, beneficence and justice in this research ethics would be applied. Respect for people during this process, the identity of each participant is protected, email addresses and recordings, whether participants accept them, would be kept confidential in order to prove the authenticity of this research and subsequently deleted (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2008). Maximising the benefits that result from the analysis of the information obtained and reducing the risks of sharing personal information. Justice, ensuring a commitment where the participants would receive the benefit

of being part of the investigation (Mack et al., 2005). In a casual verbal interaction, the participants are informed about the research purpose, the time that it is expected to take in a clear and comprehensible way.

It is unnecessary that participants sign a consent document since the type of information collected is uncontroversial, unsusceptible and safe. Any other resources found during the research would be listed in the last section of the references in order to give credit to the original author (Torjesen, 2012).

3.10. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Figure 3.4. Data Analysis and Interpretation. (Source: own Figure)

Figure 3.4. explains the process followed to analyse the data collected and its subsequent interpretation. The research is composed of face-to-face and online interviews using Skype to reach students and agents in Colombia, as well as meeting them personally in the UK. The invitation is sent by email or by phone call to reach Colombian students. The interviews for students are designed in subcategories that include decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006),

pre-departure, studying abroad, students' services and cultural activities, intercultural engagement, university impact and experiences.

The interview for institution representatives or agents is sub-categorized into recruitment process (Ozturgut, 2013), student's expectations and, university marketing strategies. Interviews would last thirty to forty minutes and consist of twenty questions approximately, the data is attached as appendices.

The feedback delivered by Colombian students with Tier 4 visas paying full fees would provide a relevant overview related to the best practices, preferences, and opinions of the quality of service provided by educational institutions in the UK (Peters, 1992). It is useful for educational organisations to review and develop new strategies proposed in this research to engage Colombian students and gain valuable customer insights. This qualitative data would help to identify trends relating to complaints, strengths, quality of service, and student experience (Sultan and Wong, 2012).

This interview method has been chosen so that the customer can express themselves freely. This type of interview is time-consuming but can reach a certain type of people with similar characteristics; it tends to incur transportation expenses and requires a voice recorder to record the interview.

Another difficulty is that opinions are from a wider range of topics from the Colombian population who have been in different institutions in the UK, but all students have one thing in common that is the experience of having studied in the UK. On the other hand, there is always a group that desires to return to study in the UK if the country offers them better opportunities.

This type of data covers a broad range of topics applicable to education and customer satisfaction (Joseph et al., 2005; Zeithaml et al., 2010; Tuten and Solomon, 2015) in UK institutions, and from this data, theoretical elaboration would emerge. The questions are carefully designed and developed to be short and easy to understand, based on a literature review of marketing strategies.

They would have a duration of thirty to forty minutes, approximately, to provide them a rewarding experience, collect more responses and keep the interviewee engaged.

The secondary data is gathered previously from journals, books, research reports, theses, videos, UK government websites and the internet. This information gathered is inexpensive and relatively easy and quickly to access.

In context, secondary data provides the information from universities, strategies used in marketing recruitment (Ozturgut, 2013), government rules and support, Colombian culture and background. However, it has been collected for other purposes and makes the information for this study in some way useful but limited.

Miles et al., (1994) and Smith et al., (1999) describe a traditional way of testing a conclusion from the data collected, as when the information can be contrasted and compared, it shows how strong the insights are. In qualitative research, the analysis of the information collected by the participants is organised in a pattern code. The information is labelled strategically before continuing with the next step of analysis. An important point in this kind of categorisation is the meaning of contribution to the research, connecting the relationship between variables.

Elo and Kyngas (2007) defend the idea that inductive content analysis organises the qualitative data in open coding producing several categories and abstraction. In this context, to describe the aspects of the content, the interviews must be thoroughly analysed in order to create the necessary headlines that answer the research questions.

As appropriate methods of study are adopted for the subject, the work becomes more scientific, so when using the N-VIVO software (Joffe, 2012; Bazeley and Jackson, 2013), it is necessary to show reliability and validity (Eisenhardt, 1989; Stake, 1995) of the way in which the data were selected, compiled and analysed. In this way, the coding table provides access to the coding framework and the exact place where that type of information is found. Researchers must show

transparency and evidence of the original information to create a link between interpretation and evidence (Yardley, 2000; Silverman, 2013)

The theory is relative, and no method can be considered universal or definitive because society acts with its values that change over time; this human behaviour is complex and difficult to explain. Therefore, in data coding, it is a process that segments or fragments the data to give meaning to the objectives and research questions (Silverman, 2013).

3.11. Process of conducting qualitative analysis using N-VIVO

Adopting the N-VIVO software (Joffe, 2012) and applying it to the data collected demonstrates the description of most of the data collected that goes beyond selecting examples of interview segments that support arguments (Boyatzis, 1998; Bazeley and Jackson, 2013; Clarke and Braun, 2013). This software enables the management of substantial amounts of data. The thematic analysis reflects an objective perspective of the data and its meaning within a specific context of streams instead of attributing excessive importance to the repetition of nodes extracted from the data (Greenhalgh and Taylor, 1997; Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006).

Name	Sources	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By
1. Usual marketing strategies are employed while recruiting Colombian students to the UK in higher education sector	8	20:24	LS		28/05/2018 20:37	LS
motivation to come to the UK	17	53	28/05/2018 20:38	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
importance of studying abroad english, job, profession	16	32	28/05/2018 20:39	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
students priorities	6	13	28/05/2018 20:41	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
Students English language level	13	29	28/05/2018 20:42	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
Agency	15	45	03/06/2018 16:38	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
negative issues with agencies	4	10	03/06/2018 16:48	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
Family resources	9	11	03/06/2018 16:47	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
Friends influence, feedback	12	22	12/06/2018 11:46	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
difficulties in UK	14	30	03/06/2018 17:04	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
countries visited before the UK	8	10	03/06/2018 16:23	LS	23/07/2018 22:19	LS
Professional program	12	24	03/06/2018 16:59	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
normal visa process	6	9	28/05/2018 20:44	LS	25/06/2018 22:30	LS
Issues visa process	8	14	03/06/2018 16:52	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
online information	10	22	28/05/2018 20:43	LS	23/07/2018 20:43	LS
loans support	14	27	03/06/2018 16:53	LS	07/08/2018 17:42	LS
2. How effective are these strategies from Colombian student	0	0	28/05/2018 20:25	LS	12/06/2018 11:13	LS
3. What are the operational guidelines for university student	0	0	28/05/2018 20:26	LS	19/06/2018 12:02	LS
4. Innovative marketing strategies to the universities in order	0	0	28/05/2018 20:27	LS	28/05/2018 20:37	LS

Figure 3.5. Process of Conducting Qualitative Analysis Using N-VIVO (1)

In order to clarify the process used to cluster the 24 interviews, Figure 3.5. explains how the four research questions were used to organise the information provided for each participant. The first research question was divided into 14 nodes, the sources in the graph show the number of students that contributed with relevant information to the Agency node in the first research question.

Figure 3.6 Process of Conducting Qualitative Analysis Using N-VIVO (2)

Figure 3.6. explains in more detail how the information was clustered manually. The first research question has 14 nodes; the first node in this research question is called “Agency”. The Sources indicate that 15 participants contributed to answering the node Agency (Appendix B)

The information selected manually is identified by references (Figure 3.6), the researcher read carefully every interview and underlined the relevant information in each interview. In the “node Agency”, the “source” of 15 participants contributed 45 useful comments that were selected manually to avoid eliminating important information provided by the interviewees. Although it is time-consuming listening to the recordings several times (Appendix E), typing the interviews in Spanish (Appendix D) and subsequently translating them into English (Appendix C), the researcher found important information at the moment of coding them

manually into N-VIVO software (Appendix E). For this reason, the researcher did not use the word frequency as suggested by the software N-VIVO (Smith et al., 1999) because it does not cover all of the information already found by the researcher.

The relevant information provided by the participants is illustrated in the analysis of this research using vignettes and avoiding ethical issues of confidentiality (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2008; Legislación.gov.uk, 2018). The process of coding categories consists of classifying the data obtained into ideas, concepts and themes. All this information is closely related to the information of the theoretical framework of the investigation.

According to Neuendorf (2017), the encoded information follows processes and guidelines that allow the decomposition and representation of the data that resulting in an accurate description of the characteristics that are present in the content of the interviews. Before starting to code, the researcher must become familiar with the data collected, which is acquired at the time of conducting the interviews and transcribing them. The coding presented in this study is based on the exploration of the material in objective categories. This process requires specific skills so that the coding of the material can be assigned correctly.

3.12. The reliability and validity of the content analysis

This reliability shows the perception and difficulties of interpretation of the codes based on specific characteristics, exhausting the content of the documents based on a registration unit where one category cannot belong to others at the same time, that is, they belong to a single classification of homogeneous categories (Dey, 1993). Recent studies seek to propose and conceptualise new terms that have already been established many years ago to demonstrate more rigorous work.

Researchers (Denzin, 2009; Silverman, 2015; Spiers, et al. 2018) seek to create new strategies that must be used according to each qualitative method and their

respective data collection, but in the end, the quality of a qualitative work depends on the researcher. Therefore, the researcher must explain how he arrived at the proposed results, the ethical decisions, the design, execution and organisation of the investigation. Similarly, in this process, there are incentives to participate; sometimes confidentiality agreements or waivers of consent arise. The report must be accessible, without falsification of data or results, or plagiarism. In this way, the researcher generates confidence because ultimately the quality of a qualitative work rests with the researcher (Spiers, et al. 2018). A better interpretation of the information is obtained after the data coding process, and the selection of results is made. The analysis and abstraction of information result in some conclusions or new meanings of the data, which are based on the theoretical framework (Silverman, 2013).

The descriptive coding used in this study evaluates each code to find the perceptions of the participants about the universities' programmes, schools' courses and customer services, therefore, the magnitude coding seeks to assess the intensity of the information gathered. This process observes the participants' behaviour. (Babin and Griffin 1998; Kaplan and Maxwell, 2005, Maxwell, 2015). It is evident that the codes are directed to the research question, therefore, these must be categorised into topics with specific references to a concept or sequences.

The presentation of the findings provides background and personal information of the participant's experiences. The code strategies that are used, the number of codes identified and their categories, they are presented as findings in a systematic way describing each topic and supported by the evidence gathered from the participants (Yardley, 2000; Silverman, 2013).

3.13. Limitations and delimitations of the study

The questions in the interview are not difficult to understand in English, but it is possible that the participants feel more comfortable and relaxed responding in their native Spanish. However, it is expected that the translation from Spanish

into English will not have an adverse impact on the Data's validity (Spiers, et al. 2018).

3.14. Summary

The descriptive phenomenon (Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004) highlights positive and negative features of the theoretical models. The evaluation of the models must consider the volume of responses, i.e. a view held by the majority of respondents carries more weight than one held by a minority. The analysis of the primary and secondary data provides answers to the research questions formulated (Elo and Kyngas, 2007). Englander (2012) agrees that this process requires constant changes in procedures, interview questions, connection between participant and phenomena (Dey, 1993; Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015) and between participants and interviewer.

The strength of UK institutions is their diversity related to budgets. However, HEIs have the same target and challenges, and if these institutions reach their goal, the resulting benefit is not confined to the education sector but also the country's reputation as a market leader (Mercer, 2015).

In marketing institutions, priorities must be set, especially regarding investment issues and changes. In addition, there must be project management to organise and evaluate the whole company's strengths and weaknesses, to create objectives and deliver the proper decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006).

The next chapter describes how the qualitative research method is characterised by measuring the behaviour of many participants, which justifies the study of supporting theories (Elo and Kyngas, 2007). The general focus of the interviewing of Colombian students is to evaluate their experiences whilst studying in the UK and the processes that made this possible. This interview process also takes into consideration the viewpoint of the agents involved in the recruitment process (Ozturgut, 2013; Willets, 2013). The knowledge obtained through data collection

validates the structure and performance of the HEI, answering the four research questions proposed in this study.

CHAPTER 4

4. DATA COLLECTION ANALYSIS

4.1. Introduction

This qualitative research expects to reinforce the empirical findings in order to encourage HE institutions to achieve branding and position strategies (Mazzarol, 1998; Elo and Kyngas, 2007) based on the objectives and vision of the organization to succeed in the international market (Morgan and Hunt, 1994; Johnston and Clark, 2008).

A generic list of questions divided into topics is used throughout the interviews of agents and Colombian students in order to develop the four research questions. These questions were modified accordingly as a response to the candidate's answers. Thirty-five minutes and one hour were the average interview durations for both groups of interviews.

The semi-structured interviews (Appendix A) were designed to be flexible, allowing the researcher to omit or add questions to clarify and expand important contributions as necessary. This qualitative method collected valuable, rich, and detailed data that helped to reshape the research questions (Elo and Kyngas, 2007). The interviews needed plenty of concentration and attention to detail to lead the conversation and use the time efficiently with the participant. The use of a recording device was a relevant tool to make the conversation more comfortable and observe the answers carefully.

4.2. Interview process

The majority of the conversations were conducted over the phone, via Skype, whilst others were conducted in person. Although the interviews were cost-effective in terms of resources, it proved difficult to establish contact due to the considerable time difference between Colombia and London. Transcribing the interviews in Spanish (Appendix D), as well as the subsequent translation into

English (Appendix C), and organisation into themes and nodes using N-VIVO software (Appendix B) (Joffe, 2012; Bazeley and Jackson, 2013) proved to be an arduous process. The first series of 40-minute interviews took over six hours to transcribe into Spanish and later translate into English, caution was exercised in ensuring the translations were true to the original transcript. A transcript of each interview can be found in the appendices, with the data coded. The analysis of data seeks to find in each section of participants' responses the interpretations, attitudes, variety of meanings and commonalities (Miles et al.,1994).

The eighteen interviews were conducted with Colombian graduates who came to the UK to study English and others subsequently decided to pursue an undergraduate or master's degree. Most of these students returned to Colombia whilst others are currently working in the UK or another country. Those participating in the interviews were enthusiastic and responded positively to the questions asked.

Four of the interviews were conducted with UK agents with a deep knowledge of the HEIs market and specialised in the recruitment of Colombian students and other nationalities. The researcher found that it was easier to talk to the agents who had access to different institutions instead of contacting individual institutions. It was seen that access to institutions individually was difficult, and even more so when it comes to the strategies employed to recruit students. Also, interviewing representatives allowed to analyse the Colombian market expectations and UK experiences in education. At the beginning of each interview, the participants were given a brief outline of the purpose of the research and the importance of their participation was stressed regarding the success of the project.

4.3. Data analysis

Referring to the schedules of the two groups of interviews, shown in Tables 4.1. and 4.2; the questions asked were divided into four groups that address each of the four research questions. The semi structured interviews (Appendix A) were recorded at the end of 2017 and beginning of 2018 (Appendix E). The recordings in Spanish, transcripts in Spanish (Appendix D) and translations into English (Appendix C) are kept strictly to provide authenticity and verification of the transcripts.

Int. number	Date	Duration	Gender	Int. Reference
1	15/11/2017	00:41:11	Female	E1
2	18/11/2017	00:39:31	Male	E2
3	23/11/2017	1:09:15	Male	E3
4	23/11/2017	00:32:29	Male	E4
5	05/12/2017	00:29:07	Female	E5
6	05/12/2017	00:20:45	Female	E6
7	12/12/2017	00:31:17	Female	E7
8	13/12/2018	00:44:12:	Male	E8
9	13/01/2018	00:29:47	Female	E9
10	24/01/2018	00:46:26	Female	E10
11	19/01/2018	00:26:26	Male	E11
12	18/01/2018	00:39:06	Female	E12
13	04/02/2018	00:36:49	Male	E13
14	07/02/2018	00:25:13	Female	E14
15	09/02/2018	00:44:53	Female	E15
16	26/02/2018	00:18:12	Female	E16
17	12/03/2018	00:41:14	Female	E17
18	18/03/2018	00:39:06	Female	E18

Table 4.1. Students Interviews schedule

Interview number	Date	Time	Gender	Interview Reference
1	08/12/2017	00:34:47	Male	R1
2	03/01/2018	00:36:46	Female	R2
3	06/02/2018	00:32:16	Female	R3
4	09/02/2018	00:27:21	Female	R4

Table 4.2. Agency Representatives' interview schedule

A useful strategy to analyse the qualitative data of this research was to listen to the recordings and carefully read transcripts of the interviews several times. This analysis generated categories with headings and classifications that answered the 4 research questions and provided important details that helped to prove the theories in marketing. The information was extracted from the transcripts and summarised using the N-VIVO software (Joffe, 2012; Bazeley and Jackson, 2013). This information was encoded in themes or nodes that contain main ideas about a concept. The themes summarise the main issues that the participants said in relation to the area, underlying patterns, concepts, or ideas (Taylor et al., 2015). The information given describes the main ideas found from the participants and extracts important data from the interviews that support the analysis. N-VIVO software is a tool that helps to categorise a large amount of data in one place (Appendix B), allowing this information to be transparent and observable to the reader (Kaplan and Maxwell, 2005; Maxwell, 2015).

The following analysis represents the main findings from the interviews, and this information is used because it enables to understand the perspectives, behaviours and beliefs of each participant. The phrases in italics and quotations were spoken by students and agents. The quotations, interview number and line number from students are identified by e.g. (E1, line 12) and agents (R1, line 14) followed by three dots at the end.

4.4. Research question 1

The first research question includes 15 nodes from Colombian students’ point of view and 3 nodes from agents supporting this question, as shown in the following Table 4.3.

What are the usual marketing strategies employed while recruiting Colombian students to the UK in the higher education sector?

Colombian students’ data analysis	Agents’ data analysis
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Positive and negative issues with agencies 2. Difficulties living in the UK 3. Students' English language level 4. Family resources and support 5. Friends influence 6. Importance of studying abroad 7. Countries visited before travelling to the UK 8. Financial support 9. Colombian Students’ priorities 10. Motivation to come to the UK 11. Visa process 12. Issues with the visa process 13. Online information for students 14. Professional program interest 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance of an agent from Colombia for the university 2. Issues that an agency faces in the recruitment process 3. Colombian market position in the UK

Table 4.3. Thematic coding analysis research question

4.4.1. Data analysis of Colombian students' recruitment process

1. Agency advantages

Colombian students rely on agencies for their information relating to the place to study in the city or the town, and tips to settle in the country that have worked for other students while studying in the UK. Alternatively, agents offer a wide range of experiences and safety that engage the students, especially when they have not gone abroad (Willets, 2013). Students stated that:

"I did not know the process, I did not know people who had done this traveling process, I did not have friends who had come here to the United Kingdom" (E13, lines 25,26)

Students find it useful that agents speak Spanish, especially to assist them during the process of visa application, information about the recollection of documents (Raimo et al., 2014). Agents have a wide selection of institutions to choose from, in this process some students verify the information given by the agent while others trust them completely because they are convinced of the experience and believe in the previous effective applications. Related to this, students stated that:

"I explained what I wanted" (E11, line 46) ... "They had already sent other students to that program" (E11, lines 47,48) ... "I compared the prices they gave me, to know if it really was a very good choice, however, for the service they gave me, the advice, the experience they also had, I trust them, and I decided to do the process with them" (E13, lines 37-39).

Colombian students research about different programs online but decide to get the agent advice to compare prices and it is an advantage that these agents support the student without cost due to the institutions pay them for recruiting the student. The student finds it useful and safe to get their services. Word of mouth is the most common strategy used by agencies than only advertising on social media (Zeithaml et al., 2010).

“I travelled with a friend, and she had a friend who had travelled before, and that company helped them” (E5, lines 68,69) ... “I believed blindly in the information given by the agency and the experience of my sister in the UK” (E6, lines 51, 52).

Students have many enquiries related to the education system, institution ranking, job opportunities, lifestyle, and culture. Therefore, they expect that an agent answers any enquiry in order to feel confident when decide to use its service due to the big investment and risk in traveling far from home. Some people not only rely on the agency immediately, but also research and talk with other agencies in the same country or overseas to make sure that they are applying with a trustworthy company.

1.1. Agency negative issues

Despite the efforts made by agencies, students spread the word when they are dissatisfied with the service due to issues with visas or courses chosen. This suggests that paying attention to the detail is extremely important for the agent who assesses the student. The documents must be exactly as requested by the Home Office, or advise the student of the risk if the documents are not complete. Some students felt frustrated and said that:

“They did not give me the correct information about the bank statement and the money I should have in the bank” (E1, lines 46,47)... “the person who attended me was not qualified because I lost a visa” (E1, lines 141, 142)... “the agency has your money and leaves you alone” (E4, lines 106, 107).

Similarly, Agencies in the UK used to add value to their service with accompaniment as soon as the student arrives in the UK. For this reason, the student relies on the agent specially the first days that are difficult to any student until he gets used to the system in the UK, the culture, language, weather, and food. Admittedly, students realised that is more expensive paying accommodation through schools or agencies than find it by themselves.

“We had to pay very high prices for the tickets to arrive on time, then we realized that we could arrive eight days later or fifteen days later and we would have had better prices” (E4, lines 53-55) ... “because we decided to pay two months’ rent in the flat they offered us ... we later realized that with that amount of money we could easily survive for six or eight months” (E4, lines 57-59) ... “when I arrived they had promised me a work placement” (E1, line 49).

On the other hand, the agents know the needs of the students and offer them job opportunities and good facilities that have been offered by the universities. A number of issues are identified with regard to the responsibility acquired with such offers that can destroy the image of the agencies when they are not well informed of the conditions of these benefits.

2. Difficulties living in the UK

In response to this question, a range of responses were obtained from students, arguing that they feel embarrassed when mispronouncing words due to a lack of confidence in English. This is one of the barriers to communication when arriving in the UK, although they had previous knowledge of the language.

One thing is travelling for holidays, and another completely different thing is studying; the responsibility is higher. Students feel alone and unsupported despite the facilities provided to be able to talk with their families in Colombia. Some participants expressed concerns about their lack of knowledge of the UK and about the prior research they had done before travelling. Students commented:

“they told me where I was going to live” (E1, line 104) ... “I started to look at the map, Google Maps” (E1, lines 104, 105) ... “and tried to talk to the woman where I was going to live, even though I did not understand anything” (E1, lines 105, 106) ... “you are already on your own, you have no one to call, no one to support you” (E2, line 47)... “he was homesick and went back to Colombia after two weeks” (E2, lines 112, 113)... “The first week of not knowing where to go to eat,

not knowing how much things cost, not knowing how much to pay for this and that, I mean, having no idea of how life works” (E5, lines 96, 97) ... “The IELTS was the biggest difficulty”(E7, line 89).

A common response was that only 20 hours of work allowed to students makes it more difficult to find a job. It means that some companies avoid students because they cannot commit to work full time, and due to having to fit in with different university schedules each quarter. Companies usually only offer a temporary job because of the visa status.

The extract below shows students' disappointment related to job opportunities. Having had experience in well-known companies and a professional job position in Colombia, they arrive in a country that cannot offer them the same merely because of their lack of English. The jobs they were offered were not professional and were not easy to find. This means that students have to take any job available in order to survive in the UK.

“To get a job that may not necessarily be as good as the one you had in your country” (E13 lines 63, 64)... “ work restrictions” (E13 line 108) ... “people who are studying English are no longer permitted to work” (E8, line 213) ... “money becomes tight, and now because of the weakness of the Colombian currency, I had to look for a job, the pressure starts” (E3, lines 276, 277) ... “if you do not work, you do not eat, you do not live ... we have to work during the weekend because it was complicated studying at the university with the lectures spread throughout the day” (E4, lines 96, 99, 100).

Some participants expressed the feeling that returning to Colombia would be the best option after studying and living in the UK, to go back to a professional job in Colombia. Others considered that they would like to try to find a professional job here in England whilst studying, even with the knowledge that the remuneration that they could find would not be proportionate to their qualifications.

“It was a bit painful to be away from my loved ones, but easier with my simple conviction I was going to return” (E6, lines 58, 59) ... “you must send about a hundred CVs a week, of those 100, the companies probably call you to two interviews” (E9, lines 107,108) ... “being Colombian, not European, did not feel like an impediment to getting a job” (E9, lines111, 112).

Related to the university education system in the UK, it became clear that there were some difficulties where students did not feel they were getting enough support from lecturers, and they felt that they had to learn by themselves.

“In Colombia they put a lot of pressure on you, but they support you, the teacher is paying attention to you, they review the jobs very well” (E9, lines 154, 155) ... “here the studying is more independent, and you read on your own, you learn on your own ... and the teacher only offers you the class” (E9, lines 156, 157).

Students need to understand the UK education system before coming, it would help them to better prepare their classes and make the most of their time at university.

3. Students' English language level

This section of the interviews required respondents to give information about their feelings related to the English language studied in Colombia and the challenge of speaking it in an English-speaking environment.

The majority of students commented that they assumed that their English would be good enough to communicate adequately. They felt they could improve their skills quickly by listening to native English speakers, and with the pressure to speak with them all the time and studying. Immersing themselves in an English culture turned out to be very different; the students confirmed that the challenge was greater. The surrounding environment was not what had been expected, possibly because of their subconscious need to find other Spanish speakers.

Students tend to easily find native Spanish classmates or live in places with Spanish speakers. This comfort made this task of learning slower, but on the other hand enjoyable. Other students affirmed that they expected to learn English in six months immersed in an English culture, however they found it difficult to meet this goal and need more than a year.

“I did an English course in Colombia, but I came here, and I realised that I did not know anything” (E14, line 51,52) ... “the IELTS score and that was the most difficult for me” (E7, line 97) ... “here I was surprised by the different accents and I thought I needed to improve my accent and improving my grammar” (E12, lines 31, 32) ... “in 6 months I did not speak English” (E3, line 27, 28) ... “I decided to extend (student visa) for almost three and a half years” (E17, line 44).

A small number of those interviewed recognised that their English language was adequate for the standards required by the university. Private schools in Colombia offer English immersion and students with financial resources spend their holidays in North America where they get familiarised with the language. This suggests that these customers expect a higher standard of education when they decide to travel to the UK.

“I started looking at universities when I was in the middle of the academic English course year” (E9, line 37) ... “I already had good bases from a very young age, because I was always studying English” (E11, line 19, 20).

These results suggest that students with more desirable English can perform better at university. An interviewee commented that if his level of English had been better, or if the classes had been in Spanish, his results would be higher. It means that he would have further taken advantage of the course at the university from the point of view of participation and contribution in the classes.

4. Family resources and support

When the participants were asked about financial resources used to travel, the majority commented that family supported them in diverse ways.

“I could not justify the payments by my own” (E2, line 122, 123) “I simply lived in my parents’ house and that allowed me to have enough money to spend on my trip and my studies” (E13, lines 50, 51) ... “I used my mother’s bank statements” (E15, line 107) ... “I did not have the power to make a decision, it was my dad” (E18, lines 66, 67) ... “my Uncle said to me: Okay, they ask for ten thousand and I have 12 thousand pounds” (E3, lines 203, 204) ... “but my grandparents helped me with a part, but for the most part I paid for it” (E5, lines 138, 139)... “I never really used Icetex, I used the support of my parents” (E8, lines 64, 65).

According to the Colombian culture, students live with their parents and save money to study or buy a property afterwards. Students can hardly save by themselves the full amount of money needed to travel to the UK. For this reason, parents support this decision and provide their bank statements. There are cases where parents encourage their children to travel and make it possible through financial means, as well as looking for advice from agencies. Many consult agencies that speak Spanish due to their lack of English, and they also find it very useful when someone else has had experience overseas.

5. Friends influence

In response to this question, a range of unanimous responses were elicited regarding the influence of friends at the moment of making the decision to travel abroad.

Friends show emotion when they travel and share the experience of having learned new things, and being able to do it, solve problems, develop skills, make faster decisions. This encourages new students when they realise that others share the same dreams. Friends create new expectations by advising candidates to save money and time when they enjoy the trip, plus the rewarding benefits of studying.

“a friend who lived in London recommended me to go to London because I was going to get bored in other towns” (E1, lines 32, 33) ... “a friend here who helped me to find the accommodation and I paid 3 times less” (E13, lines 32, 33)... “my friend was a minor and I came to accompany her” (E15, line 30)... “it was through a friend of a friend, these guys already lived here”... I knew the nephews of a friend who were living here” (E16, line 19, 23) ... “this agency because of the recommendation of a friend in Colombia who had a friend” (E17 lines 69, 70) ... a cousin who already lived in UK” (E2, line 45) ... my sister had already studied there”(E6, line 49) ... “I kept asking friends from university who travelled for some months and got back to finish their degree in Colombia” (E8, lines 51, 52) ... “more than anything else, I had a friend here” (E9, lines 28, 29).

Although agencies have a significant role at the moment of applying for a course and a visa, the feedback of friends or people that already lived the experience in the country has a strong influence on their decision. Students look for information that includes accommodation, schools, universities, provisions, travel facilities and tips that make their life easier while they are in the UK.

6. Importance of studying abroad

Respondents were asked to suggest other reasons for travelling to the UK. It is necessary to improve the language and obtain a professional diploma from a recognised institution in the UK. Colombians also, look for a better lifestyle and they know that there are more facilities nowadays to travel and study overseas. They study English in most of the schools in Colombia and, in private schools they are immersed in the English language.

“I could not find a job because I did not speak English” (E1, line 18) ... “I would have a much higher value on my resume” (E11, line 10) ... “my career was modern languages” (E16, line 11) ... “level of English was not very good and in Bogota the few centres that I knew were very expensive” (E17, line 20) ... “grow professionally and obtain a better job with a higher academic degree than those basic undergraduate studies achieved in Colombia” (E2, lines 23-25) ... “I met

people from different countries of the world and their goals were beyond the English course ... I thought if they can why can't I" (E2, lines 52-53) ... "return to my country to give what I learned" (E6, line 57) ... "when I introduce myself in an interview and I say I was in London, people see you in a different way" (E6, lines 114, 115).

Colombian companies expect that their employees speak English, although it is only partially spoken in some jobs. Colombians at the moment of finding a job in their country are not confident with their English. Furthermore, they have found that studying a postgraduate or master's degree in Colombia costs as much as could cost overseas.

It is clear that students have expectations when they decide to travel. Once they have had the experience their ambitions increase and their reasons to live abroad are supported with new aspirations.

7. Countries visited before travelling to the UK

This question came up whilst talking with the students about their experience of different countries before arriving in the UK. It was evident that people who had travelled overseas before for holidays or to study performed better, due to their knowledge, as opposed to what was observed in students who were travelling for the first time. This observation is important because some customers require a different type of attention according to their needs.

"I had already been to England" ... Europe, the United States and Central America" (E2, lines 39,40) ... "to Costa Rica once" (E5, line 21) ... "Bolivia because my mum is Bolivian" (E1, line 12) ... "to Brazil, Ecuador, Argentina, UK, Egypt" (E6, line 13).

A minority of people commented that travelling abroad was for a different reason than to study; for example, they visited countries around South America, Europe, North America and even the United Kingdom just for holidays. However, they

found that visiting English-speaking countries for a brief period is different from living there and being immersed in the culture.

“I specialised in copywriting in Buenos Aires” (E6, line 17) ... “I was in Boston, I spent four months studying English” (E7, line 15).

Taken together, these comments would tend to suggest that people are able to travel abroad to improve their lifestyle. A few respondents said that this journey to the UK was for them the first time travelling abroad.

8. Financial support

The following opinions surfaced mainly regarding financial support from institutions or family members that helped the students to meet the requirements demanded by the Home Office to obtain the visa.

Commonly, in Colombia, students request a loan from Icetex, an institution that requires two co-debtors to borrow the money to study at high interest rates for a specified period. People take such loans only in extreme cases due to the high interest rate.

“my dad received the money in his account I could show that he had the money” ... “they charge you interest according to social class” (E1, line 71, 72, 85) ... “I ended up paying about 10 times the amount of money” (E10, lines 160, 161) “it was not highly recommended” (E11, line 64) ... “Icetex credits sometimes do not have a good reputation” (E15, line 119) ... “I realized I was paying more. I calculated the capital and complained to the company, then they sent me a letter that I did not understand” (E8, lines 77, 78).

There are other students who accepted the loan with the knowledge of its costs, but it is an opportunity and the only option to travel overseas. Three interviewees stated that:

"I went to Colfuturo and got a scholarship credit" (E10, line 44) ... "I won a scholarship with ICETEX, but I didn't take it because I received a better offer from another university" (E18, lines 76, 77) ... "I came with Icetex as well" (E9, line 52).

It means that students have the possibility of using a scholarship loan with Colfuturo or Icetex. Students from Colombia argued that sometimes they avoid this type of loan because it is subject to conditions established to return to Colombia and remain in the Country for 3 to 5 years. Additionally, a student explained that a university gave her a better choice of fees and opportunities to work.

On the other hand, this scholarship is useful for students without financial resources and with the need to finish their studies to return to Colombia to work. This institution facilitates the application process for the visa and provides the tuition fees.

9. Colombian students' priorities

A variety of perspectives were expressed by the participants related to their priorities before travelling to the UK. Although Students know the reputation of the education system in the UK, they usually research in depth about the activities, lifestyle and facilities when they arrive in the UK. It is for this reason that students look for any type of information that could be provided by different means, like internet, agencies and friends.

"Investigate more about England, about the area where I was going to live, places around, the types of jobs that I could do, the rights of the students, the hours of work, the obligations of the students once they have the visa" (E17, lines 106, 109).

The plans of the students change or improve relative to the circumstances during their stay in the country. The main objective of most students is to get a better job offer when they return to Colombia or find work experience in the UK. The

purpose of some people is to learn the language quickly and be surrounded by English people, avoiding the concentration of Latin-American people or Spanish speakers.

“I looked for a job to cover my expenses” (E14, line 53) ... “my goal was to get a good job” (E1, line 126) ... “to have a master's degree already in London, first you need to speak good English ... that supposedly gives you another level” (E1, lines 128, 129)... “to set up my business” (E15, line 264).

It is well known that when learning the language, students expect to get a job, but unfortunately, they must work in inferior positions than the professional jobs that they used to have in Colombia. These jobs are temporary until the student has the necessary basis to speak confidently in a second language.

“I spent weekends with my friends” (E16, line 52) ... “to take a bus where relatively close to the school” (E17, line 146) ... “to make the journey from home to school walking, a safe area” (E17, line 143).

Participants showed special attention to the need to have an income while studying and, in the same way, to have a social life that allows them to enjoy their stay in the UK.

10. Motivation to come to the UK

A common view amongst interviewees was that the United Kingdom is in Europe giving the opportunity to travel around Europe. They find the British accent more polite and easier to understand than American English. The fact of having travelled before to the UK gave them more confidence to make the decision of coming back to study apart from the option of having friends or family members that are willing to support them.

“travelling opened my eyes” (E1, lines 37, 38) ... “I lived in England when I was a child... I have many relatives here” (E10, line 13, 14, 15) ... “the possibility of travelling to many more countries” (E13, line 18) ... “in Colombia the masters are

very long” (E10, line 265)... “going to learn a lot more about marketing globally and in a different culture” (E11, line 13) ... “to take a break from work” (E15, line 15) ... “I wanted my Independence” (E16, line 46) ... “different cultures, the opportunities to go to museums, many free activities” (E17, lines 248, 249).

Studying an undergraduate, a master’s degree, or a PhD in Colombia takes more time than in the UK, and the tuition fees are similar. Other reasons given were that universities in the UK have better prestige than those in Australia or New Zealand.

“same price of being in Colombia ... 3 years to obtain a diploma instead in Colombia the university programme lasted 5 years” (E18, line 20, 31) ... “find a job in a company and stay longer” (E2, lines 68, 69) ... “my plan was always to go back to Colombia” (E3, line 96) ... “good offer that we had one year of English, an option to study a master and, two additional years to work” (E4, lines 26, 27)... “London is a very football oriented city” (E7, lines 36, 37) ... “the economy, a lifestyle, the monarchy, soccer, so many things that make a city so attractive” (E7, lines 234, 235).

The added value is the bonus of learning a second language and being immersed in an English-speaking culture. Some studies, such as business administration and International marketing, have the advantage of operating in Business globally. Additionally, these students can enjoy the cultural attractions of the country, but they need to find the time and financial resources to do it.

11. Visa process

Talking about this procedure, the participants agreed that the process is easy as long as the documents are ready and financial support is enough for the application. Sometimes the Home Office takes considerable time approving it and the customer is aware of it.

“because it depends a lot on certain economic conditions” (E13, line 43) ... “I did very well with the whole process with the right documents, money, visa issue and the papers” (E9, lines 71, 72).

However, respondents found it arduous to collect the documents. Authenticating the diplomas takes time and is expensive; taking the IELTS exam and obtaining the requisite score is stressful; some students admitted that their score was insufficient and postponed the visa application to take the exam again. Financial resources in some circumstances are difficult, but most of the parents and family members help them; in extreme cases, students apply for a loan, although the interest is high. Applicants are aware that any issue with the documents has the potential consequence of failure; it consumes time, loses money, and in extreme cases, restricts future visa applications.

Students are still keen on coming to the UK, knowing that they are allowed to apply for a visa only from Colombia. This measure increases the cost of travelling back to Colombia to do the process again, instead of applying from the UK if they want to study English.

12. Issues with the visa process

This question intended to elicit the knowledge about different issues that students found at the moment of applying for a visa.

Talking about this question few respondents admitted the failure of the agencies in giving them the right information related to documents, and the frustration felt when their visa was rejected.

Students agreed that from the university’s point of view, there are no issues relating to the application process, but found it stressful to gather the required documentation.

Despite some inconvenience with agencies, the Home Office or universities, documents and travelling from one city to another in Colombia, students are still

persistent in travelling once they have made the decision. It is an example of two participants who waited more than a year to obtain another type of visa or improve their language ability to take the IELTS exam.

“I applied for a Tier2 visa, a work permit visa, but I was denied ... and I came to study the master's degree three years later” (E10, lines 42 - 45).

New regulations in the UK affect the application system. Students not only from Colombia but also wider Latin America experience these difficulties compared to other English-speaking countries that offer them working hours, job opportunities and scholarships.

A student picked up the fact that even though they had working hours, some companies avoid students with these, most of the jobs offered are not professional due to the short-term visa and university schedules, so companies do not take the risk.

13. Online information for students

The overall impression, according to the respondents, is that the internet is a fundamental means of communication to attract students. Most teachers from well-known universities around the world can share knowledge and work overseas. This tool allows the student to search infrastructure, programs, location, chat with a staff member about procedures and communicate with teachers in order to engage the student (Zeithaml et al., 2010).

“I contacted someone from King's College, a professor called McMillan, and he works a lot with Latin American students ... and spoke with another professor at the UCL” (E10, lines 94, 95, 116).

Interestingly, most students searched on Google to confirm the information given by agencies and to know more about the institutions. Immersing themselves in that information, students found the location, restaurants, and places of interest to visit once they arrive in the UK.

“through Google” (E11, line 38) ... “the information was available online” (E12, line 20) ... “the agency sent me the information... I checked and confirmed all that information again online” (E16, lines 85, 86).

One participant noticed the fact that participation in fairs is an interesting possibility, because the representatives of universities can solve all the enquiries face-to-face relating to facilities, programmes, documentation, and costs. Also, it is an opportunity to offer scholarships, send brochures and engage students through their email and social media. This provides more confidence to the students to apply through them. One individual said that looking at information in the newspaper was helpful to find a place to study.

14. Professional program interest

This question was created in order to inquire about the main reasons why students have come to the UK and confirm how the university programs have been attractive for their professional goals.

The general impression of the students related to this question is the desire to return to London, considering that the majority of participants had studied English or had been in the country for holidays.

The interviewees argued the desire to return thanks to the knowledge of the country and the university facilities found by the agencies.

The students living in the UK explained that they visited the universities personally to make the right decision. Other students who travelled for the second time to the UK, argued that they searched on the internet the ranking of the university, the prices, and scholarships that HEIs offered.

“thing I did was to look for universities, what programs they offered, what subjects, what I needed, I did a lot of research” (E1, lines 108, 109) ... “I saw comments from the students and I started looking for how the facilities were... I watched videos” (E1, lines 119, 120).

It is seen that the Colombian students graduating in Colombia look for a specialisation or masters in the country, in the same way they emphasise the importance of mastering a second language.

“to learn a lot more about marketing globally and in a different culture that would not happen if I study here in Colombia” (E11, lines 13, 14)... “the United Kingdom was cheaper than Australia and because it was closer then I decided” (E11, lines 27, 28)... “BPP gave me the sponsor, the sponsorship with a business project... I applied for the visa called Graduate Entrepreneur” (E14, lines 86, 87, 97, 98).

For this reason, students decided to compare the study opportunities in different countries, which is a personal and professional goal full of interesting expectations. Students are highly motivated to be immersed in a different culture, language and traditions with the advantage of obtaining a degree that would offer them job opportunities in Colombia.

4.4.2. Data analysis of the recruitment process from the representatives' point of view

1. Importance of an agent from Colombia for the University

The main problem encountered was the language barrier. Students look for agencies to obtain the information and advice to plan. Colombian culture requires the family approval because in most of the cases parents are the main supporters emotionally and economically. Families need to make sure how the investment is going to be made, therefore the role of an agent is vital because they are the bridge between the university and the student.

“parents do not speak English ... most of the parents are who invest in the students, in this case, parents need to know what they are paying” (R2, lines 12-14) ... “we have knowledge of the culture as such, and that is super important” (R3, lines 28,29) ... “I’m always struggling because of the language barrier” (R1, line 12, 13).

The agents support the idea that the institutions of the United Kingdom cannot provide the same service while a second language is not spoken, and a better knowledge of the culture is recognised to understand the student's needs (Raimo et al., 2014).

“the university does not have enough tools to follow up with the students” (R3, lines 21, 22).

Experienced agencies from Colombia provide the expertise and cultural knowledge to advise the students according to their professional goals. Universities do not have knowledge about the educational system in Colombia, for this reason a representative has an important role and can advise the students about the differences.

“students and the parents do not know what the education system is” (R2, line 11) ... “we make sure that the student has the correct information ... and admitted in the course and at the level that corresponds” (R2, lines 14 -17).

Students require extra support regarding everyday life after the visa is obtained, or especially if the visa is rejected. Applying for a visa, having the documents required from the Home Office, is the first step, but the student needs more guidance.

“We offer direct contact ... the guarantee that the student will have the refund of their fees in case they decide not to apply or changed their mind, or if their visa application is rejected” (R2, lines 19 – 21) ... “the South Americans want someone who guide us, someone to tell us the experiences ... a change of life in every way” (R4, lines 34 – 36).

Agents are more reliable when they are settled in the same country and, students feel more confident in contacting them if their business is managed in the UK and has adequate market position.

“institutions give the money back but after one year, a year and a half while through agency we have special agreements” (R2, lines 22, 23) ... “sometimes the university does not have the department that can provide the support they need, which is how to answer the questions anytime during the process” (R3, lines 23 – 25).

The services of the Agencies prove a higher standard in comparison to the university's service, as most of these agents have faced the same issues when they came to the UK to study, which allows them to better understand the customer's needs.

“legal department of the university does help the students but not like the Latin Americans expect that they could help them” (R3, lines 25, 26) ... “there is nothing better than a sale with the experience of life telling the truth, the good things, the bad things, the disadvantages” (R3, lines 123, 124).

These agencies feel satisfied when students call them back to apply for another course, or meet friends or family members with the intention of traveling. Representatives are at a student's disposal to carry out any procedure the student might need, and also because their experiences would help future customers.

2. Issues that an agency faces in the recruitment process

The issues described are intended to raise the situation faced by agencies during the recruitment process. Students find the education system in Colombia different from the UK's educational system. Agents are making the clients aware of the type of education they would receive for the value paid. Applying for a place in the United Kingdom is an opportunity to study in one of the most competitive countries in the world in educational matters, with outstanding quality. The comments below show the challenges:

“the problem is expectation ... when they arrive here and are taught only three hours a day, the full time is 15 hours” (R2, lines 26 – 28) ... “has to pass exams

like the IELTS” (R3, line 35) ... “it takes a lot of time for certain types of visas” (R3, line 35).

A non-Spanish respondent that works recruiting Colombian students described his problems at the moment of contacting a client. Although he has basic conversational Spanish skills, he recognised the importance of speaking fluent Spanish because there are misunderstandings during the process. In order to have a successful enrolment the agent uses different strategies.

“I have a person in Bogota and she translates the information in Spanish” (R1, lines 32, 33) ... “I have 5 or 6 files from Colombia and only I received one deposit, but this person paid all the fees in one go ... we find it difficult to recruit students from Latin America without speaking Spanish” (R1, lines 24, 25, 38, 39).

Some representatives see the necessity of having agents that work for them in every country in Latin America where they see a potential market (Raimo et al., 2014).

3. Colombian market position in the UK

The candidates mentioned the ambitious goals Colombian students have and their strong determination when decided to travel despite the difficulties. These characteristics make the culture attractive and good target for HEIs in the UK.

“very ambitious and focused to study” (R1, line 42) ... “one of the nationalities of students who are good fighters, ... always try to improve themselves” ... Colombians try to get the best grades, (R2, lines 52, 54, 55).

Interestingly Colombians are one of the people in Latin America that travel to study beyond an English course in comparison to Brazil. There is a considerable market in Colombia but adequate information about available facilities is hard to find, especially financial facilities, scholarships opportunities and procedures.

“Colombian students want to come but have not knowledge of how to apply, this percentage of Colombian students that do come is very minimal” (R3, lines 82 – 84) ... “70% of the students I have recruited come from Colombia, 10% from Chile, Venezuela 3%, and is very difficult to recruit Caribbean. Ecuador, Peru and Mexico add 25% between the 3 of them and Argentina the rest” (R4, lines 56, 57) ... “we have Colombians, Ecuadorians, Peruvians who love the United Kingdom” (R2, lines 58, 59).

Colombian people are the most recruited South American students. This is due to agents being Colombian and their main marketing strategies are focused on their country of origin, although they have representatives in other countries.

4.5. Research question 2

The second research question includes 4 nodes from Colombian students’ point of view and 5 nodes from agents that support this question, as shown in Table 4.4.

How effective are these strategies in recruitment from a Colombian student’s perspective?

Colombian students’ data analysis	Agents’ data analysis
1. Accommodation in the UK	3. Concerns of students choosing the university
2. Requirements to apply for a place and a visa	4. How do the students find out about universities?
3. Universities’ online access	5. Students recommend or spread the word positively about their experiences
4. Voluntary job, professional job	6. What is more important when students choose a university
	7. Importance of recruiting Colombians to study in the UK

Table 4.4. Thematic coding analysis research question 2

4.5.1. Data analysis of the effectiveness of marketing strategies with Colombian students

1. Accommodation in the UK

Concerns were expressed about a place to live. There are some students' negative comments about the places when they stayed in the UK. It was about cost of living.

“it was difficult because of the high prices” (E12, line 34) ... “I had to find something cheaper to live, but obviously everything was a balance between more areas away from school, cheaper to live but more expensive because of the transport” (E17, lines 135 – 137) ... “the agency ... had an agreement with the college and the only option was the college’s accommodation” (E2, lines 173, 174) ... “we live like 7 people in a house (E3, line 40) ... “we arrived and paid for a week in the house of a lady, we did not speak English, we had nothing ... she was not very kind either, so that part was difficult ... the first week of not knowing where to eat, not knowing how much things cost” (E5, lines 93 -96).

While other students relied on the experience of their friends and family members who lived already in the UK and helped with this process. Accommodation and quality housing concern for many students and families. Most students desire to live in a family house with English people in order to improve their English skills. Although this option is expensive, the owner makes sure the room meets the student's needs.

“a friend here helped me to find the accommodation and I paid 3 times less” E13, line 32, 33) ... “my friend knew someone, who provided us accommodation” (E 15, lines 27, 28) ... “also I lived with my friend's nephews” (E16, line 25) ... “the first month of accommodation was paid through the agency in a family house” (E17, lines 120, 121) ... “I lived with the priest Carlos for 2 months” (E3, lines 34, 35).

There were some suggestions related to accommodation that could help other students and avoid disappointment. Students agreed to pay a month of rent and once the student arrives in the UK, use that time to find better places with affordable prices with the help of colleagues at school. There is always a possibility to pay another month in the same place where the person lives although it might not be the best choice.

The participants overall showed that accommodation is an issue. The students have solved the issue themselves and without knowledge of the universities or institutions. On the other hand, some students feel alone in this aspect when there are no friends to support them.

2. Requirements to apply for a place and a visa

The majority of those who responded to this item felt that obtaining the documentation for university and visa requirements was an arduous process. Agencies and the Internet helped them to find the program and university easily, but dealing with the paperwork took time. The IELTS exam takes time and, authenticating documents from studies in Colombia, saving up the amount of money in the bank for 3 months in addition to the visa cost, NHS, and other minor expenses necessary to present them to the Home Office, is very laborious and stressful for students. On the other hand, the student must think about travelling expenses, cost of living, food, transport, and the budget necessary to live and study.

“obtaining the required IELTS score was the most difficult” (E7, lines 96, 97) ... “my friends lent me money ... the hardest part” (E10, line 145) ... “complicated by the number of documents ... show that one was going to return to the country, that one had enough money to live in England” (E17, lines 150 -152) ... “the most stressful was the interview” (E17, line 154).

In summary, regarding the strategies from universities to recruit Colombian students, evidence shows that the enrolment is not very demanding as long as

the students have the fees and documents ready. The exhausting part is making sure that all is in order to obtain the visa.

3. Universities' online access

A common view amongst interviewees was that all universities have information online and the possibility to contact a member of the staff, yet some students are not confident in contacting the university due to the language barrier, thus they find it more comfortable to contact the agency to assist with their concerns. Nevertheless, students who had contacted the universities felt that the universities replied on time and used the internet to communicate with the student directly. Students stated that:

“they sent me some brochures with the information, all over the internet” (E3, lines 295, 296) ... “the person in charge of the marketing, was the same person in charge of the sales in Latin America. I had a meeting with the agent here in Colombia” (E2, lines 82, 83) ... “we looked at the university web site for information, but everything was done directly with the agency” (E4, lines 84, 85) ... “the agency here told me what I had to do... my interaction with the university was low” (E7, lines 62, 63).

Undoubtedly, students research and make comparisons on the internet about universities, programmes, infrastructure, extra activities and are more interested when the university uses social media and offers feedback from other students around the world because it shows the institution's prestige.

“I saw comments from the students and I started looking for how the facilities were ... I saw videos, but I did not see if it was good in the ranking ... was on Liverpool Street which is a good place, the photos ... I trusted in the trajectory it already had in other subjects” (E1, lines 119 – 123, 190, 191) ... “I went to the fair and they showed me the university” (E2, line 81).

Colombian students have different points of view about what they desire and what they can afford when researching online to apply for a place at the university.

Students who are living in the UK are more knowledgeable and confident about visiting the universities personally. The most prestigious universities in the UK are more expensive and demanding. Therefore, students feel disappointed when they research by themselves. Only the representatives who have experience in the UK education system, know the Colombian market and customer behaviour, can offer a programme according to the students' needs.

4. Voluntary job, professional job

A variety of perspectives were expressed about the type of work that students find in the UK once they arrive or finish their studies. Participants are aware that their student visa status makes it more difficult to find a professional job, even by studying a master's degree in the UK.

“it is very difficult to get a professional job if you are not English or European ... It is hard to find a job after obtaining a master's degree” (E1, lines 129 – 131) ... “it was more difficult and also competitive to get a job and because... of the visa” (E10, lines 204, 205).

Talking about this issue, some interviewees said they have found a job by themselves and work as professionals due to their experience in Colombia and good language skills. It helped them to feel more confident to perform in a company.

“I never had an internship or anything like that ... always paid work ... I worked while I was studying ... I'm still working with the same company but already from Colombia” (E11, lines 85, 86, 81, 82) ... “the manager ... offered me work. So, I thought at the beginning as a temporary experience to be very honest, I worked there for two years” (E3, lines 87,88) ... “after the master's degree, I started working in the professional part of my career” (E9, lines 94, 95) ... “I got a job in marketing and they paid me well ... they did not care about the hours I was doing, and I was flexible” ... (E10, lines 231, 232).

For a small number of participants, the opportunity to change the type of visa from Tier 4 student to Tier 2 working visa, was the reason for improving their work situation. Having the choice to work full time in companies. The entrepreneur visa gives the opportunity to work not only in the UK also allows the student to set up his own business with Colombia which benefit both countries.

“as soon as I received this residence permit, the things started to change ...I feel satisfied with the work I have and with the payment (E13, lines 119 – 121) ... “when I studied the master, I had the opportunity to work in a financial firm, but ... I decided to start my own business” (E18, lines 122 – 124).

In one case, the participant thought that the job in a company was not relevant enough to add to his resume due to the basic skills involved. Although it contributed to his financial situation while he studied. It proves the importance of connecting professional skills to the right position in a company. Hi stated that:

“I found an office job and on holidays I worked 40 hours... it was really a very junior job ... which did not represent anything in my resume” (E7, lines 130, 131).

Whilst a minority mentioned they worked as volunteers in “Colombia nos une” supported by the Colombian consulate, all agreed that it is the first voluntary job offered by word of mouth where a considerable number of Colombians work by groups to support Colombian people in the UK and encourage them to do more for themselves.

“I worked in the consulate for two years as a graphic designer ... an organization called Colombia Nos Une ... as a volunteer” (E9, lines 81 – 84) ... “I worked in a governmental project called Colombia Nos Une” (E13, line 88) ... “the consulate was worth more than Colombia’s work experience. I do not have anything from Colombia on my resume. I only have the works from here” (E9, lines 115 – 117).

These results suggest that due to the kind of job, students are encouraged to work as volunteers in the Consulate, while this job provides them with the work experience to improve their resume for future jobs in Colombia. On the other

hand, a concern expressed regarding a volunteer work , was the difficulty to cover their basic personal expenses and have enough time to perform academically in the studies.

“Volunteering requires that you have some savings, or work as a volunteer or work to live or study, but all three things were very difficult to achieve at the same time” (E4, lines 135 -137).

Other students suggest that working as volunteers in companies in the UK, is the way to get a job in a company because experience is highly valued amongst companies. Although it is uncertain as to whether students will get the job for reasons like student visa and license, study responsibilities or hours allowed to work.

“I joined the Council there was a big team of volunteers, part of Stratford” (E4 lines 137, 138) ... “my wife was a volunteer ... in the Manor Park library, she was teaching people how to operate the computer that makes it feel like one more in their field of work” (E4, lines 140, 141) ... “I volunteered while I was in college, with a foundation that helped the Latin American people” (E5, lines 135) ..., “I volunteered in some organizations ...because of the type of visa I have” (E12, line 47).

Taken together, these results suggest that there is an association between work experience, professional jobs, and voluntary jobs. Colombian students look for the experience that facilitates the way to find a job in the field of their studies, Participants showed the desire to learn and get prepared for better opportunities. There exists a bigger influence of the type of job as a way into their desired professional career than the salary that the student could receive. The issue is the short-term plan that covers the time allowed in the visa.

4.5.2. Data analysis of the effectiveness of HEIs marketing strategies from the agents' point of view

1. Concerns of students choosing the university

Interestingly, there were two main concerns according to the agents' point of view when they recruit students to different universities in the UK. Most students are anxious to obtain the right score for admission to the university. Taking the IELTS exam requires time, and early preparation related to the rules and type of questions, even if the students have the expected level of English, a part of that is whether the student fails, the process must be postponed, and the place at the university suspended according to the next starting course. The Home Office rules for non-Europeans who desire to study an English course, must provide an IELTS test B1 or 4.0 in each of the four skills: writing, reading, listening, and speaking (Yen and Kuzma, 2009).

“have the IELTS exam that we recommend to the students for the UK visa with 5.5 for each component” (R1, lines 48,49) ... “if the student gets 4 or 4.5 minimum, they really come with a very low level and obviously they come here to study English and it will be difficult during the first 3 and 4 months, because of the adaptation, the change of culture and everything” (R3, lines 42 – 44) ... “to start a career you need a more technical English” (R4, lines 85, 86).

Several factors play a role in finding the effects of Colombian education. Students are attracted by the language, country status and interestingly, the duration of an undergraduate degree. Students are encouraged to study for 3 years and move swiftly to a master's degree. According to the representatives, there is some evidence that financial status and the language barrier may affect the decision to travel overseas. It may also be associated with the maturity of the student, when it concerns the level of studies and age, which makes it more difficult to travel far away from their family and friends. Also, it can be difficult for students to find work that helps them to pay for university fees, basic expenses, and any desire to explore and enjoy the country in their free time or holidays. However, the cost of

education in Colombia may have contributed to the increase in recruiting students overseas, as students compare costs and the advantages of being in a multicultural country. Although it could be more expensive, the reward looks more promising.

“in Colombia every study takes 4 or 5 years, someone told me that there is a bachelor that takes 5 or 6 years, comparing that, we have 2- or 3-years bachelor” (R1, lines 57, 58) ... “in Colombia studying at the university is very expensive” (R1, line 60) ... “the main difficulty is money because obviously, you know that the hours of work are very few” (R4, line 97) ... “not all students think of studying abroad, many of them that think of travelling see that the UK is the best; ranking, costs are good” (R1, lines 60, 61).

The payment of the fees, having taken into account that currently, the British pound is almost four times more than the Colombian peso, is a distressing issue. Families must contribute and support the student emotionally and financially at this important moment in the student's life for them to become a successful professional. The student's dream is to have a degree from the best-ranked university, but unfortunately, the fees are higher than their budget. As a result of this, agents play a significant role in supporting these Colombians with the facilities of scholarships, discounts or strategies that other universities have for them to reach their goals.

“prices in UK are too high and the students must pay £10.000 or £20.000 in one go, charges for getting the visa are so high” (R1, lines 83, 84) ... “students from Latin America, and parents always want to save because of the cost of living is expensive. The majority applies for a scholarship” (R2, lines 45 – 47) ... “the pound currency is higher” (R2, lines 172, 173) ... “look for a university that gives them more discount or scholarship” (R2, line 174)... “they never analyse that if they have a good ranking they will obviously have a relatively high price ... about 15,000 to 20,000 pounds on year without workplace” (R3, lines 89 – 91)... “The students feel judged because of the situation of the countries and feel demotivated that doesn't happen with Australia, China or USA” (R1, lines 85, 86).

Another factor associated with students' concerns is insecurity with regard to selecting the most adequate programme. Agents find it more difficult because it requires more time, compromise, and responsibility, this type of student requires extra attention and help.

“Normally, a student who is going to study a degree at a university is very confused because he does not know what he wants to study exactly” (R2, lines 184, 185).

These results suggest that there is an association between the language barrier, financial support and decision making (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006; Maringe and Carter, 2007) and an indication of the influential role of the agents in this process. According to the representatives, these are key aspects observed in students which are difficult supported by an institution in the UK.

2. How do the students find out about universities?

The majority of the participants agreed that universities advertise their programs using internet social media, including Instagram, Facebook, and contact students via email, Skype or chat, answering their queries. Students who have been studying English intending to obtain a diploma can visit universities through open days or fairs by themselves, sometimes they are informed and encouraged by agents to help them make a better decision. The findings indicate that students obtain information but, at the end of their search, they defer to agents who not only know the market, but also give advice about all the enquires associated with their daily life and offer a free- of- charge service. It is important to bear in mind the bias in these responses to identify the needs of the students from a customer service point of view. Representatives suggest:

“run campaigns on Facebook with the advantage that it can be seen in Spanish” (R1, line 45) ... “I give them good information, they give me all the documents” (R1, line 54)... “Universities really do a lot of fairs, but it is not enough with the fairs, you must make calls, you have to explain very well the type of visa” (R3,

lines 86, 87) ... *“Facebook is used a lot and Google, directly on the website of them is all advertising and via email” (R4, line 170).*

When asked about the institution's agents' work with, participants were unanimous in the view that they have contact with many universities in order to give a vast range of possibilities to the students related to prices, location, and programs.

“we have contracts with more than 200 institutions, but we work hard with 50, because there are some that give us scholarships, discounts ... to give students the opportunity to reduce their fees” (R2, lines 36 – 39) ... “the group of universities for me covers too many programs that I can offer” (R3, line 98).

The institutions offer training to representatives in marketing strategies to recruit students from around the world. The HEIs need to work harder to excel in the competitive market, well-known to representatives.

3. Students recommend or spread the word positively about their experiences

These findings cannot be extrapolated to all students, but usually, satisfied clients bring more clients. The customer experience is taken into account when the student finishes his studies with satisfactory results, and his expectations from the beginning of the process were covered. Students tend to compare the education system between both countries, and they have high expectations due to the status of the British Education system. It is assumed that agents are interested in the feedback from students recruited. Study is the main reason to travel, but the student's life experience makes the agency more knowledgeable (Raimo et al., 2014).

“as far as the students have a pleasant experience ... they will recommend us” (R1, line 66) ... “Our company is more based on Word of mouth, we have a student now, the program ends, and they notify to their friends and they recommend us three” (R2, lines 203, 204) ... “the more honest and sincerer you

are with the student the more will be the degree of conviction and in the future, they will recommend you” (R3, lines 125, 126).

Taking these results together, it is suggested that customers need to be listened to. Some students hesitate because of their English skills, program, life style, jobs, cultural challenge, financial situation. Universities play a vital role related to educational services, but students do not feel confident in talking about other issues that concern them with a member of the university.

4. What is more important when students choose a university

The most important thing for students at the moment of choosing a university is to study a bachelor's or master's degree in a top-ranking university. However, the representatives' concerns are the high requirements of those universities and for several reasons, some students need more preparation or financial resources.

“there are students that definitely say: No, I want to start with English and then start the university” (R3, lines 51, 52) ... “I recruit more for bachelors” (R1, line 30) ... “we have a list of the top universities ... and we will explain realistically what the requirements of the top universities are” (R2, lines 164, 165) ... “We have to do an analysis, we have to show them the reality, what the system is ... according to their average grades and in which university the student could be accepted” (R2, lines 168 – 170).

The following is a brief description of Colombian culture and the family role in decision-making, especially for young people who are studying and still need their parents' support. Family members rely more on an agent who speaks the same language, although universities find students mature enough to make their own decisions (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006; Maringe and Carter, 2007). Nowadays, English language skills in Colombia have improved. Students speak at least basic English because it is a compulsory subject at school and is expected in order to pass the exam at the end of the university program to receive an undergraduate diploma.

“people from Colombia used to come to study English, that is not a problem anymore ... but their parents prefer Spanish ... parents pay the money, want to know the promotions” (R1, lines 143 – 147).

As important as a good university with high standards is, so is the location and facilities for finding a job. London is the most preferred place, although to improve English skills, people recommend studying outside London, where students do not find Spanish speakers as easily.

“the teaching quality and the prestige that is within the top 100 ranking, obviously the quality of teachers and facilities” (R4, lines 108, 109) ... “most of them say in London because they can get work, although transport is very expensive” (R2, line 80,81).

These results do not rule out the influence of other factors in the student recruitment process by universities. Students expect that teachers have work experience in the subject they are teaching, which encourages them to participate more and obtain an enriched and different class.

5. Importance of recruiting Colombians to study in the UK

Concerning this question, it was found that the commitment of Colombian students and their sense of responsibility when they decide to travel with a purpose. It is believed that because of their cultural roots, friends, and age, most students plan to come back to Colombia for better job opportunities.

“Colombian students are very ambitious and focused on studying not coming to work and stay” (R1, lines 42, 43) ... “they finish with a degree with honours, because they give 100%” (R2, lines 210, 211) ... “universities also evaluate us if the students were good” (R2, 213, 214) ... “in Colombia there are many agencies, but what I say is not very specialized in offering masters or MBA” (R3, lines 113, 114).

These results confirm that agencies' responsibility is with the students, family members, universities, and the home office. Recruiting students is a demanding task that requires knowledge of both cultures, the system of education, and the normativity of the country in order to transform Colombians' lives for the better, improve universities' status and their brand awareness.

4.6. Research question 3

The third research question includes 4 nodes from Colombian students' point of view and 5 nodes from agents supporting this question, as indicated in Table 4.5.

What are the operational guidelines for university student recruitment?

Colombian students' data analysis	Agents' data analysis
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customer service 2. Discrimination 3. Extracurricular activities 4. Infrastructure and facilities, location 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The agency was updated about the latest news from the institutions 2. Facilities and support services provided by institutions 3. Encouragement and support that motivate Colombians to study in the UK 4. Main competitors for the UK concerning recruitment practices 5. Universities contact agencies as a strategy to recruit more students.

Table 4.5. Thematic coding analysis research question 3.

4.6.1. Data analysis related to the operational guidelines for university student recruitment, from the customer's point of view

1. Customer service

The point of view from students assesses the effectiveness of the service provided in relation to the quality of education in a university. Students expect pedagogy of teaching and learning, creativity, innovation, and teachers with work experience in the subject or academic publications. Universities aim to improve the practice where the staff deliver a curriculum and learning experience that is according to the students' expectations and enhance the learning possibilities, growth and students' development. Some students' experiences stated that:

“a teacher who was bad and bored, the class became too boring, but for the rest I liked it, interesting” (E1, lines 194, 195) ... “the teacher made a presentation in slides and read them as he was an undergraduate student, although I did not know what he was talking about” (E2, 163, 165) ... “Practically one must be self-taught, for that I would not have paid, and I dedicate myself to study on my own” (E2, lines 168, 169) ... “then you must also do the most motivating classes, if it is a pure theory topic then let's do something practical” (E9, lines 159, 160) ... “I do not feel that the university here is better ... my statistics teacher studied physics and he had to confirm with me, he asked me in class, if I agreed with what he was saying” (E10, lines 189 – 191) ... “had a teacher who gave us almost 6 modules during the masters, so both the teacher and students lost interest in the modules” (E11, lines 205, 206).

Although there is no evidence that these experiences affected the results and graduation of the students, it is clear that they influenced enormously in the brand image of the university and did not meet the customer's needs.

Universities look to an adding value to their students' experience with strategies such as work experience, which is very attractive for students. This strategy seems to affect the programme and the academic work done if the student cannot

obtain the work placement as it was promised. The contract signed by students must be clear and according to the skills developed by the students to avoid disappointments and issues at the end of the program. The university is the students' sponsor, and hence, students expect constant communication to feel supported and aware of their weaknesses and strengths to obtain a job in a company.

“they do not do what they say, what they offer, they tell you that they offer you three interviews, but they only gave me one” (E9, lines 148, 149) ... “I had to discussed it quickly, they did not sit with you, they did not dedicate time to you.” (E9, lines 164, 165) ... “they did not send an email about the internship and the difficulties to give me an interview” (E8, lines 152, 153) ... “good information about interviews and CVs” (E2, line 284).

Respondents were asked to indicate whether strategies used by universities fulfilled their expectations from the moment of selecting the university and program. Students agreed that universities give the information required and the staff in general offer a good service, replying to them on time. Building a relationship with the student is a good start, students value it highly because they feel that it is important for the university and feel welcomed already.

“I contacted to a professor at King’s College, they are very kind, because you write them, and they send you all the information by mail ... like the brochures of the different academic programs” (E10, lines 91 – 93) ... “always had a lot of support from my professors and from the office staff ... the teachers were always very respectful” ((E12, line 69, 74) ... “it is important that a teacher appears on the internet ... If he has published books” (E3, lines 410, 411) ... “at the second university I already had enough English level to interact and be able to take part or talk” (E4, lines 187, 188) ... “They had a small department just to help the students with the visas” (E5, lines 171, 172) ... “when we complained they gave us solution” (E8, line 135).

The recruitment strategies start by contacting the student, but it does not finish when the student is enrolled. Some respondents did not engage with the institution and required more support, taking into account that their learning style and the culture in Colombia are different to the UK. Some Colombian students are aware that the educational system in the UK is different, and so when they decided to travel, they felt confident and proud of themselves. Other students were unsatisfied with the service because they expected more support.

“the services were very limited, maybe the students deserved a better service. Maybe the staff was a bit hostile because of the number of students, and the students did not speak English very well” (E13, lines 143– 145) ... “other people were not so kind because we did not speak good English, then they got impatient” (E6, lines 85, 86) ... “staff of the university were kind, they were not outstanding” (E7, line 163).

The UK Higher Institutions are classified in rankings, and the top universities are focused on their customer relationship and committed to putting the customer first, offering the best possible experience by treating the students with consideration in a professional and friendly manner. These top universities need students with a certain type of financial resources, knowledge, and language skills. Most Colombian students select a university according to the cost, place and feedback.

“they did not try to connect with the student, they responded to what one asked them, in a good way, there was not more kind of interaction or added value” (E11, lines 120– 122) ... “that one realizes that usually it is not that they want you. It is more the economic or profitable interest, once you pay” (E2, lines 151, 152) ... “the graduation ceremony was scheduled when some students had left the country already because their visa had expired” (E7, lines 187 - 189) ... “that not all universities are prestigious and not high quality of education here” (E12, lines 61,67) ... “the systems did not work, they sent me invoices until after I graduated, a year later” (E 15, lines 169, 170) ... “that master did not help me professionally, it did not open me any door,” (E13, lines 100, 101).

Engaging students could be an arduous work, usually students are unaware of the support services that universities have to manage students' time, anxiety and motivate them to build a relationship that enhances their time in the UK while they are studying, working and enjoying their social life. Sometimes, international students are reluctant for many reasons, cultural shock, language barrier, fear of not being understood or shame. Colombian culture is recognised for having friendly, participative, committed and hardworking people.

2. Discrimination

These results, therefore, need to be interpreted with caution. According to Colombian students, people who link their nationality with social difficulties show their disinformation and lack of knowledge about the culture. These stereotypes contribute to discrimination against students. It is important to highlight that students' values when cultured people recognise the contribution from other Colombians to the world and can address points of view with real arguments.

“they asked us if we were from Colombia and the same joke as always, about cocaine, drugs, and war” (E17, line 235) ... “the best coffee and flowers and I told him yes, we are the third flower exporters in the world... it was a fact-based conversation, intellectual, academic” (E3, lines 462 – 464) ... “There was a teacher in the English school who did not like Colombians. I do not know why he treated us like that, like ah Colombia, another Colombian” (E5, lines 188, 189).

Students desire to have the same opportunities as other nationalities, but each case must be considered in particular because there are established rules at the university and companies. There have been cases in which the student's visa hinders the search for opportunities, but on the other hand, there are students who, with significant effort, have begun their work experience and companies at some point sponsor them to continue working in the country, recognising their good performance.

“At certain moments you feel racism and preference for other Europeans or Americans” (E15, line 167) ... “the work placement is sold as something economic and not as a benefit for the student ...for a person who lives in England or who does not have visa issues it is easier than a student who comes from Colombia” (E7, lines 182 - 184).

Colombians feel frustrated when they are studying a master's degree, it is expected that the students fit in a country, have knowledge of the culture, learn new subjects at university and get ready to be in the labour market in almost two-years' time. These students experience high pressure to make the most of the time with their persistence and commitment.

3. Extracurricular activities

The results of these data infer that there is a professional and labour interest rather than the desire to take part in extracurricular activities. It is perhaps due to the amount of time students would spend in the country, particularly for a master's degree, which takes a year. English schools' students participate in social and cultural activities offered by the institutions, while universities have less participation in social, cultural and sports events.

“it was not like extra activities planned from the university” (E1, lines 181, 182) ... “some of my classmates played football... it was not my interest therefore I did not know” (E11, lines 103 – 105) ... “I knew that this service existed for the students, but I never participated” (E12, line 50) ... “my English school, they did not offer many extracurricular activities” (E13, line 127) ... “my school was not very good compared perhaps to a university such as Oxford or Cambridge where surely there will be much more extracurricular activities” (E13, lines 129, 130) ... “there is not the opportunity to participate in sports because there are not spaces for that” (E14, line 141) ... “school made trips to small cities, to Oxford by bus, but it was small, for one day, to Cambridge I did it 3 or 4 times” (E3, lines 347, 348) ... “I never had time to know about the activities” (E5, line 15)... “there was

a fair to know everything that the university offered and in that fair the representatives of the football team were there” (E7, line 150, 151).

Participants mentioned that time was limited to respond to educational demands and work; for this reason, they did not feel committed or interested in taking part in sports teams. Another interviewee affirmed that institutions located outside of London have more reception when promoting extra-curricular activities because they have the right spaces in the campus and students do not need to travel. Universities would need more information or constant promotion of these events.

4. Infrastructure, facilities and location

Related to the institutional and university framework, students are recruited in Colombia through online advertising or agencies. Students who are already in the UK can visit the institutions and make a more conscious decision. However, there are aspects such as the number of students per classroom, the resources of the library, cafeteria, among other things, where students can only appreciate them when they are already studying.

According to most of the interviewees, their perception of the infrastructure was small to the number of students enrolled, it made the services less efficient in the library, cafeteria, and common areas. Students found the online library most useful despite the complex registration system.

“the place to work, the library, also had good computers and well located too” (E1, lines 186, 187) ... “we spent a lot of time in the laboratory” (E10, line 169) ... “we did not have a place where one could study properly, because there were too many students” (E11, lines 108, 109) ... “the books or access to teaching materials was very obsolete and very poor” (E13, line 137, 138) ... “the virtual library was quite wide and then there were all the journals and all the collections and with this information we worked, I never had to go to another library” (E15, lines 150, 151) ... “system difficult and complex, I needed passwords, numbers, codes” (E2, line 265)... “The university was lacking in the infrastructure aspect, it

was a very small university ... always overcrowded in the public parts, the classrooms were small, the technological facilities were good, the Internet was regular, the location of the university was very good, and the library was inadequate because there were not enough books” (E7, lines 156, 159).

Students found the cafeteria or restaurant as a useful place to socialize. Some institutions use these spaces to carry out integration activities. Definitely the classrooms were the most criticized point due to the overcrowded spaces. On the other hand, students highlighted classrooms, library, technological facilities, cafeteria and the location were the most important to them.

“had a restaurant like area ... we watched movies, we met to talk, they sold very cheap food” (E17, lines 212, 213) ... “there were many students per classroom ... they were about 100 people” (E3, lines 361 – 363) ... “the facilities seemed much more suitable, much more beautiful, was a much more compact university ... organized ... more professional” (E4, lines 161-167) ... “excellent library... services, also the places for leisure and the gym, but I did not use it” (E12, lines 55, 56).

Campuses in London usually have a modest infrastructure in comparison to universities outside London. However, there are spaces that are not used properly because students have other priorities or probably are not informed of them.

4.6.2. Data analysis related to the operational guidelines for university student recruitment, from the representatives’ point of view

1. Agency updated about the latest news from the institutions

Respondents reported positive communication between the agencies and universities. Representatives are comfortable with the updates and marketing strategies that HEIs use and the information related to new laws, programs, costs, and scholarships.

“We have flyers going to the agencies if there is a scholarship available for anybody, it is my duty as a representative to inform the agencies to be aware and they can pass the information to the students” (R1, lines 94, 95) ... “universities send us newsletters ... they have representatives who are communicating, they are aware of what is happening in the market ... scholarships ... changes, the new systems” (R3, lines 168 – 170) ... “they send me emails, they call me, and they offer me the promotions that are for the year 2018” (R4, line 137).

Most universities personally meet the representatives and train them because they know that agencies can recruit potential clients due to their cultural and linguistic knowledge. Also, these institutions have refresher courses with certifications for representatives.

2. Facilities and support services provided by institutions

The facilities and support services provided by institutions cover the main part of the business aspects. Agents have extensive knowledge of the institutions and can give a better orientation to the students. Students would like to study in top-ranking universities, as representatives commented, but most of the students do not have the financial means. Agencies classify the universities into three groups, one is the most expensive, where most students want to go and have the best feedback related to infrastructure, extracurricular activities, and service. The second group is the one that most students can afford, but usually these universities have a campus in London, and the infrastructure is not as good as that outside London. In addition to this, students prefer to come to London because they can find a job easily.

Additionally, representatives suggest that their students apply to different universities according to their requirements. Once the universities send them the offer, students can make the most appropriate decision.

“Universities in London do not offer a campus like other universities offer on the outskirts like gymnasium, libraries, but it is more for the restricted space that they

have” (R2, lines 84 – 85) ... “I always tell the student to choose and apply to two or three options because there is no cost to apply” (R3, lines 159 – 160) ... “the cheaper one is obviously going to have a campus, but it will be a campus in a simple building, will have computers, they will not have many social sites, its campus is not in the centre. The middle institution or university has more facilities and a good ranking. If you tell the student how things are, they will not be surprised” (R3, lines 161 – 164) ... “institutions are within the standards of the British Council and any entity that is accredited ... it has adequate facilities to receive international students” (R4, lines 132, 133).

Agencies are very cautious when agreeing to work with universities or schools because the name of the company may be affected if the university does not meet the basic standards of education needed by the Home Office. In addition, it must be considered that students are investing time and money. Agencies seek that the student returns to Colombia with the best experience obtained in London and, in the same way, he would recommend them to more people who desire to come to the UK.

3. Encouragement and support that motivate Colombians to study in the UK

It is relative how some agencies compare the educational system of Colombia and the United Kingdom. Other representatives maintain that the quality of education depends on the university, student commitment and adaptability to change. There is a significant positive correlation that shows that Colombian students who wish to study abroad look for economic reasons and the advantage of travelling around Europe on holidays.

“British education is far superior compared to Colombian” (R1, lines 76 – 78) ... “students from any country come to Europe, come to London because they see the things are much safer than their own countries” (R1, lines 150, 151) ... “the family is proud of saying to his friends and members of the family that their son has a scholarship, even if it is a partial scholarship” (R2, lines 94 – 96) ... “when

you have a title here, it's valid in all parts of the world" (R3, lines 141, 142) ... "we have very good universities, with good rankings that are offering scholarships and sometimes they do not know it ... if they have a degree in UK, when they return to Colombia they will get better job opportunities" (R3, lines 174 - 177) ... "they are interested in having the experience of life, culture, they are interested in travelling, because it is close to Europe, and we no longer need a Schengen visa to go to Europe" (R3, lines 177 – 179).

It can be inferred from this that Colombians are hardworking, cheerful, and full of energy, ready to take advantage of every opportunity that life presents to them. Colombians tend to share their experiences with family and friends and help others to achieve it.

4. Main competitors for the UK in relation to recruitment practices

The most surprising aspect of the agents' data is that Colombians tend to study in places closer to their place of origin. This is the case of the United States, a country that has many universities with a strong marketing strategy to recruit students. However, other countries offer attractive courses and facilities for Colombians. This is the case in Canada, Australia, New Zealand, and the United Kingdom. These countries have a great demand for Latin American students for their different advantages, language, scholarships, job opportunities while they study and obtaining a job opportunity at the end of their degree. Some students travel with the conviction of staying in the country as long as they find a professional job opportunity better than one in Colombia.

"For Colombia traditionally, the USA is the big market, people go to Canada, Australia, and New Zealand" (R1, line 82) ... "The United States is one of the countries in which universities invest a lot in representation abroad. We also have European universities, but the majority of institutions that go to Latin America are British schools" (R2, lines 73, 74) ... "in Colombia they have several agencies, but focused more in other countries like Australia and Canada, but they never offer UK" (R3, lines 117, 118)... "There is an agency that is offering Dubai as a

new destination” (R3, lines 146, 147) ... “Australia, Canada and New Zealand are also offering a lot and especially because they are more beneficial for the student, allowing them to work” (R3, lines 152, 153).

In this stream of research, it is necessary to clarify that once the students have decided to study in a specific country, the immigration regulations are different for Colombians. This is the case in the United Kingdom, where students have certain rules to consider when choosing the type of course and institution.

5. Universities contact agencies as a strategy to recruit more students

Further analysis showed that representatives act on behalf of the Colombian market, introducing new customers to the UK institutions. Although they are paid by commission for any student, universities have the advantage of the considerable knowledge of the Colombian market that agencies have.

“Once the agency takes one or three refusals from a school they stop working with the school and start working with another one” (R1, lines 99, 100) ... “there is nothing better than a sale with the experience of life telling the truth, the good things, the bad things, the disadvantages” (R3, lines 123, 124) ... “simple processes in the application to the university” (R4, line 117).

It is believed that representatives’ wide expertise of the culture knows how to take advantage of the opportunities not only of the target market but also the marketing strategies of the educational market in the UK. On the other hand, Institutions recognise that contacting agents, is a strategy that avoids finding and training their own employees in a specific market and all the costs that it leads (Raimo et al., 2014).

4.7. Research question 4

The fourth research question includes 5 nodes from Colombian students' point of view and 6 nodes from agents that support this question, as Table 4.6 shows.

What recommendations can be made to universities in selecting the best marketing strategies to enhance recruitment and improve student retention in the UK?

Colombian students' data analysis	Agents' data analysis
1. Best experience lived	1. Best South American Markets for International educational institutions
2. Colombian embassy or consulate	2. UK help and services in Colombia
3. Financial improvement	3. Colombian embassy and consulate support
4. Expectations of students	4. Strategies to become a world-class university
5. New opportunities abroad	5. Standardised procedures for responding to e-mail enquiries in institutions
	6. Strategies to recruit students through agencies

Table 4.6. Thematic coding analysis research question 4

4.7.1. Data analysis related to marketing strategies from the customers' point of view

1. Best experience lived

This question relates to the satisfaction obtained by the students according to their educational and personal experiences. It is seen that the students achieved their dream of studying, having a degree and obtaining more than they expected.

“finishing a master's degree in London gives you a satisfaction that if you could do that, you can live in another country” (E1, lines 251 – 253) ... “any degree obtained in the United Kingdom, in Colombia and Spanish-speaking countries, is already a guarantee or a good endorsement to the CV” (E12, lines 82,83) ... “Colombians are considered as good students, committed, different from other students” (E3, line 200)... “the investment is usually more, but in the long term you recover the investment of both, time and money for all the opportunities that there are in London” (E18, lines 194, 195).

An interviewee who is working in Colombia advised investing a little more in prestigious universities to achieve better job opportunities in Colombia. As it has been seen in earlier analyses referring to the decision making of Colombians when choosing universities (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006), it is seen that unfortunately the majority of students do not have enough economic resources to apply to more prestigious universities, besides fulfilling the academic requirements that these universities demand.

“look for a more prestigious university like Cambridge, Oxford or some other universities that will weigh more on their resume and help them to create more opportunities” (E11, 137, 138).

On the other hand, a student who managed to set up her own company in the UK, encourages students to take advantage of the opportunity to be an entrepreneur with the support that universities offer.

“The majority (universities) have the opportunity to sponsor students who want to start a new business here ... the university sponsors you and you have 2 years of visa” (E18, lines 206 – 208).

Students proudly commented that with their experience in Colombia and studies here in UK, they managed to obtain a job in a British company where they feel valued for their professional skills.

“to get a sponsorship with a company. That was the personal achievement that was worth it” (E11, lines 174, 175) ... “British people for me in that sense have been wonderful and generous ... I told them that I had to return to Colombia, they helped me with the visa, it took 9 months and they paid the lawyer, they have always valued the work that I do” (E10, 297 – 299, 303, 304).

It can be deduced that the majority of students valued living immersed in a different culture. They commented that their experience was very enriching. They invite Colombians not only to study, but also to enjoy everything that a European country has to offer, to develop other skills, to mature more as a person, and to value their culture and traditions.

“every day getting up to take the transport, create relationships with people from other countries, not only at the university but also outside, it is something unique ... I recommend to everyone to live and study abroad because it makes you grow as a person” (E1, lines 256 - 259) ... “United Kingdom is a culture that encourages us to go forward to make the best effort and to be creative and highly competitive” (E12, lines 102, 103) ... “because in Colombia we develop other types of skills ... we have to be recursive, you have to work, you have to be persistent, you have to work under pressure ... you develop other skills ... the professional here is a little calmer” (E15, lines 227 – 230) ... “being outside of Colombia made me appreciate my origins ... the human warmth, the family, our spiritual life, It has no price” (E18, lines 234 – 236) ... “London is one of the best cities in the world because it gives you many opportunities ... having access to art, access to

education, to music, to ballet, to history, to classical music, to sporting events ... to eat food from all over the world” (E3, lines 495 – 501).

Colombian students are proud to have the reputation of being committed and good fighters when they intend to meet their proposed goals. Students had a difficult moment in the UK, especially when they arrived for the first time, as it is described before, but in the end, students have the reward of their effort, and their life has changed for the better wherever they are working around the world.

2. Colombian embassy or consulate

The purpose of this question was to find out how much the embassy and the Colombian consulate in the UK are supporting the students when they arrive in the United Kingdom. The consulate has created volunteer programs for Colombians living in the United Kingdom, but unfortunately, Colombians are not informed of these programs because the government does not promote these events. Most Colombians only go to the consulate when they need to change their passport or authenticate documents that require assistance from the Colombian government.

“I never went to the Consulate” (E12, line 44) ... “the help may be more in the sense of making documents, paperwork, but not support” (E13, Lines 84, 85) ... “they did not give much information, it was a bit disorganized, there were not many options or a lot of information about how they could help Colombians in London or the United Kingdom” (E17, lines 179 – 180) ... “The only way that information is given it is through networks” (E2, line 219) ... “register yourself at the Consulate because if something happens to you, at least they know who you are, where to send you. When you give your personal information... they send you emails, about conferences, meetings, events” (E3, lines 333 – 336) ... “I worked as a volunteer in the consulate, there is a program called Colombia Nos Une, it is an international program, it works in all countries, but the current president does not support it” (E8, lines 98 – 100).

The Colombian government through the consulate needs to create a program to help Colombian students feel more supported and confident when they arrive in the United Kingdom. This responsibility is on the Colombians and has not been received by the educational institutions or by the Colombian government.

3. Financial improvement

Most of the students interviewed are working in Colombia. It was very enriching to compare the economic results before and after travelling to the United Kingdom. The students show great satisfaction and pride in what they achieved. However, it is observed that the labour situation in Colombia has suffered difficulties, and the majority of students have obtained job offers, but they are not paid fairly.

“Now, the economic situation in Colombia does not allow paying 13 salaries to a person, for example, now the age is important if the person has good work experience. If the company is going to pay 13 minimum wages, which is like what the market offers then it gives priority to the person who has more work experience” (E11, lines 168 -170) ... “the great investment that any student makes after having studied in the United Kingdom will not be paid in a short time in Colombia, due to unemployment and the low salaries in our country ... although it is appreciated on the resume is not considered to receive a good remuneration exclusively for the fact of having studied abroad” (E12, lines 95 -97) ... “it would be fair for a person who has a second language and who has studied a master's degree overseas. I think it would be 10 minimum wages” (E7, lines 204 – 206).

According to the student's abilities and experience, a person studying abroad must earn an average of ten times the legal minimum wage. This figure is irrational when it is observed that companies have an established salary, and the employer must accept it if he needs to work. A common point of view is that work experience continues to set the standard at the moment of applying for a job. Obtaining a degree overseas is a great achievement and undoubtedly students

are proud of it, but unfortunately, the usual demand of Colombia's job market is obtaining a degree with international work experience in the specific field.

6. Expectations of students

At the end of the interview, students were asked to express their opinions about the university model they would like to find when studying in the UK. Students who travelled years ago recognised the facilities of paying for the entire course in English schools once they were in the United Kingdom. They liked this option, so the students would have the facility of coming to the United Kingdom and finishing paying their fees here. However, students are aware of this difficulty and suggest other alternatives that can help them achieve their dreams of studying. They suggest that the institutions could offer them more scholarships.

Students found several difficulties arriving in the UK. It is seen that the educational institutions are not aware of the life of the student. Colombians did not feel supported and admitted experienced difficulties. That is why it is suggested that the institutions could offer accommodation at comfortable prices, and mobility support in general once they are in the country. Others suggest more time to get to know the country before starting the course at university.

“help students with scholarships ... allow the students to travel and pay part of their studies or master while they are in the UK ... agencies have enough information about the types of scholarships that universities offer, ... also in other countries” (E1, lines 261 – 265) ... “in Colombia we look for agencies, it is very unlikely that a student searches on Internet, finds a university that costs £30,000, applies and comes” (E18, lines 289, 290) ... “inform the student in their own language, as well as investment costs, cost of living, culture, idiosyncrasy, transportation, leisure and entertainment” (E12, lines 108 – 111) ... “a master's degree where the student can come 4 or 6 months before ... so they can get used to the culture and language” (E10, lines 310, 311) ... “obtain a place at university here is very easy... but the money is difficult” (E10, lines 314 – 317) ... “At that time, we paid 30% as tuition and they sent us the letter and with the letter from

the school we applied, and they gave us the visa, when we arrived here we continued paying the course in instalments, then every month we paid the school” (E16, lines 131 – 133).

Regarding student recruitment, Colombians prefer to receive information in Spanish, regardless of their English language skills. For this reason, students prefer that educational institutions have staff from the country from which they are recruited. It makes students and families feel more confident to make the best decision, as this is due to a personal and economic risk when the student travels to an unknown country. The financial facilities must be extended to different areas of knowledge or professions, not just business. The majority of scholarships are offered in business areas due to the competitiveness, but Colombians would like to enjoy these offers in art, education, or law. Once in the university, students wish to receive a type of teaching where the teachers have experience in different companies and have the pedagogy to share that knowledge.

“one would expect teachers with different types of work experience, that would give you a different perspective” (E11, line 203, 204) ... “scholarships given by the universities are very limited” (E14, line 200) ... “not just focus on business but to offer different kind of courses ... universities could also offer scholarships in these areas” (E14, lines 207 – 209) ... “the university has to offer here it is educational quality, quality of the programs, opportunities to participate in research, to develop projects” (E15, lines 188 – 190).

It is well known that universities travel to countries to promote university programs to students in the main cities of the country. Unfortunately, it does not reach all the public that wishes to study abroad. For example, there are smaller cities in Colombia that have a potential student market.

“to attend the school fairs that are in Colombia ... but in intermediate cities where you will also find many students because the level of English in Colombia has grown a lot in small cities” (E17, lines 286 – 289)... “facilities with accommodation, something cheap through the university” (E7, line 220).

Thanks to technology and globalisation, students are well informed of what happens related to education due to the research they do to make the right decision and travel to an English-speaking country. Some students observed that universities did not take them into account after they got a degree. They perceive that their passage through the university was purely financial because the universities are not interested in investigating if the student was satisfied with the service provided, in addition, how useful the education received in the student's professional field has been.

“Universities in Australia have a student tracking system to know what happened with the students after their graduation, what they are doing, where they are, and how they have done” (E2, lines 313 – 314) ... “invite students that had travelled to the UK before to share their own experiences” (E8, lines 188, 189).

An interviewee adds that it is not strictly necessary to travel abroad to have professional success. In Colombia, you can get a satisfactory level of English, and it depends on the person who is studying a second language.

“If you have a good English language and have a degree from a Colombian university, you have a good professional guaranteed future, more than if you were going to study abroad and have no work experience” (E11, lines 152 – 154) ... “it is linked to the policies that come from the Home Office. The restriction is to have a minimum number of immigrants entering the country per year” (E11, lines 182 – 184) ... “they should have flexibility or economic benefits to avoid those students choosing very economic programs with very low quality” (E13, lines 199 – 201).

It depends on experience and work performance that allows to the professional to have a profitable future in the same country without the need to travel overseas. It must be considered that the needs of each person are different regardless of the challenges and processes they must take to achieve it.

4. New opportunities abroad

The objective of this question was to know the plans of the students once they finished their studies in the UK. The answers were surprising. The story of each Colombian has been different, some did not imagine the opportunities that awaited them. A Colombian woman is in China working after having lived few months in Germany, another is in Canada studying to be a pilot, others created a company here in London, others in Colombia, most of them returned to Colombia with a respectable job opportunity, but others are still looking for better opportunities.

“I do not know if I will go back to London because I am already a certain age” (E1, lines 217, 218) ... “I want to do a PhD for pleasure ... people suffer a lot in these doctorates” (E10, lines 286, 287) ... “a university that is recognized in Colombia, it is more valued now than going abroad” (E11, lines 151, 152) ... “starting my own business ... create that point of connection between Colombia and the United Kingdom” (E18, lines 249 – 251).

The students in the interview showed their desire to continue travelling and retake their studies in the UK, mainly because they already know the system. However, these students would like to find better opportunities to develop their skills rather than study at university.

“opportunities for development and participation in research and projects ... have the experience here” (E15, lines 199, 200) ... “It is difficult after living for some years overseas to get used to your country again and the salary would be less” (E8, lines 172, 173).

The majority of students agreed that the work experience was their immediate goal and then to continue with their studies if the job needed it. However, they say that with training courses it is enough to keep up to date on a job.

“I’m working in China ... I must work because I do not have much experience” (E1, lines 224 – 227) ... “I had to have experience on my resume” (E15, lines 68,

69) ... *“study courses relevant to my profession ... traveling around the world (E13, lines 176, 177) ... “Migration policies in Australia are friendlier ... more opportunities to work in companies and have work experience” (E2, lines 301 – 303) ... “visit the United States, but here in Europe it is a little more open, less discriminatory” (E5, lines 217, 218) ... “I find Australia, Mexico, Brazil interesting” (E6, lines 101, 102) “so I do not want to go elsewhere to start from scratch without having had a good experience here in London” (E9, lines 188,189).*

All these Colombian students with UK degrees desire to obtain job experience and have refreshing courses if necessary for their current jobs. Few of them would go to university again, but they are proud of their achievements and surely would support people who want to travel overseas.

4.7.2. Data analysis related to marketing strategies from the representatives' point of view

1. Best South American Markets for International educational institutions

In the interview with agency representatives, it was observed that the Colombian market is increasing due to the support of the government and its interest in enhancing English as a second language in Colombia to improve the economy of country. These representatives assured that the Brazilian market is a potential option, considering the size of the country and the population. The difficulty encountered by the agents was the language barrier, they would need a representative who speaks Portuguese and Spanish to recruit these students, Although Argentina is a country with better English language skills, very few students have been recruited by these agencies they added that have not seen many Argentinian people at universities in the UK.

“Brazil, I think is the best one” (R1, line 136) ... “there is a lot of potential in Peru and in Ecuador ... agencies there offer New Zealand Canada and Australia” (R3,

line 289, 293) ... *“Colombia 70% Chile with 10% Venezuela 3% ... Ecuador and Peru and Mexico add 25% between the 3 and Argentina” (R4, lines 56, 57).*

According to one interviewee, agencies in other countries are offering other international options to students who desire to study English and professional programs. This increases the competitiveness but also the demand in the UK. Peru and Ecuador are potential markets that need a good market strategy to recruit students to the UK.

2. The UK help and services in Colombia

The British Council is an important entity that informs students and agencies about educational opportunities in the UK. This entity offers English courses in Colombia, exams, and help in visa applications. Colombians use this means to stay informed, but most students look for the agencies that offer them more scholarships and educational institutions with discounts. In addition to this, representatives support the students in the application process in a more personalised way and help them solve their concerns related to more affordable housing and other issues.

“British council has six or seven agencies in Colombia to help students to have admissions” (R1, line 132) ... “in Colombia, in Latin America, in Ecuador, in Bolivia, due to the Brexit, they have been promoting the Chevening scholarships, they are doing events to promote education in the United Kingdom, to open new educational relationships of agreement with institutions in Colombia” (R2, lines 140 – 143) ... “they have agreements with the universities ... they rotate the universities according to what people want to study” (R3, lines 248, 249) ... “students contact us more than the British Council” (R4, lines 181, 182).

The British Council helps all institutions fairly by allowing them to recruit students, while agencies represent all institutions and look for the best scholarships and contact the institutions to obtain even better offers for students. At the end, the student decides which one to accept, regardless of the number of students each

one receives. Therefore, institutions should strive to create better market strategies for agents to showcase their institutions more favourably than competitors' institutions.

3. Colombian embassy and consulate support

Two agencies share the same opinion, they mention that the embassy of each country should have a database to support the agencies. Therefore, these agencies must prove to be responsible, serious, and experienced in their student recruitment in order to become known in the Colombian market. Students can rely on these agencies because they are recommended by the embassy.

“we have always done educational events with the Colombian embassy in London, Ecuadorian, Bolivian embassy ... it is the recognition that the embassies give us ... we have to show the professionalism that we have as a company to the universities because every year they review their contracts with us” (R2, lines 219, 223) ... “a project could be developed to seek the benefit to attract more people ... as an agency would like to support that kind of event ... they did not want to enter into conflict with other agencies, because we wanted to develop it with our logo” (R3, lines 194,197).

It is observed that there is a will to create projects that lead to the expansion of Colombian recruitment, but they have also presented difficulties because other agencies would feel excluded from this privilege. To summarise, the embassy and consulate must decide to create these types of facilities for Colombian students and encourage representatives to participate in this project.

4. Strategies to become a world-class university

This question refers to the strategies that universities use to obtain a better status in the educational market and thus achieve a brand image by attracting new clients through their experience in the UK. Some universities focus more on the selection process to find the most suitable students for the university's profile.

Other universities also improve their infrastructure and tools for students to develop their educational potential.

A representative indicated that there are universities that have a standard price according to the programs they offer. The difference is the calibre of students that they desire to receive in their institutions to keep their status within the educational market. This refers to the student's background, educational level, English level, and purpose of travelling to the United Kingdom.

“there is more emphasis on how the library facilities are and infrastructure” (R1, line 92) ... “I do reject the applications when I talk to the student and I feel that the student is not talking to me properly ... with 90 percent of universities in the UK, they give the offer letter without even talking to the student and that is why they have visa refused and have bad students and staff” (R1, lines 115 – 118).

Universities that seek a higher educational prestige usually show better performance in certain programs than in others, it is because in the evaluation of a certain program they obtained a higher accreditation. Usually, students misunderstand the information and believe that all programs are highly accredited. This generates disagreements and bad educational reputation because the quality of the program is not as expected.

“several institutions that do the audits regarding the subjects, the modules, interview the students and that is how they can determine the ranking” (R3, lines 213, 214) ... “help them with employment agencies to get a job recommended by the university” (R4, line 151, 152).

Universities must work to keep prestige within the top positions in the education system. That is why they must follow regulations and laws that guide them, inspect, and evaluate them. These inspections give more security and confidence to the students because they come to universities accredited by the ministry of education and know that they would receive quality of education for the investment made.

“Universities always have a ranking that is evaluated every year by different organizations and they also have to pass internal inspections ... they are controlled not only for academic performance but also for immigration compliance” (R2, lines 98 – 100)... “more events, much more promotion, and above all that a lot is happening here in terms of politics, in terms of Brexit” (R3, lines 134, 135).

Due to the situation in UK with reference to the Brexit, many students feel unsafe to travel. Regarding this, universities can offer educational talks, conferences fairs and inform students about the reality of Brexit, showing the pro and cons that could be obtained by studying in the UK during this period of political crisis in the country.

5. Standardised procedures for responding to e-mail enquiries in institutions.

Online marketing strategy is the most used tool by institutions to reach students from all over the world without traveling to each country. This online strategy makes the recruitment procedures and students retention faster and more efficient. To attract students through the website is necessary to show the clearest image of the institution and how it would be to study in it, keeping the experiences of students with honesty.

“The Internet is something like you scanned and you send it... I can do a Facebook or Google campaign targeting people in Bogota” (R1, lines 127 – 129) ... “inscriptions with the universities are in two ways, one via the UCAS for degree, the other is directly” (R2, line 119) ... “registration form is very easy because anyone can do it online, only that many students do not know what documents ... that's why the process fails” (R2, lines 120, 121) ... “Facebook has been left aside because now everything is Instagram, Twitter” (R3, line 239) ... “if the person finds a good service, he recommends you with ten, if you have a very bad service they complain with 50 and it damages your reputation” (R3, lines 245,

246) ... *“they do it directly with the agency... the university send them a welcome letter” (R4, lines 159, 160).*

This information must reach students within their economic resources, genuine, potential researchers and bright academics who wish to study abroad through scholarships. The website, apart from displaying student experiences, must be updated with extracurricular activities that students have performed. Universities should have a student tracking system that engages the students before and after the programme is finished, which would retain students through a network of alumni that would eventually increase every year. Students find it interesting to have teachers from different parts of the world, due to the learning experience being more valuable and increasing the prestige of the university.

6. Strategies to recruit students through agencies

The representatives interviewed insisted on the importance of understanding Latin American culture. It means not only offering them an academic program with economic facilities in an attractive institution, but also guiding them in other situations that need special attention such as saving money, opening bank accounts, finding housing and facilities when traveling on holidays. This service is highly valued by the student and family.

“They need someone who understands the students, like how to save money, how to obtain better options, how to do things easier once they come to London” (R1, lines 63, 64).

Recruitment agencies suggest that universities should implement other strategies that probably are not implemented because of the cost and time they generate. These representatives suggest that staff of universities should travel to countries, in this case to Colombia and promote their courses in cities and universities.

On the other hand, institutions must continue with the marketing strategies promoting fairs, conferences with staff that know the university perfectly and have good personal communication skills.

“visit the main cities in Colombia and run events in colleges or universities where the students can come and ask questions, has to be banners, information that attracts students to come to the desk” (R1, lines 71 – 73) ... “attend more Latin American educational fairs, which exist in Colombia, in Ecuador, in Brazil more often so that students can meet with the representatives directly” (R2, lines 68, 69) ... “reach the family, parents, friends through events” (R2, line 103) ... “marketing promotes a lot, institutions make many conferences through Facebook, or Skype, there are many conferences to attract students” (R3, lines 208 - 210) ... “I used WhatsApp as an enterprise... universities use Skype” (R4, line 174).

An interviewee who recruits students but is not part of an agency talked about their point of view related to the agencies. This person sees that the agencies also look for their economic benefit and encourage students to enrol in institutions that offer better benefits for the agency. On the other hand, it is not clear if agencies are in favour or not of different institutions, but it is clear that it is the student who decides between different institutions, which one suits their expectations.

“agencies are more like business, they don't care about the university, they care about where they get the most money from” (R1, lines 105, 106) ... “they have the opportunity of doing an internship, a volunteer project, a work directed with a company ... universities have to match the student's profile with the company and it is a long process” (R2, lines 110 – 113) ... “they have a very good service in order to recruit Latin American students” (R4, line 214).

Universities must also decide if the student meets the requirements of their student profile. There are institutions that add value to the programme giving the opportunity to work during or after studying and practice what has been learned. In conclusion the decision to have a place in the educational institution depends on different entities and people.

4.8. Summary

The interviews used in this qualitative study are acceptable to the participants because most of the interviewees expressed their point of view of what they have experienced. Usually students like to share their experiences with enthusiasm or complain, talk about their university time, achievements, and experiences, similarly this topic helps them to reflect and further value their achievements as Colombians abroad.

It was previously mentioned that interviews were time-consuming and involved considerable attention to detail by the interviewer. One of the difficulties in this type of research is to feel that the main aim is lost, or the approach of new and interesting topics could divert the purpose of the interview. In addition, the difficulty of collecting a large volume of valuable information, but at the same time difficult to analyse it. (Kvale, 1983; Smith, 1996). The interviewer must be diligent in dealing with the negative responses that are changing the direction of the analysis and focus the student on the topic (Cassel and Symon, 2004).

The interview process began with a question in which the interviewee felt confident and willing to respond easily. Some questions were descriptive in order to give the interviewee time to relax and think about the answers in a natural way. On several occasions the need to repeat part of the answers was seen to achieve more clarity to the information provided by the interviewee.

In general, it could be summarised that the data collection was rewarding, all the interviewees took part with pleasure and gave helpful feedback and also expressed their disagreements about the educational system and agencies, as it was seen during the analysis of the research. Five interviews were not conducted because people did not want to take part, despite inviting them several times and being informed about the purpose and advantages of the interview. The planning of the interviews was expected to last between thirty and forty minutes. Some of the interviewees took more time than the established one. The students shared their experiences and different situations during their stay in the United Kingdom.

Other interviews were shorter than planned; this was due to the brief time of the student in the United Kingdom and the type of studies; however, their contribution and participation were important.

The next chapter discusses the findings related to the divergent phases analysed in the data as thematic codes described in this chapter 4, Tables 4.3 to 4.6 from students' and representatives' perspectives that answer the four research questions. Also, the next chapter explains how this research contributes to knowledge in the field of higher education. It explains the impact of international education in Colombia, the determination of Colombians to study abroad and compete in the global labour market. It briefly describes the basic process of student selection by the UK HEIs

CHAPTER 5

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Introduction

The government reforms are focused on the satisfaction of national industries and local economies in order to increase the level of productivity. In the same way, in order to be valued in the labour market, education must have the prestige of offering robust academic programs that strengthen the students' abilities corresponding to the economic and employment priorities.

The responsibility of the universities is to contribute to the development of the student community by addressing their needs and challenges. The new generations seek to develop themselves as leaders through the universities' resources (Fischer et al, 2015). That is why these institutions must be able to face the global challenges with resources of knowledge, values, and competencies. On the other hand, HEIs must encourage high-quality research in order to generate innovation. In terms of educational marketing, this focuses on the economic advantages with an institutional commitment that improves the image and position of the institution (Marzo et al., 2005).

This chapter explains the findings analysed in the data in chapter 4 from students and representatives experiences, subsequently, some clear and innovative guidelines that seek to increase the retention of Colombian students are suggested (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Clarke and Shyavitz , 1992; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler et al., 2009; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). These guidelines are divided into two groups, the first group shows the current obstacles to the recruitment practices by the government. The second group explains the strategies that universities must take into account when recruiting Colombian students (Ozturgut, 2013). These guidelines are based on theoretical marketing models investigated in chapter two, and the contribution made by Colombians

who studied in the UK, and recruitment agencies with extensive knowledge of the Colombian market, analysed in chapter four.

5.2. Contribution to the knowledge

This research contributes to knowledge in the field of higher education in the United Kingdom based on the educational needs of the Colombian market. It proposes to apply strategic guidelines to retain Colombian students according to their culture, demonstrating solidity through the levels of customer satisfaction, the quality of teaching and experience in the market (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). The best option to propose innovative strategies with attractive and competitive proposals in the international market is through the analysis of the experience of Colombian students and representatives who are recruiting students from Colombia to universities in the UK (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Mercer, 2015).

An analysis was made of what Colombians think about the quality of education offered by the United Kingdom. This study was conducted from the moment the student decided to study in the UK, providing information about the process, difficulties and achievements until the time he completed his studies, as well as the application and usefulness of his studies in the current labour market. These results add to the debate on the advantages of studying in the UK and the weaknesses of universities from the point of view of Colombians' experiences.

This research supports the findings with concrete and substantial indicators of the Colombian student market and seeks to improve the quality of life of Colombian professionals. This research contributes to the growth of educational status and helps the economic development of the United Kingdom. Through the qualitative research method, the approach that has been carried out to date in the UK education sector, and the relationship with reference to the expectations of Colombians in a professional field is broadened (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006).

Undoubtedly the universities of the United Kingdom welcome international students, but there is a low demand of the Latin American people and specifically in the Colombian market. This means that the United Kingdom must approach the Colombian market and not the other way around, considering that most Colombian professionals aim to improve their English language and perform better in the professional field.

Evidently, the researcher did not find any research related to decision-making, trends in Colombian culture, and evaluation of educational quality service by the Colombian students who completed their studies in the United Kingdom. There are no statistics that show student mobility from Colombia to the United Kingdom in the field of student recruitment in higher education. The next part of this paper is a detailed explanation of how this research contributes to the knowledge regarding the HEIs in the UK to increase the recruitment of the Colombian student market (Sultan and Wong, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013).

5.3. Discussions of main findings question

The main question of this research was divided in to four sub questions that helped to investigate the HEIs behaviour from students and representatives' point of view, detailed in chapter four.

The main research question of the current study is:

What are the innovative marketing strategies that are employed to recruit Colombian students into the UK HE sector, and what guidelines can be developed from a university perspective to enhance the growth of such recruitment?

The motivation of this research was to analyse the phenomenon experienced by the students (Dey, 1993; Creswell, 2014; Maxwell, 2015), their perception of reality and the factors that motivate them to study in the United Kingdom (Babin and Griffin, 1998; Husserl, 1999; Kothari, 2004).

5.4. Impact of International HE in Colombia

The Colombian government expects to contribute to the knowledge of the Colombian market and boost its development. The Colombian government has shown interest in recovering and retaining Colombians who have studied and worked abroad (Moncada, 2007; British Council, 2016). In the same way, HEIs in the UK seek to maintain and increase the movement of international students in a globally competitive environment where the export of their students is valued internationally (Conlon, 2011; Smith, 2015).

According to the students, recruitment strategies (Ozturgut, 2013) work when the student feels safe to invest in the program and makes the decision to follow the visa application process. Subsequently, the evaluation of the service is measured through the experiences of the students from the moment they contact the institution until they are graduated and work.

Figure 5.1. University selection system (Source: own Figure)

Figure 5.1. captures the process that most universities use to enhance the performance of their brands through effective communication with the student and a strategic student selection system. To meet the educational profile of the university (Fisher et al, 2015), during the selection of students, the universities observe the candidate's cognitive abilities, desire for progress and motivation. According to the program, the university analyses the resume and university transcripts obtained by the students in their previous degrees, experience in the area and their aspiration to develop themselves professionally (Dennis,1998).

Knowledge in the area of education makes the difference with other institutions, it offers innovative and strategic programs created to motivate talented students to develop themselves professionally and personally. Universities generally seek to improve the education of future generations, establishing systems that encourage research and development with useful programs for 21st-century society (Sultan and Wong, 2012). Also, these types of universities provide experience through immersion of the students in the program, language and culture. Each university has its work plan and, according to its resources, they recruit qualified staff with working experience and pedagogical skills to prepare international students professionally, considering their needs (Zeithaml et al.,

2010; Fisher et al, 2015). Finally, universities provide certifications according to the training and degrees offered, keeping track of their success as professionals.

5.5. Guidelines from Government Entities

Figure 5.2. Guidelines from Government Entities

Figure 5.2. proposes five guidelines that can be developed by the UK Government as strategies to enhance the growth of Colombian students' recruitment.

Student immigration rule

The government should create a policy that independently calculates student immigration, thus it would prevent international students from being included in the net immigration data that the UK expects to reduce (Brokenshire, 2015; Crofts, 2017). The United Kingdom is reducing opportunities to study in the UK and expanding recruitment opportunities in competing countries that have strategic objectives of welcoming foreign students.

Policies of student recruitment

The government has the facility to create a target with interesting strategies that encourage students to decide to study in the UK.

Figure 5.3. International Recruitment targets (Adapted from Ilieva, 2018, p.7)

The Figure 5.3. indicates that Australia, Canada and New Zealand have a strategic plan for the next four or seven years, related to the targeting of international student recruitment (Ilieva, 2018), but there are no clear statistics that demonstrate this commitment by the United Kingdom and the United States.

Considering the United Kingdom's situation compared with competing countries, it is observed that student recruitment policies should be studied immediately to improve the statistics. This prevents students from making the decision to study in competing countries and from recommending them to future Colombians.

Facilities for English students

Students who wish to study English should have the right to work part time. The work helps them to practice the language while receiving an economic remuneration and prepares them to take the university IELTS exam (Hajela and Sumption, 2016). Many students suggested improvements in educational rates and payment facilities in instalments to access the university, instead of paying the full fees from Colombia before travelling to the UK.

Pre-sessional English courses

Studying English in the UK before a university program would help students to practice being immersed in the culture and make the most of their lectures at university. Whether a student learns English in another country, because of the working facilities, it is more likely that they apply to a higher education level in the country they already know and have been living in, instead of travelling to the UK to start higher education, seeking accommodation and engaging in a new culture.

Post-study work opportunities

United Kingdom has great benefits of recruitment for its reputation in the academic field, costs of university programs and undoubtedly, the benefit that international students bring to the United Kingdom in the education system (Fisher et al, 2015; All Party Parliamentary Group, 2018).

The UK strategy provides four months of post-study work, it seeks to encourage students to apply for a Tier 2 work visa with a specific salary and job. Unfortunately, students find it difficult to apply for a job in a company that sponsors them for 4 months before their Tier 4 visa expires. This action attempts to reduce the net immigration concerns in the UK, but has denied the opportunity to gain valuable work experience to students and the option to develop their own business (ICEF Monitor, 2019).

Figure 5.4. International Post study work opportunities (Adapted from Ilieva, 2018, p.7)

Figure 5.4. Ilieva (2018) shows the UK competitors and strategies used to attract international students with work opportunities (All Party Parliamentary Group, 2018; ICEF Monitor, 2019). Australia is highly attractive with the opportunity of studying for between two to four years, depending on the program taken. It is followed by Canada with three years. New Zealand and the USA offer one year, unfortunately, the UK post-study work has the lowest number, just four months. This means that strategies to recruit students are more difficult (Becker and Kolster, 2012).

The Russell group, which represents an elite group of twenty-four out of a hundred and thirty universities that operate in the UK, suggests that students who complete a master's degree have the right to work for a term of 12 months in the United Kingdom. According to the interviews conducted, this strategy is very attractive for students, considering that international work experience and degrees obtained in the UK result in better job opportunities in Colombia. This measure would notably improve the recruitment of Colombian students (Ozturgut, 2013), who would perceive that their contribution to the UK labour market is

welcomed and valued. This measure is expanding their work opportunities in Colombia or any other country as well (ICEF Monitor, 2019).

Overall, other relevant benefits to the UK, which are not measured due to insufficient evidence, are the additional taxes paid by international students, visits from their relatives, English exams, pre-sessional English courses, partnerships, international staff recruitment, and research opportunities. It is important to highlight that the UK education system is a very strong entity that brings educational and social benefits (Zeithaml et al., 2010; Migration Advisory Committee, 2018). It encourages higher education institutions to evaluate the education quality and seek new strategies to compete with universities worldwide in order to enhance the societal impact and multicultural educational status, recruiting more international students than in the past (Mercer, 2015).

5.6. Marketing guidelines from UK HE sectors

Figure 5.5. Marketing guidelines from the UK HE sectors

Figure 5.5. shows the analysis of data and information collected in the literature review. It is inferred that the educational institutions have some indicators of evaluation to improve their educational system; most universities evaluate themselves periodically. However, in the field of marketing, there are some criteria to improve the educational performance (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Helgesen and Nettet, 2007). The researcher found that strategies used by

educational institutions are the same in general terms. This information was analysed when collecting the data from the point of view of agencies.

Market Segmentation

The marketing strategy in HEIs is to communicate with a Colombian audience between 20 and 29 years old, mainly (see Figure 2.2, p.44, Colombian Population by targeting age 2017 to 2021). Nevertheless, professionals need to update their knowledge and enhance their experience to add value to the company where they perform (Kotler et al., 2009; PopulationPyramide.net, 2017). Thus, in higher education, it is considered that anyone can apply to university and age is not a limitation because in every industrial sector, professionals need constant learning (Eder et al., 2010).

Marketing Communication:

The communication between the university and the student must be according to digital marketing strategies (Beech, 2015). In the interviews, it was observed that Google was the most used tool by students to find educational information. Students edit and watch videos and make them viral through different social media such as YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Also, they communicate constantly through WhatsApp and Skype (Paliszkiewicz and Koohang, 2016). Although universities use live chat sessions and social media to communicate with students, it is necessary to design a website with effective navigation bars, invest in mobile presence to optimise the website for mobile devices and deliver short and clear information. Students require a polite and individual attention to build customer retention before the student arrives in the UK (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

Traditional marketing strategies still work in the educational field when the student is in the UK because they can attend fairs, receive flyers, brochures, educational magazines and newspapers. A key point to approach Colombian students is

travelling to the country and participating in educational fairs or joining agencies that have a presence in Colombia and promote university programs there. This strategy is expensive, but it creates awareness of the brand in the country. The promotion strategies are very varied and need special care when they are implemented, promising and giving the experience offered to each student.

In order to propose new strategies, it must be considered that, due to globalization, students are the ones who control social media and not universities. When the message of the institution is clearly expressed, students are responsible for expanding it and creating movement in social networks helping to strengthen the brand (Fisher et al, 2015).

Educational institutions in their online marketing campaigns motivate students to be immersed in the culture and on the university campus (Ozturgut, 2013; Beech, 2015; Mercer, 2015). For example, students are filmmakers; their feedback on viral videos is a useful strategy because they publish students' university life and lifestyle, which generates more prestige and confidence in new students. This information allows students to have a concept of the quality of education offered by the institution and the field of work where they could perform once they obtain their university degree (Fisher et al, 2015).

Alumni network

Students interviewed showed that after the registration and payment were made to the university, the communication was very little. The university did not show interest in the student's journey from Colombia to the UK and his well-being during his stay. Universities should respond to the students' queries effectively and efficiently from the admissions procedure, demonstrate special interest and support during their journey until they arrive in the UK. The fastest and most direct way of communicating is through social media, WhatsApp, or email (Paliszkievicz and Koohang, 2016). International students are people who require special support from the moment they leave their own country until they have completed their studies. Students need to receive more information about

how to mobilise in the UK and tips that help them make their stay more pleasant. In innovation strategies, the student's experience must be constant, useful and in a friendly interaction, where the student feels heard, valued and cared for (Sultan and Wong, 2012).

Colombian students as ambassadors of the UK education system can inspire other generations to develop themselves professionally by creating new connections through a network (Ozturgut, 2013). Students can create a bank of opportunities and global support in order to share educational and work experiences. In the interviews, the students showed interest in participating in volunteer projects; some of them were part of the group of volunteers at the Colombian consulate and libraries. They put their professional knowledge into practice and also gained experience for their resume. It means that Colombians are people committed to assisting others.

Student departments or alumni networks create a sense of belonging to the institution before, during and after their studies. Graduates of the universities who are committed to the institution can give information to new students by resolving their doubts about the university and encouraging them with their own experience. This is a strategy to retain students in education (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016), since not all students study beyond an undergraduate or master's degree.

Customer service

Figure 5.6. Customer service attributes (Source: own Figure)

The Figure 5.6. explains the organizational structure is focused on the student to optimize their experience (Sultan and Wong, 2012) and it is based on a chain that links the attributes of the service.

1. Qualities of the Service

Pre-experience starts when the students find all the university information searching online, word of mouth, and through agencies from Colombia, as characteristics of the evaluation of possibilities (Fisher et al, 2015). These physical attributes online must have attractive content with a clear message according to: location, costs, infrastructure and programs. Students agreed that the location of the university was appropriate to their needs and the structure of the program, and what they observed through the Internet fulfilled the proposed objective. This information is promoted through digital (Beech, 2015) or sometimes traditional marketing strategies.

Well-designed websites, the use of social media wisely, live chat sessions, online fairs, and webinars are options to contact students in Colombia (Paliszkiewicz and Koochang, 2016). Those who are living already in the UK, obtain information through different advertisements, radio ads, brochures, leaflets, fairs, university visits, open days and related articles in newspapers and magazines. Reliable and adequate online information found about the university has a massive effect on the perception of the institution.

2. Performance

Service experience is found through physical observation and how the student perceives the quality. For this reason, the student considers different factors when arriving in the UK and experiences a reliable, friendly, and attentive service (Fisher et al, 2015). The experience gained from the quality of service affects satisfaction and is required for the evaluation of the service received (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Danjuma, 2016). Students expect interactive, entertaining and quality lectures, teachers with experience in the labour market who can contrast their experience with the theories and models taught in the lecture. Also, having different teachers in each lecture would enrich the class.

3. Personal values

The post-experience is generated according to the performance and the student's perception of the service. The customer experience is based on cognitive and emotional aspects, and it is a credible source for those who listen to the feedback, thus helping the universities' communication and image (Sweeney, et al., 1992).

The most effective strategy to retain Colombians is through the experiences told by satisfied students who graduated from that university (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016). Due to the kind of service that the university offers, a small percentage of Colombian students would pursue another programme in the same university or even in the UK. Students are more interested in having work experience after

their studies; as a result, their positive experience is a way of recruiting and retaining new students (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015).

The marketing relationship (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006) regarding recruitment and admissions must anticipate the needs of the student rather than meet their demands. Recruiters who have this clear goal can reduce the anxiety of students and their families.

Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction results from exceeding the expectations of the service obtained (Babin and Griffin 1998; Binsardi and Ekwulugo 2003). Normally, students present complaints at some point concerning academic programs, support services, or professional or academic advice. The student's experiences are interconnected, creating the student's university experience. It depends on the universities how they manage this situation, creating trust and solving misunderstandings promptly and adequately.

Students need more confidence in their English skills because they feel incompetent to participate or discuss a topic in class, which hinders their learning. In this situation, home students tend to participate more in discussions and can have a wrong perception of international students. HEIs can be inclusive when they can understand the culture and needs of international students, and also create strategies that encourage the students to strengthen their weaknesses in order to be more participative, critical thinkers and consequently improve their experience and take advantage of their studies in the UK.

Work experience is one of the most important objectives for students apart from having an education (Hajela and Sumption, 2016). It is seen that some universities offer a work placement as a recruitment strategy; this offer must satisfy the students' expectations and be clear enough for the students to avoid disappointment. Students had many experiences at university in different fields, but it was observed that, with only one unsatisfactory experience, the students

can end the reputation of an institution if it is not properly and promptly handled. The universities must identify the most important aspects chosen by the students at the time of the recruitment process and which of these areas have the greatest influence on student satisfaction (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015). It is evident that students will focus on these aspects when evaluating the institution.

The positive evaluation of student satisfaction attracts and increases the recruitment of other Colombian students (Oliver, 1999; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Wong and Sohal, 2003). Highly satisfied graduates become a key tool in public relations for the recruitment of future Colombians.

Marketing Relationship

An effective communication (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006) allows the offer of experiences to the students to be an uncomplicated process in the selection of the university. The advantage of the Colombian students' market is that they have already decided to study and know their needs, but want to know whether the institution is adequate and meets their professional and academic goals. Recruiters should be trained facilitators able to create a relationship with the students and their family, and allow them to feel that, as individuals, they fit into the university without any kind of pressure. According to the students' points of view, the mistake that some institutions have made is to sell a program to the student instead of an experience.

Recruiters have an influential role in the institution, therefore, they must have some knowledge of the Colombian culture to understand their needs. Recruiters who have lived a similar experience or have been involved in the institution with students of that culture understand their customers better and help them to meet their goals enthusiastically (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015). In addition, representatives committed to their role, who are self-empowered and enthusiastic, are able to enrich others with their experiences and create new recruitment strategies through the marketing relationship.

The added value that Colombian students receive from agencies is the constant support and friendly service. The representatives belong to the same culture and can make a more detailed follow-up of the student's trip, taking care of all their needs and responding to their anxieties. During this process, a closer relationship with the customer is built. This is the way the student is retained and will surely recommend the agency for future students (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Kotler et al., 2009; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

To provide better customer service (Babin and Griffin 1998; Binsardi and Ekwulugo 2003), it is expected that only one person interacts with the student and is responsible for the process of registration, visa application and welcoming to the country. Identifying the student by name and value his background allow the student to feel important and unique as a customer (Russell, 2005; Ariani, 2015).

In the literature review, it was found that nowadays, educational institutions are interested in creating marketing strategies that enhance their customer recruitment. HEIs still need support and experience to create brand awareness and position themselves in the educational market. The prospect is contacting marketing agencies who specialise in student recruitment campaigns that guide them in the field, while the institution grows and manages its marketing strategies (Higher Education and Research Bill, 2017).

Colombian culture is family orientated, parents and friends play a very important role in the decision making of students (Gronroos, 1994; Cubillo et al., 2006), for this reason, the family must know that the student will be comfortable in their place of residence. Assuming that universities provide the accommodation to students, institutions can encourage students to decorate and share photos of the rooms through social media.

5.6.1. Marketing Mix for HEIs

The analysis and guidelines proposed in this research related to the Marketing Mix model are based on Table 2.3 in the literature review. It clearly shows an innovative tool for HEIs to accomplish their goals and satisfy the customer needs in each one of its 8Ps. The marketing plan in universities must be based on the knowledge and evaluation of the external markets, for this reason each university must implement the PESTEL model according to the benchmark market, it includes the national market, Colombian market and potential competitors (Gronroos, 1990; Cubillo et al., 2006; Raimo et al., 2014). Also, institutions require knowledge about the target segment of the population according to the university programmes and to develop significant and measurable strategies and objectives to recruit students effectively (Nicolescu, 2009; Becker and Kolster, 2012; Mercer, 2015). In Colombia, students visit the British Council, which supports most UK universities, and have a broad knowledge of living abroad, procedures, and student support. Although the British Council is a benchmark where considerable information is found, students find their services expensive and feel more confident contacting an agency.

Figure 5.7 Marketing Mix 8Ps to the Colombian market

Followed by the marketing plan, the university must create a portfolio that meets the needs of the Colombian market and promotes new opportunities at all levels for these students. The Figure 5.7. represents the university's commitment to Colombian students' subject to the evaluation of the marketing mix model (Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Nicolescu, 2009).

Product/service: based on the portfolio of programs that meet the needs of Colombian students and the adoption of new programs that would be useful for the development of Colombian students abroad. Interesting lectures and motivation to research (Russell, 2005; Ariani, 2015).

Price: In the investigation of the Colombian market, competent markets must be considered in order to offer better scholarships and payment advice (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Mercer, 2015). A strategy valued by Colombians is the program's payment fees while they are studying, instead of paying the total tuition fee before starting the program.

Promotion: Undoubtedly, the fastest and most effective way to recruit students is through technology using social media appropriately (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Beech, 2015; Mercer, 2015). The website must have a design that is easy to understand, with a Spanish language option, live chat sessions and with information created especially for the Latin American market, students and family members. This strategy is not expensive, but it needs knowledge of the Colombian market, special attention to detail and constant online presence to respond to the students' inquiries immediately. Students tend to apply to all the options suitable for them online, to choose the best option and service provided from those applications (Russell, 2005; Ariani, 2015). Similarly, Colombian students in Colombia and the UK enjoy attending student fairs, collecting information through magazines, brochures, newspapers, attending meetings by financial bodies and educational support. This means that traditional marketing still has a strong presence in this market.

Place: Colombian students prefer cities such as London as a cultural attraction and for international prestige. However, many students are open to different offers that suit their needs in the UK. Accessible location and transport facilities from the accommodation to the university are important points of reference for the student.

People: The interaction of the university staff with the student is a key point in the relationship (Zeithaml et al., 2010). Previously, students evaluated the performance of the faculty; now, every person who works in the university is important in the evaluation of the university. It is normal for students to have problems at some point, but solving these disagreements immediately will make the student feel heard and valued. Colombian students who are recruited contribute significantly to the recruitment of future students (Becker and Kolster, 2012; Ozturgut, 2013; Mercer, 2015). Their Feedback will be taken into account by new students when deciding to study at the university. Colombians would value being able to contact alumni or student ambassadors to be sure of their decision. From the point of view of the representatives interviewed, Colombians

are committed and genuine students who seek to improve their professional performance and improve their lifestyle, always finish their studies satisfactorily and look for recognition.

Process: An advantage when recruiting Colombian students is that they have already made the decision to study, as a necessity imposed by the Colombian labour market (Ozturgut, 2013). Studying abroad has become a habit; previously, it was a privilege for a social elite with financial resources. The students interviewed found that funds are an important factor that makes the decision slower, therefore, the Colombian government has created financial organisations that can support Colombians. The process of meeting all the requirements, especially taking the IELTS exam, requires time. This English test is the most stressful part for the student. The students interviewed admitted that applying for the student visa is an easy process, but it requires full attention to detail. Therefore, students look for the support of a university representative or an agency. According to Figure 2.3 in Chapter 2 of this research, it is observed that most Colombian students tend to look for information and make decisions during the first months of the year more than the rest of the months.

Physical evidence: Colombians get the first impression of the university online; many universities have a virtual tour and offer extracurricular activities that show the institution's facilities (Russell, 2005; Ariani, 2015). The virtual tour shows the reality of the university and helps the student not to feel disappointed upon arriving at the institution. Some interviewees felt dissatisfied with the institutions because the classrooms and meeting places, such as cafeterias and libraries were too small for the proportion of students enrolled. Students are also interested in participating in conferences, seminars, presentations and meetings that enhance their learning experience (Eder et al., 2010). Also, universities could offer agreements with recreational institutions such as gyms, centres of interest, sports and social groups; they will help the student to interact with other people and feel immersed in the culture.

Participation: It is observed that one-to-one communication (Ivy, 2008; Tuten and Solomon, 2015) helps to build a relationship with the student, calling the student by his name, knowing his academic history and taking it into account, being part of the institution is highly valued. The Spanish speakers' representatives have a significant role because students require more support in their visa application due to the UK regulations, also can give clear information to their families due to their family orientated culture, additionally, the student needs personal advice about tips to move to the UK, job opportunities, lifestyle, culture, transport, home and daily issues. Feedback and experiences lived by other students from the same country are important in this aspect.

Most Colombians who travel to study are professionals and are attentive to sharing their knowledge. Similarly, students interviewed accepted having participated in work experience programs. Creating an international student department, or alumni network, recruiting students (Ozturgut, 2013) from the moment that they arrive at the institution would enhance their student experience, since they will be immersed in the university environment with the opportunity of advising future students as student ambassadors (Fisher et al, 2015). Connections with companies such as charities or internships will make the student feel highly committed and satisfied with the institution. In addition, it is well known that the Colombian labour market requires this work experience for their resume. More personal communication with Colombian students can be done through the university's app, mobile websites, a personalised website to talk directly with professors, parent chats in the admission process, and virtual university fairs (Beech, 2015).

In the marketing mix (Binsardi and Ekwulugo, 2003; Nicolescu, 2009), all areas are linked together in order to enhance the recruitment of Colombian students and offer the best professional and personal experience in the UK (Ozturgut, 2013). The difference between the strategic plan in other markets and the educational market is the concept used and its practices to achieve it. In Educational institutions, the concept of "offering a professional and personal

experience" has a positive attitude instead of selling a program. Offering an experience has a significant connotation of excitement, improvement of skills and a better lifestyle for the student; it benefits the institution's status and sustains the prestige of the UK.

The investigation of the Colombian culture and market must be considered in the strategic planning to meet their needs. The application of this research into the educational system will help to evaluate the processes, ensure improvement and prioritise solutions (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2001; Helgesen and Nettet, 2007). Investigating a country's performance will develop strategies for the Latin American market easily and recruit a broader market in other countries that retain similar traditions (Kotler and Clarke, 1987; Gronroos, 1990; Danjuma, 2016; Kotler and Armstrong, 2016).

5.7. Universities Operational Framework

The operational framework of the universities was analysed based on the interviews with the representatives of the agencies that work with universities. It was observed that the majority of universities in the UK clearly have a position in the market (Mazzarol, 1998; Marzo et al., 2005) and face a heavy competition in the UK and internationally. The mission and vision are similar between them, which hardly differentiates them.

Due to government regulations and changes in legislation, global competition and the needs of international students, universities are looking to create strategies that optimise resources and differentiate themselves in the market by offering a valuable proposition to genuine and committed students. These decisions can only be made if an effective plan is created with alternative strategies that vary according to the customer's needs, competence, and technology.

Universities are free to create their identity based on academic programs, support for research, scholarships, services and facilities for students (Russell, 2005; Ariani, 2015). This identity is addressed to a specific profile of students with

programs that vary according to the needs of the student, technology and institutional resources. Universities look for the enhancement of programs that lead to international recognition in research, professional and personal development, and scholarships that allow them to distinguish themselves from other universities in the education market.

The researcher observed that in the success of a university program, the teacher must have the ability to apply current work experience to the lectures to counteract this information. The students interviewed added that pedagogy is important in the educational profession, but work experience in the international market is an added value. Thanks to the autonomy that universities have to design their programs, policies and procedures, universities can modify existing techniques to meet the learning needs (Dennis, 1998; Zeithaml et al., 2010).

Another added value is the entrepreneurial development, creating alliances with the industrial sector where students can gain work experience and companies benefit from creative students willing to contribute their knowledge in the area. Also, the opportunity to set up a new business, looking for funding opportunities and institutional support. Creating an international reputation through a high level of education that will not only guarantee excellence but also retain competent teachers, potential students and funds for research and business associations (Gronroos, 1990; Clarke and Shyavitz, 1992; Kotler et al., 2009).

Universities can achieve a solid future direction that will lead them to obtain international distinction and reputation through the participatory action of the educational community, teachers, general staff, students and interested parties.

5.8. Research Limitations and Challenges

This study is based on Colombian people and customer satisfaction (Joseph et al., 2005) to review the strategies used by HE institutions. No investigations have been found related to HE institutions and strategies applied to recruit students and specifically from Colombia. Associated topics from other countries have been

founded. It means that this thesis is already contributing to the knowledge and encouraging people to research more about the Colombian educational market in the UK.

Interviews were conducted online since most of the students have returned to Colombia. Also, to obtain more relevant information the interviews were in Spanish and translated in to English. These interviewees were more relaxed and comfortable speaking in their mother tongue, although they have an adequate English language to answer the questions.

Another key point to mention is that most universities have their strategies to recruit students, and difficulty would share that information to conduct this research. For this reason, the interviews were applied to the agencies that work with highly trusted universities in the UK and the Colombian student market. The second group of interviews was applied to Colombian students who were enrolled in different institutions in the UK.

5.9. Further Research

Studies in marketing tend to be characterised by empirical research based on certain industries. It has been an important contribution to other service firms. The marketing literature requires to focus more in the issues that different services are facing to give a better value.

Word of mouth is essential in educational marketing services; more studies about different strategies that help this intangible business can be appropriate to offer more accurate advice (Russell, 2005; Zeithaml et al., 2010; Ariani, 2015).

Some recommendations have been made to ensure that the United Kingdom has its status in Colombia as one of the best countries in international recruitment practices (Ozturgut, 2013). An immediate consensus on the part of the government and a strategy that supports it are needed, considering the challenging impact of Brexit.

Although it is known that Colombia is not the strongest source of student recruitment for the UK, this study could cover a larger scale of Colombians studying in other cities in the UK, this exercise can attract students to specific places and universities, in addition to feedback on the performance of each university and its recruitment practices.

This research can be done internationally by interviewing Colombians who study in countries that compete with UK universities. This would allow observing the Colombian students' needs and how these are provided by the country where they are studying. In this way, the HEIs in the UK could develop specific policies to improve their recruitment strategies.

5.10. Conclusion and Final Comments

The findings of this research provided context and discussion on the effectiveness of marketing strategies from Colombian students' and agents' points of view in order to enhance recruitment and improve the retention of these students.

This study supported the literature review on the importance of coordination between the HEIs recruitment strategies and the Colombian students' educational needs and extended the literature by analysing the models and theories that must be used in the educational sector to attract new markets, understanding the culture and working alongside the policies between countries.

The analysis of this study evaluated the marketing strategies that engage Colombian students and encourage them to apply successfully to HEIs in the UK. Through their experiences, the researcher evaluated the processes that have been used by the institutions and proposed new guidelines that can be applied to improve these recruitment practices. It also seeks that future students receive a better service, taking into account their expectations, needs and culture. The new proposed guidelines contribute to the improvement of the HEIs and agencies' performance following a new international market.

The first objective of this research was to evaluate in detail the effectiveness of the recruitment process. This information was collected taking into account the first moment when the student makes the decision to study, the experience of living in the UK until the completion of their studies (see Figure 2.7 Conceptual Framework and Table 4.3. Thematic coding analysis research question 1). The information was strongly supported by the agents working with this group of students, highlighting the importance of the language and needs that HEIs have not taken into account when registering a Colombian student. The relevant information allows greater understanding of the needs of the customer and the weaknesses and strengths that the HEIs are facing.

The second objective was based mainly on the students and agents' points of view. This information analysed the needs and expectations that students had before traveling, and the results obtained during and after their stay in the UK. (see Table 4.4. Thematic coding analysis research question 2). Agents contributed giving their opinion according to Colombian students' feedback who have used their services.

The third objective was based on the examination of the secondary data collection in the Literature Review, with the primary data collected from students and agents. This information identified the strategies used by HEIs, their performance in the international market and the use of marketing strategies and their effectiveness (see Table 4.5. Thematic coding analysis research question 3).

The fourth objective was achieved by analysing the primary data in the semi-structured interviews (See Table 4.6. Thematic coding analysis research question 4), the literature research and the proposals offered by students and agents. Specific guidelines were created, which can help to improve the performance of the institutions according to the opinions of interviewees. It is concluded that universities seek to improve their services, but few research studies show in detail these needs according to the Latin American community and specifically the Colombian market, as has been done in this study.

One of the most relevant aspects in this research is the use of the marketing models studied in depth in the literature review and the practices of HEIs. These theoretical concepts improve the practices and strategies in HEIs regarding Colombian students' experiences. The data collected provides a unique, rich information from agents and students that discloses the historical and cultural aspects from their point of view regarding the UK institutions where they studied.

5.11. Summary

HEIs in the UK are aware of their competitiveness and the effects of globalisation; for this reason, top universities in the UK find it easier to recruit students due to the prestige and image of the institutions (Ozturgut, 2013). Students tend to be analytical and critical when deciding to travel overseas; their preference for the United Kingdom is seen, the quality of education it offers, plus the advantage of being able to travel to other countries on holiday. To students, word of mouth is important because they find tips that help them save money and time. (Zeithaml et al., 2010).

Every year, international non-EU students tier 4 visa, have the uncertainty about new regulations and the way these might affect or benefit their academic and professional objectives. Added to this problem is the impact that Brexit will have on the educational regulations, economy, and the fluctuation of the currency.

Higher education should be a national priority to improve international competitiveness. This is possible if there is a continuous effort by the parties, such as government departments, institutions, and national agencies. The inclusion in the strategies of the post-study work opportunity is a global attraction that the UK can learn from its competitors (ICEF Monitor, 2019).

The research extends the literature showing that strategic plans in the institutions are relatively new, but these seek to find new directions, motivations to implement new strategic plans and help to achieve the objectives proposed. The strategic plans created by HEIs reflect how they adopt new challenges, knowledge and

skills to become more competitive internationally. The practice of sustainable design through teaching programs and research must be emphasised in an environment of cultural and intercultural diversity.

This study explores the marketing mix, marketing retention and other models that can be applied to increase the recruitment of international students. HEIs must invest in online marketing resources, social media and representatives, as it was explained in detail in the literature review. On the other hand, it is particularly important from the customer service point of view, the knowledge of the new market, culture, language and needs, as it was found through the students' experiences in the analysis of the data gathered.

The role of the external agents is important; thus, institutions must create close relations with these agencies due as international recruitment of students must be included in the admissions practices to avoid conflicts in the practice of admissions, faculties and institutional staff. It should be taken into account that the alignment with the students' expectations is created from the moment they contact and apply to the university.

This research shows the importance of balancing the practices of the HEIs their recruitment strategies and their internal processes as the expectations of the international students according to the professional and personal needs.

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7. APPENDICES

Volume 2

Appendix A, Colombian students and Representatives' semi structured Interviews

Appendix B, N-VIVO thematic coding analysis research questions 1 to 4

Appendix C, Colombian students and Representatives Interviews translated into English

Appendix D, Colombian students and Representatives Interviews transcripts in Spanish

Appendix E, USB with interviews recorded

Appendices D and E would be added if they are required as evidence and reliability